

**Examining the influence of Organisational Commitment on
Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB): A study of employees'
perception in the context of a university setting in Pakistan**

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DEDICATION

I dedicate my work to the Imam of our time Sahib-e-Zama, Imam-al asr ajf. I am grateful to Almighty Allah and my Maula for endless reasons.

I am thankful to my parents (Shabnam and Abbas) and my grandparents. My grandmother (Suraiya) has always encouraged me to progress in my academic career, who has been standing like a pillar during this journey. I am grateful to my late Grandfathers (Ch Riaz Butter and Ch Ghulam Qadir) who have always been proud of my achievements, but they could not live to see my success today. It is the fruit of their endless prayers that God has enabled me to complete my thesis.

I would also like to thank specially Amad Ali because I wouldn't have been able to complete this project without his guidance and support.

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PERSONAL DETAILS

May 27, 1991.....	Born in PAKISTAN
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AUTHOR’S DECLARATION

I affirm that this dissertation is my own work. It represents my thoughts in my original words, all the analyses, the findings and conclusions which have been included in this study are my own. The study entitled “*examining the influence of organisational commitment organisational citizenship behaviour: A study of employees’ perception in the context of a university setting in Pakistan*” is purely my work, except where it has been otherwise acknowledged. Also, I declare that this study does not contain any content which has been submitted previously for any other award, diploma, or degree program by any other candidate, except where it has been otherwise indicated in the dissertation work.

STUDY ABSTRACT

The study is mainly concerned with the extension of present knowledge related to organisational commitment to demonstrate its influence on organisational citizenship behaviour, organisational and individual performance within the field of management. The qualitative study investigates the effect of the constituents of commitment on employee perceptions of organisational commitment despite many positive and significant views of organisational commitment as a significant component to build organisational citizenship behaviour from employees' perspective.

A qualitative research design has been adopted in this thesis. The employees' perceptions are the base of qualitative study and the current literature helps to explore the theoretical aspect of the influence of organisational commitment on organisational citizenship behaviour in the context of a university setting in Pakistan.

The current thesis as the foremost researchers on the concept of organisational commitment s conceptualised and operationalised the focal construct, its components. This study has been expected to be a value addition in the current body of knowledge to a threefold contribution by extending the theory in the literature, enhancing the conceptual understanding, measuring, testing, and generalising the theory. In addition, it is desired that these research findings will make a significant managerial impact on the comprehension of decision-makers in the organisation about the overall association between a favourable organisational commitment, its antecedents, and its key consequences. The relevant concepts and their dimensions' clear understanding can support the managers to enhance organisational commitment, favourable organisational citizenship behaviour, organisational and individual performance.

The study sought to gain a comprehension of the constructs, some antecedents, and outcomes of organisational commitment, even though there are some limitations in the sample/analysis and measurement methods. Therefore, there have been given additional suggestions in the expectation of incorporating unique directions of research to inspire further research and investigations in the domain of the conceptualisation, antecedents, and consequences of organisational commitment.

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter consists of the background of the research study, the problem statement of the research work, the background of organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB), the research objectives, methodology, significance of research study, and compiled thesis structure. This chapter consists of a total of eight sections. Section 1.2 describes the background of this research study. Section 1.3 explains the problem statement for this research. Section 1.4 describes the background of OCB. Section 1.5 briefs the objectives, and section 1.6 consists of the methodology. Section 1.7 expresses the significance of the current research study. Finally, section 1.8 details the main structure of the thesis.

1.2. BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The study of behaviours within organisational settings has highlighted critical variables that are detrimental to the performance of organisations. (Pohlman and Gardiner, 2000). Organisational corporate social responsibility and organisational commitment are widely studied factors in management literature in different contexts (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Parker *et al.*, 2005; Bodla and Danish, 2009; Bodla and Naeem, 2009; Lorena *et al.*, 2020), which are the precursors of organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) (Tindowen and Mandezabal, 2020). According to Mandezabal (2020), more attention has been given to the employees' behaviour for more than seventy-five years. These behaviours are referred to the attributes of the individual employee by virtue of which an individual behaves better than others as compared to the employees of the other organisations where characteristics related to cooperative behaviour are not considered (Akhtar, 2019).

Organisational commitment encompasses the employees' emotional attachment to the work and identification with the workplace (Meyer and Allen, 1991). The attitudinal construct is more related to the acceptance of organisational objectives and values, willingness to go the extra mile for the organisational goal, and an intention to maintain association with the organisation (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020). According to Meyer and Allen

(1991), commitment is a multi-dimensional concept encompassing the affective commitment (employee's emotional affiliation to the organisation), continuance commitment (employee's perception of the costs related to leaving the organisation), and normative commitment (employees feeling of responsibility to continue working with the organisation) (Khan and Sharjeel, 2019). Although, it is obvious that individual attitudes affect the overall behaviour in the firm. In terms of attitude, organisational commitment is likely to influence organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) (Buchanan and Huczynski, 2019; Kim *et al.*, 2019). This has logical validity because employees within an organisation who feel emotionally attached to the organisation, on behalf of the organisation, should sensibly go an extra mile (Odhiambo, 2019).

Moreover, employee commitment can be seen as an attitudinal indicator that is recommended by social exchange theories. Thus, it relates to the extent to which employees within an organisation observe themselves to be in high-quality social exchange organisational relationships (Lavelle *et al.*, 2009). Hence, an employee may show commitment to the organisation as a result and in exchange for supportive and good conduct from the organisation, which ultimately prompts employees to feel obligated to the work and workplace. Additionally, it engages employees in citizenship behaviours (OCB), particularly many empirical studies support a consistent relationship between affective commitment and OCB (Organ and Ryan, 1995; Hoffman, Blair, Meriac, and Woehr, 2007; Penate *et al.*, 2020).

In developing countries (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Van Riel *et al.*, 2001; Akhtar, 2019), despite its significant economic and social importance. Globally, many universities have also incorporated organisational commitment into their process's development programs and even mission and visions (Tindowen and Mandezabal, 2020). However, research on policies and practices of organisational organisational commitment is significantly limited in higher education sector (Fischer *et al.*, 2020). Thus, this study aims to highlight how organisational commitment results in organisational citizenship behaviour, OCB. Organisational commitment is considered as the precedent of organisational citizenship behaviour, and the relationship between individual performance and organisational performance is also well established (Penate *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, perceptions of employee organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour are investigated in this study (Akhtar, 2019).

According to scholars (e.g., Penate *et al.*, 2020), these constructs are more essential to study in higher education context where universities are the sole medium to educate the intellect of

nations. However, the overall organisational performance of an educational set up depends on the commitment of academic and non-academic employees ultimately (Akhtar, 2019). Therefore, understating the employee perception of organisational commitment needs more attention (Ali *et al.*, 2020). Organisation commitment refers to the emotional attachment of employees, sense of identification, and involvement in the organisation. It is generally considered as a three-dimensional construct comprising of affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment (Allen and Meyer, 1996; Karrasch, 2003; Turner and Chelladurai, 2005; Boehman, 2006; Canipe, 2006; Greenberg, 2005; Ali *et al.*, 2020).

Raza *et al.* (2020) denotes commitment is defined as “strong belief in and acceptance of the organisational goals and values, willingness to exert considerable effort on behalf of the organisation, and a definite desire to maintain organisational membership”. (Kim, 2014; Ali and Aziz, 2018; Rapp-Ricciardi *et al.*, 2018). Jans (1989) and Otter (2015) has defined it as the extent that an employee accepts, internalises, and perceives one’s role based on organisational values and goals (Raza and Imtiaz, 2020). Organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) assists in innovation, adaptability and resource transformation to improve the efficiency of the organisation (Greenberg, 2005; Canipe, 2006; Ali *et al.*, 2020), but OCB is not documented in the contract of an employee. However, such type of behaviour is always desirable by the organisation to enhance the performance of an employee (Fawzy and Shore, 2020). The formal job responsibilities do not perceive the actions of OCB (Xiong and Wen, 2020).

In organisational behaviour research in recent years, organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is one of the most widely studied topics (Khalid and Ali, 2005; Ahmad *et al.*, 2020). Bateman and Organ (1980) introduced the concept of OCB, it was refined and further strengthened by several scholars (Jahangir *et al.*, 2004; Khalid and Ali 2005; Ahmad *et al.*, 2020). A special type of work behaviour defined by Organ (1995), as individual behaviours that are beneficial to the organisation and are discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognised by the formal reward system are organisational citizenship behaviours (Khalid and Ali 2005; Ahmad *et al.*, 2020). These behaviours are mainly of volunteer choice, and their omission is not considered punishable in the organisations. Research holds different views regarding the dimensions of OCB (Ahmad *et al.*, 2020). In this regard, Smith *et al.* (1983) conceptualised OCB with two dimensions: altruism (behaviour targeted at helping individuals specifically) and generalised compliance behaviour reflecting compliance with norms, general rules and expectations (Ahmad *et al.*, 2020).

Further, Organ (1988) identified five dimensions of OCB, namely civic virtue, altruism, courtesy, conscientiousness, and sportsmanship (Law and Chuah, 2020). Organ (1988) further explained that the efficiency and productivity of both the employees and the organisation could be maximised through OCB that ultimately contributing to the effective working of an organisation (Tindowen and Mandezabal, 2020). The flow of intense knowledge and awareness has increased the competition amongst the organisations. Therefore, organisations are required to upgrade the behaviour of the employees as per the goals of the organisation in order to gain a competitive advantage (Buchanan and Huczynski, 2019; Kim *et al.*, 2019). Rahayu *et al.* (2019) argued that the clear direction sense given to employees using the training and development program might be helpful in obtaining the goals of an organisation. The employees who are aware of the decision-making criteria in the organisation perform better than others. Hence, an environment of empowering the employees is helpful in improving the professionalism, leadership, and quality of the work (Paramaatha *et al.*, 2019). The organisations in which policies regarding the work-life environment are present are more effective in transforming themselves into a learning organisation (Law and Chuah, 2020). The teachers are the central part of the education system and act as a backbone in the country's development with the help of an exemplary system of education (Odhiambo, 2019). The quality and ability of the teachers are determinants of the success of a system of education (Tindowen and Mandezabal, 2020).

Alayoubi *et al.* (2020) suggested that the high-quality teaching services are dependent upon the ways by which organisation provides services to the employees within the firm. The previous studies suggested that highly committed faculty members of an organisation involve themselves in their institutions in which they work, and they try their level best to highly perform to achieve the organisational goals (Farooq, 2019). The current study is being carried out on the employees in higher education settings. Hence, it is necessary to understand how the processes and policies impact the staff, which ultimately determines the success criteria of organisational and individual performance (Khan and Sharjeel, 2019). Qureshi and Paramaatha (2019) argued that the higher education sector is an under-researched area in developing countries. Therefore, this research shall illustrate the themes by virtue of which supportive and corporative behaviours of the employees in higher education settings may be improved (Odhiambo, 2019). This study shall help the other scholars analyse the effect of

organisational commitment on the OCB, particularly in the context of higher education settings.

1.3. RATIONALE

Education as a business has gained global attention. The reason of selecting universities as a point of focus in this study is due to its significance importance in the social and economical development in any country. The teachers are the role models for students and the universities as the important social institutions impact the behaviour, development and progress of the youth of a nation. The provision of quality education is the main aim of the universities due to such a competitive environment when universities are in competition of attaining high ranking as compared to other universities (Khalid and Ali, 2005; Ahmad et al., 2020) . The point to ponder is, why some teachers and some universities are more dedicated and committed to provide better services and care about the student development and progress? On the other hand, some teachers and institutions do not go extra mile and they care more about business than the quality of service they provide? There might be various factors that determine the behaviour of employees working in universities as managers, teachers and administrative staff. In the context of Pakistan as a developing nation, universities are crucial as they are responsible to shape the behaviour of students, attitude towards work, professionalism and the industrial knowledge and skills to be a competitive graduate. The students reflect the set of attributes what they get in the classroom from their teachers (Naz et al., 2020).

In this study the factors that impact overall organisational commitment of employees are going to be explored and investigated and their impact on organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) which triggers the employees to go extra mile being a discretionary behaviour. These factors are responsible and impact OCB which defines this behaviour as a discretionary behaviour (Ababneh, 2020). Researchers started concentrating on the employee behaviour nearly 65 years ago. This categorisation of unique employee traits made it clear why some employees behave more devotedly than others. (Sanders & Koster, 2006). Being a good corporate citizen benefits resources by enabling them to change, adapt, and innovate, which boosts the effectiveness of the firm. However, no contract calls for it, and the typical employee does not really expect it. (Turnipseed & Murkison, 1996).

Organisational citizenship behaviour refers to the behaviours that are not prescribed or mandated by the formal employment requirements. (Farh, Zhong, and Organ, 2004). Businesses today confront fierce competition as a result of the tremendous flow of information and awareness. To maintain their competitive advantage, organisations must adapt quickly, which necessitates a high level of employee dedication (Lok and Crawford, 2001).

Organisational commitment is closely related to the concept of organisational citizenship behaviour. Many organisational factors highlighted in this study help to achieve organisational commitment goals when there is a clear sense of direction (Wilson & Western, 2000). Teachers with decision-making authority in a favourable organisational structure, management style, organisational justice, organisational culture and climate take part in decisions that have an impact on teaching and learning. Empowered work environments assist to enhance professionalism, teacher leadership, and the quality of work life (Henkin, and Duemer, 2002).

Firms become passionate learning organisations as a result of the environment in which favourable factors work-life rules are provided, which determines the learning that takes place in businesses. (Yong, 2000). The backbone of each developing country is considered to be its robust educational system, with teachers playing a key role. The ability and calibre of a system's teachers affect how well it performs. (Joolideh & Yeshodhara, 2008). The argument made by Bienstock, DeMoranville, and Smith in 2003 holds that the method in which employees provide their services affects how high-quality those services are. Studies in the past have shown that highly committed academic staff employees stay active in their current organisations and work hard to deliver excellent work for them. (Chughtai & Zafar, 2006).

This research is carried out among Pakistani university faculty members because the importance of picking these subject stems from the fact that instructors play a significant role in boosting the quality of education. Raising educational quality is a top priority for the Pakistani government. According to the National Education Census 2005/2006, there are 227,791 educational institutions that provide 33.4 million students with a variety of educational opportunities. From pre-primary to university level, the system employs 1.356 million teachers.

Pakistan has 49 general universities and 11,434 teachers working there. The primary challenges and concerns with teacher education in Pakistan over the past 30 years have been the subject of numerous research. (National Professional Standards for Teachers in Pakistan, 2009).

Per the Ayca et al., (2000) Pakistan is the nation that has received the least quantity of research. As a result, the main objective of this study is to examine the prevalence of OCB among university academics in Pakistan. Universities are where high-level education is offered; hence its quality and delivery are crucial. This study will explain the factors that influence why some teachers act more empathetically and cooperatively than others.

As quality depends on working culture, climate and working environment and professional growth, teachers' work cannot be separated from it. Participation from everyone involved in teaching and learning is necessary for high-quality growth. (Odhiambo,2008). This research will help other researchers better understand how organisational commitment affects OCB, especially in the context of Pakistani university teachers. It will also demonstrate the significance of OCB in increasing an organisation's effectiveness and pinpoint the factors that either cause or affect OCB.

This study will also demonstrate how organisational commitment is related to organisational factors, empowerment practises, work-life regulations, and training and development opportunities, and how organisational commitment influences how Pakistani university staff behave in terms of organisational citizenship. This study will evaluate the impact of staffs' commitment on the success of the universities.

1.4. STUDY OBJECTIVES AND STUDY QUESTIONS

The main concerns of a manager are to motivate the employees of the organisation for cooperating with successful businesses (Shao and Ariss, 2020), as it is going to be more challenging and difficult because of the uncertainty of the environment of work. Therefore, nowadays, the complex type of business in the world requires that employees of an organisation perform up to the required level in order to attain the goals of the organisation. This type of space added demand of the worker at every level of the organisation (Navarro *et al.*, 2020). A deep understanding of technology and the performances of the various activities are required for different companies (Yu, 2020). The intonation and corporation beyond the formal type of the job descriptions are significantly required for the organisation as it is not possible from points of view of the organisation in prediction every type of attitude (Georgellis, 2015;

Tindowen, 2019). Hence, refined organisational commitment is required from the employees of the organisation when making changes in the environment that surround them (Surty and Scheepers, 2020). The flexibilities are required in order to adjust the changes in the organisation. It is proven that the changes in organisations result in “unexpected extra mile” (Kanter, 1989, p. 91) and to cope with the uncertain conditions, it is necessary to control the organisational commitment and behaviour of the employees under the educational setup of the university. The informal types of relations are based on self-defined, adaptable and voluntary behaviour as these are also expected as per the mandate of the organisational culture and obligations of the contract (Shields *et al.*, 2020).

The main objective of the study is to sort out the best working conditions which yield the best performance of the individual and the educational organisation as well. The behaviour of the workers is required to be organised beyond the traditional types of the roles relevant to the efficiencies (such as quality, quantity and work output). Therefore, it is the main objective of the study to introduce the environment of the OCB in the organisation in which workers perform beyond the job responsibilities voluntarily (Shields *et al.*, 2020). The OCBs are described as the “individual behaviours that are discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognised by the formal reward system, and that in the aggregate promote the effective functioning of the organisation” (Organn *et al.*, 2006, p. 3). This is cooperative and helpful behaviour of the individual, which helps in lubricating the machinery of the social society where the organisation is persisting. The main objective of this behaviour is to improve efficiency, provide flexibility and decrease the friction between society and the organisations (Guinot and Chiva, 2019). Obeying the regulations and rules help the co-worker keep them abreast of changes in the organisation while neglecting the faults which organisations made against the employees are because of the behaviour of the employee having OCB. Four research objectives of the study are as follow:

1. To critically review the existing literature identifying the factors that most likely to have a significant influence on organisational organisational commitment.
2. To investigate the perceptions of employees on organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour in the higher educational context.
3. To investigate the outcome of organisational commitment as organisational citizenship

behaviour (OCB) and organisational performance.

4. To develop and propose recommendations to the management to enhance organisational commitment impacting organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational performance.

The major research questions which are important to be asked as a major source of the qualitative or quantitative study are given below:

Question 1: What are the factors that are impacting the organisational commitment among employees in university settings in Pakistan?

Question 2: How organisational commitment impacts organisational citizenship behaviour in the organisations?

Question 3: How organisational citizenship behaviour impacts organisational performance?

Question 4: What are the steps that can be taken by the management to enhance employee perceptions regarding organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour?

Thus, the study by (Odhiambo, 2019) proves that OCB has a direct positive relationship with the individual as well as the organisational performance in the context of university settings in order to improve the performance of the educational institute. Similarly, the organisational commitment and organisational corporate social responsibility are required to be studied in terms of the organisational culture, organisational structure, organisational justice, organisational climate, employee behaviour and management style to improve the performance of the individuals and educational institutes (Aguiar-Quintana *et al.*, 2020; Donglong *et al.*, 2020; Kim and Holland, 2020).

1.5. STUDY DESIGN AND ANALYTICAL METHOD

The research study is conducted based on qualitative analysis. The data of the required respondents for the qualitative interview has been collected using the online recruitment

process with the help of advertising on the available online media. The shortlisted candidates shall be called for the qualitative interview. The data of the interviews have been recorded, interpreted analysed using NVivo (Welsh, 2002). The data analysis has been presented in the form of coding as presented by the NVivo. The coding in the NVivo has been done as per the antecedents, moderators, dependent and independent variable's relationships. The manual coding has also been conducted along with NVivo for data triangulation reliability and validity in the analysis.

1.6. STATEMENT OF SIGNIFICANCE

This study aims to add to the existing research for a better understanding of the organisational commitment concept. The research outcomes attempt to extend the literature on management and specifically organisational commitment. Moreover, this study contributes to the theoretical, methodological, and managerial areas (find the full details of this section in Chapter 8, Section 8.2 implications of research findings).

In this research, the empirical findings presented does not only encompass previous findings in commitment-related research but also add to research on commitment, management and organisational citizenship behaviour literature. This research enhances the current view of organisational commitment and its outcomes (organisational citizenship behaviour and performance). The gaps found in the literature have been bridged by the key contributions of this research, i.e., *what are the factors that are impacting the organisational commitment among employees in university settings in Pakistan? How organisational commitment impacts organisational citizenship behaviour in the organisations? How organisational citizenship behaviour impacts organisational performance? What are the steps that can be taken by the management to enhance employee perceptions regarding organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour?*

The literature gaps have been summarised as follows:

- 1) The previous research on the relationship of organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour and performance was done in the context of private universities only. Therefore, the research could have been done in

both public and private sectors with a wider scope of area (Ridwan *et al.*, 2020). Such as Noor (2009) have investigated the impact of training and development on commitment where many other factors have not been considered in the context of Pakistani universities. Therefore, it is required to investigate other factors impacting organisational commitment and citizenship behaviour in the context of Pakistani universities.

- 2) The Meyer and Allen scale was used to measure employee commitment as it relates to affective, normative, and continuance dimensions of commitment (Singh & Gupta, 2015). Findings indicate that even though employees exhibited higher rates of commitment based on team or professional affiliation and loyalty, there are significant differences in various organisations in terms of how employees perceive affiliations based on the existing organizational factors (Singh & Gupta, 2015). The previous research on different contributing factors and consequences of organisational commitment was done from the perception of academic staff and in different industries not considering many factors in one study, but new research can be conducted with respondents having administrative and managerial positions in the universities as it has not been studied extensively before (Wilkanandya *et al.*, 2020).
- 3) Employees belonging to a collectivist society are found to be more strongly engaged in OCB. Individual differences are a weak predictor of OCB (Moorman & Blakely, 1995). Van Dyne *et al.* (2000) found that there is a strong and significant link between collectivism, individual differences and perceived trust on organisational citizenship behaviour. The perception of organisational justice and OCB varies in accordance to the national culture; this evidence is found by Ang, Dyne and Begley (2003). They conducted research across nations to measure the OCB of employees belonging to different cultures. Cohen (2006) also found that cultural differences especially individualistic or collectivist orientation does have an impact on organisational citizenship behaviour. He argued that collectivist cultures encourage OCB. A little has been investigated on the relationship between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour in Pakistani university context from employees' perceptions of the organization. So, this study shall explore more

about the relationship in the light of the employee's perception (Ayesha Noor, 2009; Evans *et al.*, 2020).

- 4) According to Oplatka (2006) and Hannam and Jimmieson (2002), there is very little research carried on organisational commitment and OCB in the context of universities, it needs some serious attention. The university staff commitment particularly teachers' commitment and OCB can be seen in three forms. First is involvement in novel and initiative actions. Second is helping the colleagues in their job and third is improving and helping the students and teaching them with positivism and helping them in getting their targets (Somech & Drach-Zahavy, 2000). According to Yucel (2008) all the employees especially teachers play an important role in improving the organisations and students. Teachers with high commitment and OCB have more value as compared to other because academic institution is dependent on them. Teacher's relationship with students is strong in high achieving institutions as compared to lower achieving universities (Shann, 1998). Therefore, it means organisational commitment and OCB is practiced more in high achieving universities than the low achieving universities. There needs to be a study about the commitment in the university settings (Hussain and Khan, 2020; Michele *et al.*, 2020).

- 5) Quality of relationship amongst the teachers and the other departments of educational institutions are determined by many factors such as employee behaviour, perceived organisational justice and support, perceived organisational structure, climate, culture, management style, rewards systems and job satisfaction. These are the factors that determine OCB in an educational institution. These factors have a strong impact on organisational commitment and yields OCB of employees in universities and teachers (Garg & Rastogi, 2006). Organisational commitment is influenced by management style, organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational climate, employee behaviour and organisational justice has a direct relationship with OCB, performance of employees and OCB therefore this performance includes OCB. These organisational factors should be very favourable in order to make this relationship effective (Gadot, 2006). Management literature requires to shed more light and encompass these factors in a study which can help to

enhance the managerial comprehension to effectively support the university to increase employee organisational commitment and OCB. on employee perception of commitment and OCB (Abugre, 2020; Donglong *et al.*, 2020; Holland and Kim, 2020).

This study demonstrates the relevant associations between organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational performance in the context of university settings. Hence, this study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by enhancing findings of previous studies. For example, many researchers (Allen and Meyer, 1996; Greenberg, 2005; Ali *et al.*, 2020) suggest that organisational commitment is related to organisational citizenship behaviour, but they have rarely examined this relationship. Although a recent study by (Kim *et al.*, 2019; D'Aprile and McLay, 2020) investigated organisational commitment but these studies were not conducted in relation to organisational citizenship behaviour and performance. Researchers (Allen and Meyer, 1996; Kim *et al.*, 2019; Ali *et al.*, 2020) results contribute to filling the existing theory gap in this research area. The present study, hence, extends past studies by investigating the relationship between organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour and performance.

The current study contributes theoretically to the existing body of knowledge by adding different insights to organisational commitment. (Allen and Meyer, 1996; Karrasch, 2003; Turner and Chelladurai, 2005; Kim *et al.*, 2019; Ali *et al.*, 2020). The study also contributes to redefining research into the field of organisational commitment. Hence, this study contributes to the extension of the understanding of organisational commitment and strengthen the relationship between organisational commitment, its antecedents, and consequences (organisational citizenship behaviour and performance).

The research is therefore also able to add to employee management theory. Organisational commitment has received the management authors' attention (Allen and Meyer, 1996; Karrasch, 2003; Holland and Kim, 2020). The contribution made by this research supports to hold a broader view of employee commitment as well as employee engagement by exploring whether the integration of organisational commitment influences the organisational citizenship behaviour and performance of employees of a firm. This research results in several implications for managers. Firstly, this research suggests managers must comprehend that organisational commitment is a wide and complex phenomenon that is determined by various factors such as

organisational structure, culture, justice, employee behaviour and management style. It also suggests that managers should pay attention to building and retaining employee commitment by enhancing factors that influence organisational citizenship behaviour. The characteristics of the job and other factors which influence the relationship between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour, which yield performance in the organisation, are yet to be understood and implemented by managers. (Ode and Nasrullah, 2020).

Moreover, the research identified the critical factors required to achieve a favourable organisational commitment. Therefore, the research findings are of utmost importance for decision-makers such as leaders and managers as they play a fundamental role in the development of an organisation's culture. Managers need to carefully devise the policies related to organisational structure, justice, management style, culture, climate, and the overall atmosphere, as these are the main factors that contribute to the favourable organisational commitment. The findings indicate that there is a direct relationship between organisational commitment, its antecedents, and consequences. In addition, there are implications for the managers and administrators: to develop and retain commitment, there must be more implication of the factors that contribute to organisational citizenship behaviour.

The need for consistency in managerial communications to help the employees understand the policies, values and beliefs related to corporate social responsibility, commitment and organisational is significant. Furthermore, managers should give more emphasis to employee commitment which influences organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour and performance.

1.7. IMPORTANT CONCEPTS AND CONSTRUCTS DEFINITIONS

Organisational structure is defined as the structure of interrelated events, the way people get organised and they are coordinated and divided (Katz, 1978; Tasic, 2019) by which work is divided in different tasks (Mintzberg, 1983; Toft and Liefermann, 2020) in order to formally allocate the work roles (Child, 1972; Turi and Sorooshian, 2019) by formalisation, hierarchy

layers, integration levels, authority centralisation and communication patterns in the organisation (Thompson, 1966; Ehiorobo *et al.*, 2020) to coordinate, conduct and control the activities of the organisation for responsibilities fulfilment and power distribution (Jackson, 1982; Alown *et al.*, 2020).

Organisational culture is defined as the assumptions about ways of working process (Hampden-Turner, 1990; Tyagi and Moses, 2020) in an acceptable pattern ensuring internal integration and adaption to new ways (Bate, 1994; Tyagi and Moses, 2020) which encourages the members to contribute more to the organisation towards the problem solving (Linstead, 1992; Alqadre, 2019) through shared beliefs, behaviour and values among employees (Schein, 1991; Wiley *et al.*, 2020) and this type of organisational culture may also refer to as corporate culture (Hampden-Turner, 1990; Tyagi and Moses, 2020).

Organisational justice is defined as a fair manner of resources allocation (Lee, 2001; Engelbrecht and Samuel, 2019) to reward the employees (Adams, 1963; Shahid *et al.*, 2020) to enhance the organisation-employee relationship (Bies and Tyler, 1990; Olowookere *et al.*, 2020) by correct decision making of the top management (Cropanzano *et al.*, 2001; Olowookere *et al.*, 2020) and normally divided into three types of interactional, procedural and distributive justice (Colquitt, 2002; Alsaree, 2020).

Organisational climate is defined as sentimental, intellectual and influential environment (Carr *et al.*, 2003; Goswami *et al.*, 2020) of personal wellbeing of employees (Leigh, 1996; Ali *et al.*, 2020) to build ethical attitude of the policies, corporate behaviour of employee (Vidaver Cohen, 1998; Jha and Singh, 2019) to enhance organisational commitment (Brown, 1996; Shinde *et al.*, 2020) in instrumental, cognitive and affective dimensional atmosphere of an organisation (Ostroff, 1993; Omole *et al.*, 2019; Malhota and Sharom, 2020).

Employee behaviour is defined as a behaviour which construes the activities of the organisations (Birnbaum and Somers, 2000; Choi *et al.*, 2020) to integrate the individual attitudes with the motives of the organisation (Guest, 1987; Landers, 2019) by developing and integrating the values and regulations (Arthur, 1994; Chaudhary, 2020) which connects employee's needs with organisational goals and reaction of employees to certain situations (Walton, 1985; Williams, 2004; Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Kim and Luengalongkot, 2020).

Management style is defined as success striving style of management (Mintzberg, 1980; Wirtz, 2019) which controls, co-ordinates, organises and plans activities (Henry, 1916; Saxena, 2019) in a team leading and power management manner (Thomas, 1994; Hastings *et al.*, 2019) for improving effectiveness (Margerison, 1979; Arsto *et al.*, 2019) by interpersonal characteristics of making decisions to achieve the main objectives of an organisation (Elwood, 1990; Titon and Pettan, 2019; Yin and Liao, 2020).

Organisational commitment is defined as the attachment of an employee to the organisation (Lambert, 2003; Jameel *et al.*, 2020) through devotion to the objectives (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Poltcon and Cansoy, 2019) to be identified and involved with the organisation (Meyer, 1990; Hawkins, 2019) and perceiving cost while thinking to leave an organization which helps to sustain an of environment obligation (Meyer and Allen, 1990; Yigit, 2016; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020; Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021). It is a state where employees adopt the values, goals, and objectives of the organisation as their own goals and they feel highly involved and encouraged therefore they aim to stay in the organisation (Nguyen *et al.*, 2020; Soelton *et al.*, 2020; Noermijati *et al.*, 2021).

Job satisfaction is defined as an effective orientation of employee towards the role assigned to him (Vroom, 1964; Orgambidez and Extremera, 2020; Saputra and Riana, 2021) to the extent by which employee is rewarded (Moorman *et al.*, 1993; Statt, 2004; Indarti *et al.*, 2017; Candelario *et al.*, 2020) in suitable environmental, psychological, and physiological conditions (Hoppock, 1935; Madhukar and Sharma, 2017; Romi and Ahman, 2020) by fulfilling both psychological and material needs of an employee (Moorman *et al.*, 1993; Aziri, 2008; Prasetyo *et al.*, 2017; Asgari *et al.*, 2020; Moustofa and Muafi, 2021) to get sum of believes and feelings that employee have about their job at workplace (George *et al.*, 2008; Kanimozhi, 2019; Silitonga *et al.*, 2020; Karuna, 2021).

Organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is the engagement which is expressed by an individual outside the expected role (Organ, 1988; Podsakoff *et al.*, 2000; Lambert, 2003; Jameel *et al.*, 2020) by devoting the efforts towards the objectives of the organisation to an extra mile (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Hall *et al.*, 2009; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Teng *et al.*, 2020) to be attached and get identified in the organisation (Organ and Bateman, 1983; Meyer, 1990; Hawkins, 2019; Ahmad and Kaleem, 2020) without any expectation of formal rewards (Allen, 1990; Appelbaum *et al.*, 2004; Kuncoro and Wibowo, 2019) that results in increase in

effectiveness and performance of the organisation (Meyer and Allen, 1990; Kloutsiniotis and Mihail, 2020; Rao and Zaidi, 2020).

Individual performance is defined as the state of employees fulfilling the job requirements (Lodahl, 1965) to the extent that it enhances job commitment and involvement (Kanungo, 1982a; Febrina and Syamsir, 2020) to engage and pre-occupy to the responsibilities given (Paullay *et al.*, 1994; Truss *et al.*, 2013; Fontannaz and Osthuizen, 2007; Bakotic, 2016) by indulging and involving effectively and efficiently with the work yielding required results (Kanungo, 1982b; Tenrisau *et al.*, 2019; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020).

Organisational performance is defined as the capability of an organisation to attain its main objectives (Daft, 2000; Bakotic, 2016; Moneva *et al.*, 2020) of economic efficiency and effectiveness (Chandler, 1993; Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019; Haque, 2020; Bhuiyan *et al.*, 2020) as an aspect of productivity in consistent and quality control manner (Hefferman and Flood, 2000; Pinho *et al.*, 2014; Asif *et al.*, 2019; Moneva *et al.*, 2020) which indicates the consistency, quality, and other aspects (Waggoner *et al.*, 1999; Wade, 2001; Ongori, 2009; Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019; Haque, 2020).

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. INTRODUCTION

The chapter is comprised of the concepts relevant to the organisational commitment are discussed in the section 2.2 of this chapter. The concept of organisational commitment is an integral part of this chapter, and it is discussed under section 2.3. The theoretical approaches to organisational commitment as per theories is described in the section 2.4 of this chapter. The social exchange and psychological approaches are detailed in this section as well. The organisational commitment is described in detail on the bases of the theories and concepts in the section 2.5. The antecedents of the organisational commitment are expressed under section 2.6 of this chapter. The definitions related to organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate, employee behaviour and management style are described under sub sections of 2.6. The consequences of the organisational commitment are described in the section 2.7. The organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB), individual performances and organisational performance are described in the sub-sections of 2.7. The moderators of the organisational commitment are explained in the section 2.8 of this chapter. The job satisfaction is described in the sub-section of 2.8. The moderators of the OCB are discussed in the section 2.9 of the chapter. In the end, the summarised description of the chapter is discussed.

2.2. ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT AND RELATED CONCEPTS

The terms commitment and engagement, according to Meyer *et al.* (1991) are frequently used interchangeably in both verbally and in writing, as well as in some corporate definitions. It has been claimed by authors (Schaufeli and Baker, 2010; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020) that the concept of engagement only has been worthless if engagement and organisational commitment are regarded similar. Similarly, according to (Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Hardiningsih *et al.*, 2020; Utami *et al.*, 2021) the fact that engagement also seems to have a dimension of how the work is conducted and this clearly distinguishes these two concepts. Engagement is defined by a high level of enthusiasm as well as identification with one's task (Bakker and Leiter, 2010; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020).

The scholars (Staw,1977; Richers,1985; Haque *et al.*, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020) emphasised that work engagement and employee engagement are the two engagement types. According to researchers (Salanick,1977; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020) work engagement refers to the relationship of employees with the job, although employee engagement can also refer to the employee's relationship with the organisation. Since the notion is so close to organisational commitment in this scenario, hence it can be jumbled (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2010; Astuty and Udin, 2020). Work engagement on the other hand, is conceptually distinct from organisational commitment (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2010; Astuty and Udin, 2020).

It is indeed a motivational idea in which employees are enticed to work toward a difficult goal. It also demonstrates the individual enthusiasm that employees bring to their jobs. (Bakker and Leiter, 2010; Supriyanto *et al.*, 2020). Alternatively, Nguyen *et al.* (2020) suggested that employees are motivated to achieve and put forth great effort in all aspects of their work. To sum up, "work engagement is a positive, gratifying, affective-motivational state of wellbeing related to work and can be understood as the opposite of job burnout" (Bakker and Leiter 2010, p. 2; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020). According to Orgambidez and Benitez (2021) workplace engagement is made up of three elements: energy or, dedication, and absorption. The employee's vigour refers to the amount of energy he or she expends daily. Employees are eager to put effort in their work and they are persistent, even when there is difficult work (Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021; Riyanto *et al.*, 2021).

Dedication is defined as a strong devotion that produces positive emotions such as inspiration, importance, pride, and passion. Finally, absorption occurs when an employee is fully focused and engaged in his or her work to the point that time seems to fly by, and it is difficult for him or her to disengage from it (Schaufeli and Salanova, 2007; Halbesleben and Wheeler, 2008; Riyanto *et al.*, 2021). Absorption is sometimes defined as a "flow" emotion that is both stable as well as long-lasting (Hallberg and Schaufeli, 2006; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020; Choudhury *et al.*, 2021).

Therefore, according to the authors (Hallberg and Schaufeli, 2006; Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019; Choudhury *et al.*, 2021; Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021) work engagement and organisational

commitment have one thing in common: they both relate to a significant positive relationship to one's job. These both concepts make theoretical relations to one another. However, Akhtar and Pangil (2020) demonstrated that there really is a theoretical distinction in between these notions. Organisational commitment and work engagement had a 46 latent intercorrelation (Nienaber and Martins, 2020).

Thus, Nienaber and Martins (2020) implied that these are linked but not identical, indicating that these are distinct constructs. Additionally, within these notions, there have also been diverse patterns for relationships between health complaints and job factors (Pio *et al.*, 2018; Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020). Work engagement, as discussed by Masale *et al.*, (2021) was shown to be to be more negatively connected with health complaints, whilst organisational commitment has been found to be more negatively correlated to the intention turnover. Hence, correspondently these concepts are interchangeably used in some contexts, although there are theoretical variations between these two concepts (Nayeema *et al.*, 2021; Tayyab and Saira, 2021; Maleka *et al.*, 2021).

According to Nur *et al.* (2021) social identity as an extension to engagement, is a term that is quite like commitment. Akhtar and Pangil (2020) emphasised that diverse people have had quite different perspectives on the relationship among commitment, identification, and a form of social identity. Whereas, according to scholars (Meyer *et al.*, 2006; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020; Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021) these are occasionally confused, with commitment being perceived as part of identification and identification being antecedent to commitment in some cases. The reason which has been argued is that there is no attempt made to integrate. The idea that social identity includes a person's self-concept such as aspects of a person particularly the group identity, is common to all these conceptions (Riyanto *et al.*, 2021).

Nguyen *et al.* (2020) asserted that both identification and commitment refer to a person's emotional or psychological connection with the organisation, although the nature of the relationship differs. Identification is considered as psychological oneness, whereas commitment shows a bond between two different things (Nienaber and Martins, 2020). Similarly, when an employee identifies with the company, the company's values, standards, and interests become part of the person's self-concept (Tayyab and Saira, 2021). As a result, collective interests are transformed into self-interests. (Van Knippenberg and Sleebos, 2006).

In the research by scholars (Van Knippenberg and Sleebos, 2006; Nienaber and Martins, 2020; Nayeema *et al.*, 2021) they sought to determine whether these two notions are separate. It has been discovered that when it comes to identification and commitment, there are several types of relationship. These two notions overlap in certain ways, but they illustrate separate parts of the organisation-employee relationship, similar to how engagement is differentiated (Tayyab and Saira, 2021).

Finally, various concepts are utilised to defining the association between the employee and the organisation (Genty, 2017; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Haque *et al.*, 2019). Some of the conceptions are similar, however Noermijati *et al.* (2021) asserted that there are empirically validated distinctions as well, as previously stated. According to Nienaber and Martins (2020) the focus in this research will be on organisational commitment, as after acknowledging the significance of organisational commitment, the elements that the organisation can adapt to make their employees more devoted will be explored from the employee's perspective. Therefore, the scholars (Meyer *et al.*, 1991; Salancik, 1977; Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020) suggested the concepts related to personal emotions of vigour and determination are not something that the organisation can easily influence. Hence, from the employee perspective, it is critical to establish an understanding of the elements that influence employees' organisational commitment which would facilitate to identify and examine the ways to strengthen it.

2.3. BACKGROUND OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

The importance of organisational commitment and its significance for organisational success have been demonstrated in several research. Organisational commitment is viewed from two perspectives: attitudinal and behavioural approaches (Meyer and Allen 1991; Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Doan *et al.*, 2020). However, in the theoretical analysis of organisational commitment it has been distinguished between behavioural and attitudinal commitment (Mowday *et al.*, 1982; Reicher, 1985; Salancik, 1977; Scholl, 1981; Staw, 1977; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, if employees are deeply devoted to their organisation, they will articulate their goals and values while also expressing a strong desire to join the organisation and demonstrating positive behaviours (Nguyen *et al.*, 2020).

The faculty and administration of the university play vital roles in making an educational institute a successful institution (Khalid and Ali, 2005; Ahmad et al., 2020). Therefore, the commitment of the staff and administration is very necessary to make the high ranked institute (Naz et al., 2020). The organisational commitment (OC) is identified as a bridge in relating the employer and employee of an organisation for many years (Naz et al., 2020). The definition of constructs shows the significances in binding the individuals to their educational institutes and with the course of actions that are related to the targets of commitments (Naz et al., 2020). The former research analysis is evident that there exists a relationship between turnover intentions and organisational commitment (Ababneh, 2020). The relationship between the organisational commitment and extra job roles, discretionary extra duties and OCB was also identified by the scholars Paramaatha et al. (2019).

2.3.1. Components of organisational commitment

The organisational commitment is divided into three main components approved as per the literature review of author Cho et al. (2019). The first one is an affective commitment which holds the people with the help of emotional involvement, attachment, and identifications with the organisations. The second one is continuance commitment which is dependent upon the awareness of employees about the cost of leaving an organisation. The third one is normative commitment is referred to the feelings of the employees about their job responsibilities towards the management and the co-workers (Buchanan and Huczynski, 2019; Kim et al., 2019). The component of each type of organisational commitment may have various antecedents, but all of them lead to lesser attention to leaving the organisations, and they result in the outcome of extra-job behaviour at the site of work (Paramaatha et al., 2019). The OCBs, as described above, are the extra roles or duties that staff performed at the site of work without any greed of money, and it is related to the organisational commitment. The research studies verify that the OCBs are proved to be the positive outcomes of the workforce, which is committed, and volunteer activities performed by the staff which act as the contribution of employees which is not determined to be the organisational formal rewarding setup (Banwo and Du, 2020).

The general relation between the organisational commitment and OCBs are completely documented in the form of the research studies (Paramaatha et al., 2019), but it requires further investigation in various setups and different countries and businesses (Buchanan and Huczynski, 2019; Kim et al., 2019). Therefore, the study of the influence of organisational commitment on the OCB in the context of the university settings is formally stated in the described research statement. Hence, the cross-cultural applications of the constructs of organisational commitment and OCB remain open for debate. The invariances of the structure of the organisational commitment under different types of cultures and in different types of the businesses has been focused on by various scholars for the purpose of analysis and knowing the impacts of both constructs of organisational commitment and OCBs (Erum et al., 2020).

The organisational commitment was considered under the culture of Chinese educational institutes, and analysis proves that there exist direct relationships between organisational commitment, OCB, turnover, behaviours, personality, and work engagement (Xiong and Wen, 2020). However, a South Korean research study conducted based on the normative commitment was proved to be less convinced affecting empowerment of the employees as described by the authors Bae et al. (2020). They provided four models that fit the data gathered from South Korea (Oh, 2019). The roles of the normative type of commitment raise questions in non-western and western settings (Navarro et al., 2020). However, both continuance and affective commitments are based primarily on the association of the individuals with the normative commitment of the organisation as per the interactions of the organisation.

The familial and cultural socialisation process the individual learns as per the appropriateness of the concept of self-interest, obligation and loyalty is based on the organisational commitment. The scholars such as Thirumalai et al. (2020) suggested that the increased significance of the normative type of commitment, in addition to the cultural values, enhances the social group performance, and it plays a vital role in improving the attachments and attitudes of the individuals with the organisation (Navarro et al., 2020). The same findings were collected in the context of Turkey, where organisational commitment was studied as per the attitudes of the employees (Galle et al., 2020).

2.3.2. Organisational factors and organisational commitment

The antecedents of the organisational commitment are considered to be the organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate, employee behaviour and management style as per the study of the previous literature of different authors (Aguilar-Quintana et al., 2020; Donglong et al., 2020; Holland and Kim, 2020). The moderator of job satisfaction in the relationship of organisational commitment and OCB is considered in the research problem statement as per the recommendations of the authors (e.g., Sendjaya et al., 2019; Nasrullah, 2020). The author Odhiambo (2019) suggested that OCB have a direct positive relationship with the individual as well as the organisational performance. Therefore, the current research study focuses on these variables and apply them to educational institutes in order to find out the answers to major questions of the research. Hence, to know the impact of the above-mentioned factors on the organisational commitment, the problem statement of the influence of the organisational commitment on the OCB.

Additionally, as discussed by scholars (Doan *et al.*, 2020; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020) such employees will be willing to do additional work outside of his or her normal duties and obligations and will always put up his or her best effort for the company. On the other hand, if employees lack organisational commitment, they will not only be non-productive, but also likely to leave (Jadhav *et al.*, 2017). Organisational commitment, according to Hardiningsih *et al.* (2020) is a critical element for creation of accountability. Whereas, according to Mobley *et al.* (1979), organisational commitment is a key factor in the decision to leave a company. A firm belief in the organisation's goals and ideals is defined as organisational commitment (Meyer and Allen, 1991). Contrarily, organisational commitment, according to Doan *et al.* (2020), is the power of identity between an individual and an organisation. Organisational commitment, as per authors (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Porter *et al.*, 1974; Steers, 1979; Hardiningsih *et al.*, 2020) is defined as an employee's willingness to make major contributions to the organisation (Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Doan *et al.*, 2020).

The organisational commitment normally considered to be the critical type of the variable in attitudes and behaviours related to the working of the organisations (Meyer *et al.*, 1990; Hawkins, 2019), therefore, it is getting the considerable attention from the researchers. On the other hand, organisational commitment also reflects the attitudes of the employee towards the organisation. The organisational commitment is referred to the identifications of the employees within the organisations (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Supriyanto *et al.*,

2020). The organisational commitments have three types of the main traits as per concepts of the organisational commitment which are given below. 1) The strong acceptances and beliefs of the values and aims of the organisation. 2) The strong intents to remain in an organisation. 3) The will of exerting the additional effort to ensure the success of institutes. 4) The strong desires or intent to be with the organisation (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019; Supriyanto *et al.*, 2020).

The organisational commitments also result in improving the productivity and performance (Meyer *et al.*, 2002; Hawkins, 2019; Park *et al.*, 2021), job satisfaction, motivation, and organisational citizenship behaviour (Cooper-Hakim and Viswesvaran, 2005; Hardiningsih *et al.*, 2020), it also reduces the absenteeism and turnover as well (Cooper-Hakim and Viswesvaran, 2005; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020). The organisational commitment is also observed to be influenced by the factors of the organisation such as the organisational justice (Chughtai and Zafar, 2006; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020), demographic factors, pay and supervision (Azeem, 2010; Nienaber and Martins 2020) and organisational structure (Nahma *et al.*, 2011, Abdul Hameed *et al.*, 2012; Nienaber and Martins, 2020).

However, organisational commitments have various kinds, most of these studies emphasises on the effective organisational commitment as it is closely related with the organisation and work performance (Grawe *et al.*, 2012; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020).

The organisational commitment is related to the emotional attachment of the employees with the organisation, and involvement and identification of the employee with the organisations. The concept of the organisational commitment is comprised of three basic types of the dimensional constructs which are affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment (Boehman, 2006; Turner and Chelladurai, 2005; Hawkins, 2019). The affective commitment is related to the continuous working of the employees with devotions on the voluntarily bases. While the continuance commitment ensures the employee of the organisation may be retained, but the employees who are committed also ensure that the employee are retained in the organisation as a premium member.

However, the committed persons of the organisation feel obligations on the part of staying in organisation. The organisational commitment is described by the author (Porter *et al.*, 1974; Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Haque *et al.*, 2019) as, the firms' beliefs in and adoption of the

organisation's values and goals, as well as a readiness to put out substantial effort on behalf of the company that shows a strong willingness to remain a member.

Jans (1989) described that the extent by which employees perceives, internalises, and accepts their roles based on the goals and values of the organisation are the main concepts of the organisational commitment. The employee also become committed with the organisation on the bases of following concepts of the organisational commitment. 1) They accept the values and the organisational mission, and they also own it. 2) The employees are mutually agreed to exert the dedications and efforts towards the goals and values of the organisation. 3) The employees have intense desires in continuous serving in the organisation (Mowday, Steers, and Porter, 1982; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020).

The scholars (Buchanan, 1974; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020; Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021) described the commitment as,

“a one-sided or affective attachment to the aims and values of an organisation, to one’s role in relation with these aims and values and to an organisation for its own sake”.

Thus, in the context of the teachers and staff of the university organisational commitment may be described as: 1) Her or his strong beliefs to accept the values and goals of the university.2) Ready in exerting the dedicated effort on the university’s behalf; and 3) Firm desires to have sustained her or his membership in the university.

The committed and devoted employees may easily adhere to the goals and objectives, and they are also keen to accept them (Valentine *et al.*, 2002; Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019). The individual will become more committed with the organisation due to reasons: the persons may stay in the organisation due to the goals, values and mission which are in line with her or his own benefits; the other individuals may remain because leaving organisation may influence their social networks, benefits or prestige, while another reason may also be the commitment to the organisation because of the senses of obligations (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Visamitanan *et al.*, 2021).

2.4. THEORITICAL APPROACH TO ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

The cost and benefits approach of the organisational commitment is described as, “a result of the perception of benefit associated with staying in and the perception of cost associated with leaving from an organisation” (Kanter, 1968; Richers, 1985; Meyer *et al.*, 1991; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020). The normative approach of the organisational commitment is also described as, “the aggregate internalised normative pressures to conduct in a manner which meets organisational objectives and interests” (Wiener, 1982; Richers, 1985; Genty, 2017; Pio *et al.*, 2018; Soelton *et al.*, 2020). The five dimensions of **Hofstede's Cultural model** (Uncertainty Avoidance, Power Distance, Individualism Vs Collectivism and Long-term Orientation Vs. Short-term Orientation) are also different in different countries and in various organisations. Pakistan being a collectivist nation tend to be bound to have emotional attachment at work so it impacts their commitment to work and OCB. Hence, it is required to investigate the factors which impact OCB and organisational commitment in this nation.

The organisational commitment has been researched in lieu of the various types of perspectives described by different scholars (Semedo *et al.*, 2016; Loan, 2020; Febrina and Syamsir, 2020). Few of the studies (Chen, 2001; Saeed *et al.*, 2014; Yin and Liao, 2020) are based on the theories of the social exchange to express the organisational commitments whereas other described the organisational commitment on the bases of the behavioural or attitudinal approaches (Elwood, 1990; Titon and Pettan, 2019). The scholars also claimed the concepts related to the organisational commitment may not be described without consideration of the nature of the multi-dimensional factors related to the organisation (Reichers, 1985; Karmakar, 2020; Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021). The various strategies and approaches related to the organisational commitment are relevant to the social exchange and psychological approach.

2.4.1 Theory of organisational commitment

A distinguished theory in organisational commitment is the Three-Component Model (TCM). According to this theory, there are three distinct components of organisational commitment:

1. **Affective commitment:** This is the emotional attachment an employee has towards the organization. If an employee has a high level of active commitment, then the chances

of an employee staying with the organisation for long are high. Active commitment also means, an employee is not only happy but also engaged in the organisational activities like, participation in discussions and meetings, giving valuable inputs or suggestions that will help the organisation, proactive work ethics, etc (Valentine *et al.*, 2002; Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019) .

2. **Continuance commitment:** This is the level of commitment where an employee would think that leaving an organisation would be costly. When an employee has a continuance in commitment level, they want to stay in the organisation for a longer period of time because they feel they must stay because they have already invested enough energy and feel attached to the organisation attachment that is both mental and emotional. For example, a person over a period tends to develop an attachment to his/her workplace and this may be one of the reasons why an employee wouldn't want to quit because they are emotionally invested (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019).

3. **Normative commitment:** This is the level of commitment where an employee feels obligated to stay in the organisation, where they feel, staying in the organisation is the right thing to do. What are the factors that lead up to this type of commitment? Is it a moral obligation where they want to stay because someone else believes in them? Or is it that they feel that they have been treated fairly here and that they do not wish to take the chance of leaving the organisation and finding themselves in between the devil and the deep sea? This is a situation where they believe they ought to stay. Here comes the motivation of employees which also helps them determine to stay in the organisation. Motivation and organisational commitment of employees is an important element to enhance job performance.

A significant predictor of this commitment is also the type of motivation, which motivates teachers to spend time and energy at work (Mowday, Steers, and Porter, 1982; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019). Following are the strategies that are used in the educational institutions to motivate employees.

2.4.2 Strategies to enhance commitment

Salary: Salary can be one of the most successful factors influencing motivation and job satisfaction. For using salary as motivation factor managers must consider several factors such

as job rate, personal allowances, length of service, performance, personal traits etc (Visamitanan *et al.*, 2021).

Incentives: Money has the power to attract and retain. Giving various types of incentives will keep staff motivated and better committed to the organisation. Basically, every staff is working for some sort of financial benefit, so the monetary benefit paid to the employees should be adequately cover their standard of living and competitive enough in the industry otherwise employee turnover will be higher for the company and the existing employees will not be motivated, instead frustrated employees cause reduced commitment to the organisation. So, management must take sufficient interest and care to maintain their employees with good pay and incentives it will help to improve organisational commitment (Mowday, Steers, and Porter, 1982; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019) .

Staff training: This is an important motivational factor for all the organisations It is an indispensable strategy for motivating employees. This will give information with latest development and technologies in their respective field of work. So that the employees will feel confident and equipped with new strength to work more effectively and scientifically, ultimately it will increase motivation and productivity (Buchanan, 1974; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020).

Information and communication: Availability of information regarding the consequences of the employee action on others help to keep employees motivated (Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021).

2.4.3. Social exchange theory

Allen and Meyer (1990) distinguish three types of organisational commitment. The affective commitment is defined as "an emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organisation" (p. 21); whereas continuance commitment is defined as "the perceived costs associated with leaving the organisation"; and normative commitment, is defined as a perceived obligation to remain in the organisation." Recent meta-analytic research (Bakker and Leiter, 2010; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020) show that all these commitment types are linked to intentions to leave the company and employee turnover. On the other hand, it also asserts the association between affective commitment and to a variety of desired outcomes of employees, such as employee attendance, work performance, stress at work, health, and work-life balance (Meyer

et al., 2002; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Astuty and Udin, 2020). Therefore, individuals see themselves as members of social categories as proposed by social identity theory (Turner, 1985; Ashforth and Mael, 1989; Brammer *et al.*, 2007; Rai, 2013; Fatimah *et al.*, 2018; Tayyaba Akram and ShenLei, 2020).

According to social identity theory, a person's perception of themselves, or 'self-concept,' is influenced by their affiliation with social groups. However, individuals strive to create or improve their positive self-perception (concept) by comparing their own and their group's features with those of other individuals and groups (Brammar *et al.*, 2007; Loan, 2020). The exchange perspectives view the employment relationships as consist of the economic or social exchange (Aryee *et al.*, 2002; Cropanzano *et al.*, 2003; Xu *et al.*, 2020).

The economic exchange relationship involves the exchange of the benefits related to the returning of the efforts of the employees in the form of financial compensation and are also dependent on the contracts formally done with the employees which are also enforced in the organisation as per the employment laws. (Ashforth and Mael, 1989; Dutton *et al.*, 1994; Rao *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, it has also been emphasised by the scholars (Rai, 2013; Suroso and Anggraeni, 2017; Tafamel and Ehiabhi Andrew, 2019; Supriya and Dadhabhai, 2020) that social exchange theory suggests that the employees trust the organisation and show their commitment which is also a kind of resource, and the organisation needs to provide an environment and compensation to retain that trust and commitment.

On the contrary, the social types of the exchange are a kind of volunteer action which is initiated by the treatment of the organisation towards the employees as per expectations of the individuals working in the organisation and employees may also be obliged to the reciprocation of the deed by the organisation (Aryee *et al.*, 2002; Blau, 1964; Gould-Williams and Davies, 2004; Belsito and Reutzler, 2020). As per the views of the organisational commitment and exchange approaches, the employees of the organisation attach themselves to the organisation and they receive the rewards as a return (March and Simon, 1958; Farrell and Rusbult, 1981; Hawkins, 2019; Utami *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, based on these views' employees entering in organisation with certain expectations, goals, desires, and skills find the environments in which they may use the skills they acquire and get their desires satisfied and achieve their aims (Dung, 2020). The perception of the rewards/exchange system in the mind of the employees results in

an increase in the organisational commitment of the employees (Brammer *et al.*, 2007; Masale *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, the perceived awarding system in relation of its cost has resulted in an enhanced organisational commitment of the employees (Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020).

Nonetheless, failing of the organisation in provision of the requisite reward in exchanging the effort of the employee results in deteriorating in the organisational commitment (Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Haque *et al.*, 2019). These perspectives are consistent to the idea of the Becker (1960) who have calculative types of the commitment where commitment of the individuals is the part of the function performed by an organisation as per the accumulated investment (Genty, 2017; Pio *et al.*, 2018; Astuty and Udin, 2020; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020). The perspectives of the employer to employee relationships as suggested in the social exchange theory emphasised that the employees respond to the good working condition provided by the organisation in a way which benefits the organisations and other individuals working in the organisation (Dietz *et al.*, 2017; Tafamel and Ehiabhi Andrew, 2019).

Similarly, employee retaliate against the dissatisfied condition of the organisation which result in negative working attitude which are described as the lateness, absenteeism, tardiness or readiness for quitting the organisations (Haar, 2006; Crede *et al.*, 2007; Yean and Yusof, 2016; Al Zeifiti and Mohamad, 2017; Rao *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, it is expected that the individual perceiving the working condition to be distressing and negative, may reciprocate this negativity in the work attitude which is relevant to the reduced commitment, low morale and job dissatisfaction, whereas those employees who are perceiving the workplace condition in positive manner, may reciprocate the positive type of the work attitude which are related to the low turnover, satisfaction and high commitment (Cropanzano *et al.*, 2001; Crede *et al.*, 2007; Hendri, 2019; Dung, 2020).

The other perspectives of the social exchange are the norms of reciprocities which are based on two factors: “(a) people should help those who have helped them, and (b) people should not injure those who have helped them” (Gouldner, 1960, p. 171). Hence, the employee who perceives that the organisations treat and value them in fair manner, will have a feeling of obligations which is paid back or reciprocated by the good or positive working attitude and behaviour of the employees (Aryee *et al.*, 2002; Parzefall, 2008; Belsit and Reutzel, 2020).

Furthermore, it is also recommended by many studies that the norms of the reciprocities are considered as moral obligations which are owned by both employer and employees as an exchange of their relationships which caused in receiving the benefits for both parties (Gouldner, 1960; Linden *et al.*, 2003; Parzefall, 2008; Nienaber and Martins, 2020; Ndlovu *et al.*, 2021).

Similarly, it is also suggested that the employee who perform jobs in an enriched manner devoid the stresses and get the attractive pays, job's securities and good treatment from the organisations and bound in expressing the gratitude for support received due to an enhanced commitment with the organisation (Loan, 2020). Hence, the factors such as payment that motivate employees and extra benefits that complement their salaries, as well as socio-emotional advantages like respect, approval, and care, all help to promote organisational commitment (Mowday, 1979; LaMastro, 1999; Brammer *et al.*, 2007; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Visamitanan *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, social exchange theory asserts that concrete incentives which including money and other items, are exchanged which motivate them to put in extra effort and stay with their companies (Armeli *et al.*, 1998; Eisenberger *et al.*, 2001; Brammer *et al.*, 2007; Dung, 2020; Rao *et al.*, 2020) The reciprocity norm in the exchange process holds the employee in the organisation with a process of paying back which is linked to their commitment (Hendri, 2019; Loan, 2020; Utami *et al.*, 2021).

2.4.4. Behavioural theory

(a) Behavioural approach

Howard S. Becker (1960) proposed the "side-bet" idea as the first contemporary explanation of commitment. Workers are committed in this paradigm because they have made a completely hidden investment, or "side bet," in a certain organisation. Becker (1960) concentrated on "side-bets," which is defined as the process through which employees bind themselves to organisation by investment of effort, time, and compensation. These types of investments, on the other hand, come at a cost that limits an employee's future freedom and activities (Grego-Planner, 2020).

Hence, behavioural approach which is relevant to employee behaviour grew out of Becker's (1960) work (Javad and Davood, 2012; Georges, 2020). This is known as the exchange-based or side-bet theory (Becker, 1960) and holds that individuals are committed to the organisation as far as they hold their positions and accumulate better benefits (or incur greater costs at departure), this may dissuade them from seeking alternative employment (Becker, 1960; Javad and Davood, 2012; Georges, 2020). Similarly, individuals are committed to the organisation because the benefits assimilated with staying in the organisation are higher than the alternative opportunities and costs to leave (Blau and Boal, 1987; Collins and Seller, 1988; Herscovitch, 2002; Haque *et al.*, 2020). Commitment is thus an outcome of inducement or contributing transactions between an organisation and its members (Becker, 1960; Blau and Boal, 1987; Singh *et al.*, 2008; Luu and Phan, 2020). Consequently, according to Stevens (1978), a limitation of exchange-based measures of commitment due to lack of empirical evidence stems the ongoing behavioural outcomes within the organisation which is referred as behavioural approach (Georges, 2020).

(b) Attribution approach

The attributional approach focuses on attitudes that result in the attribution of commitment which is also suggested by the scholars (Calder and Burnkrant, 1977; Muller, 2020; Seele, 2020) to be concerning with the reasoning of the behaviour and events as explained by the individuals. According to Johnston and Snizek (1991), these attributions are referred to maintain consistency between one's behaviour and attitudes (Becker, 1960; Herscovitch, 2002; Seele, 2020). Therefore, it is a moral or attitudinal approach in which the individual behaviour is guided by emotions, heart, or affective/value rationality (Calder and Burnkrant, 1977; Johnston and Snizek, 1991; Muller, 2020). On the other hand, scholars (Bar-Hayim and Berman, 1992; Guest *et al.*, 2021). The individual is socialised by showing active participation and affective participation for the goals of the organisation.

Accordingly, organisational commitment is conceptualised as a state in which an individual identifies with a particular organisation and its goals, and their wishes to maintain membership in the organisation to facilitate its goals (Becker, 1960; Blau and Boal, 1987; Haque *et al.*, 2020). The attribution approach as per the authors (Reichers, 1985; Seele, 2020; Guest *et al.*, 2021) conceptualises commitment as a binding of the individual to behavioural acts, which

occurs when individuals attribute an attitude of commitment to themselves after engaging in behaviours that are volitional, explicit, and irrevocable.

(a) Psychological approach

Employees nowadays do not regard their workplace solely their means to income. They seek to meet other needs, which including self-development or a sense of acceptability (Lindgren, 2012; Laguna *et al.*, 2015; Grego-Planner, 2020). Hence, the organisation's duty is to develop working conditions that allow employees' requirements to be addressed while also facilitating the development of highly engaged and loyal personnel (Muller, 2020). These dedicated employees that can be the foundation to success of the organisation. Motivation and job satisfaction are not treated the same way as commitment (Grego-Planner, 2020). It shapes behaviour despite the presence of other, frequently opposing motives or attitudes (Richers 1985; Astuty and Udin, 2020; Utami *et al.*, 2021).

“The relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organisation is characterised as organisational commitment (OC)” (Mowday *et al.*, 1979, p. 226; Lindgren *et al.*, 2015; Hardiningsih *et al.*, 2020). It's reasonable to infer that a dedicated employee believes in the organisation's vision and goals and associate themselves psychologically to the organisation. “Commitment is defined as the willingness to make independent judgments and identification with the firm, which is reflected in the acceptance of responsibility for the organisation's actions” (Lewicka, 2014, p. 224; Yigit, 2016; Supriyanto *et al.*, 2020). Becker (1960) an American scholar, is regarded as a pioneer of organisational commitment research in the literature. However, this scholar examined the notion via the perspective of the employee-organisation economic exchange connection (Becker, 1960; Georges, 2020). However, the subsequent research considered the emotional side of organisational commitment (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Herscovitch, 2002; Javad and Davood, 2012; Luu and Phan, 2020).

Organisational commitment, according to scholars (Ch. A. O'Reilly and J. A. Chatman, 1986; Laguna *et al.*, 2015; Grego-Planner, 2020) is an employee's intrinsic emotional attachment that reflects itself in the attitudes and association toward the organisation. Meyer and Allen's

organisational commitment model is tremendously famous since 1990s (Meyer and Allen, 1991; Guest *et al.*, 2021).

Organisational commitment is defined by these scholars as an employee's identification with a company and is presented in three different dimensions: affective, normative and continuance commitment (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Meyer and Allen, 1991; Lindgren *et al.*, 2015; Grego-Planner, 2020; Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021). Employees' emotional tie to the company is known as affective commitment (AC) (Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021). Sen *et al.* (2006) argue that it is a personal choice for the employee to maintain its emotional attachment. Furthermore, high affective commitment entails self-motivation rather than force (Doan *et al.*, 2020; Utami *et al.*, 2021). It's even thought that an employee continues with the company because he wants to stay associated with the organisation due to its emotional investment (Marzec, 2014; Haque *et al.*, 2019; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020).

Continuance commitment is another facet of commitment which is linked to the employee's notion that leaving job would have been too costly. (Lichtenstein *et al.*, 2014; Doan *et al.*, 2020). The normative commitment is the third and final sort of commitment (Herscovitch, 2002; Nayeema *et al.*, 2021). According to Meyer and Allen (1991), the dedication of an organisation is determined by social norms. A sense of moral need to stay in, it leads to normative commitment. The employee stays with the company because he believes it is the most suitable and ethically reasonable course of action (Laguna *et al.*, 2015; Maleka *et al.*, 2021). Interests in studies of the multi-dimensions of the organisational commitment is due to the resulting of two main aspects. The first aspect of the previous literature on the organisational commitments was being criticised due to its failure in investigating commitments as the constructs which are different from the others in terms of the psychological concept (O'Reilly and Chatman, 1986; Utami *et al.*, 2021).

It is described by the research that psychological approach of the organisational commitment is relevant to the control systems, effective rewarding, financial investments, and value's congruences or by providing the opportunities as desired by the employees (Wiener, 1982; Becker, 1960; Yigit, 2016; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018). Second approach of the organisational commitment is related to the behaviour and attitude of the employees which is distinct from the concept of the commitment (i.e., costs, loyalty and psychological attachments in lieu of resigning from the organisations), the scholars (Mowday *et al.*, 1982; Genty, 2017; Hawkins,

2019) observed that there exist two types of the approaches which are not normally interrelated with each other. The scholars (Mobley *et al.*, 1979; Mowday *et al.*, 1982; Richers, 1985; Doan *et al.*, 2020) described that there are continuous cyclical relationships in between the two types of the organisational commitment while high levelled attitudinal commitment led to committed types of the behaviour that reinforce the attitudes of the commitment.

Hence, in the same way, the authors (Coopey and Hartley, 1991; Yigit, 2016; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018) suggested that commitment might be developed through behaviour and is reinforced through each other.

The scholars (Armeli *et al.*, 1998; Yigit, 2016; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018) reported there exist two various types of the approaches which are entirely distinguished from the theories and the measurement of each is contained with the element of each other. For example, the employees may draw in the organisation for exchanging the causes (known to be the calculative commitment). However, according to scholars (Meyer *et al.*, 1991; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020) later these attitudes are converted into the membership of the employees with the organisation (attitudinal commitment). As an alternative, the person may join the organisation due to the attitudinal commitment, however, to continuously stay in the organisation it is required to maintain the calculative commitment in the organisation (Cooper-Hakim and Viswesvaran, 2005; Loan, 2020). The inter-relations between the behaviour and attitude are also stated by the authors (Meyer and Allen, 1991, p. 62; Loan, 2020; Rao *et al.*, 2020) who reported that as previous studies restricted the organisational commitment to be reflected in the psychological states as,

“... incorporate both the attitudinal and behavioural approach and their complementary relationship... that this psychological state need not be restricted to value and goal congruence ... that it can reflect a desire, a need and/or an obligation to maintain membership in the organisation (Meyer and Allen, 1991, p. 62; Laguna *et al.*, 2015; Loan, 2020).”

Research on the multiple dimensions of organisational commitment begin to get attention in early years of 1990 where it rooted back to the study done by the author Kelman, (1958) on attitudinal changes (Kelman, 1958; Bagozzi, 2002; Eketu *et al.*, 2021). It is argued by Kelman (1958) that the individuals may accept influences in various three types of the ways described as, 1) The compliances may occur if “an individual accepts influence because he hopes to achieve a favourable reaction from another person or group” (p.53). The individual may be

adapted by the behaviours to get the rewards or approvals; however, it is not necessary as she/he share the beliefs and goals of organisations. It is same as to the continuance commitment. 2) The identification also occurs if “an individual accepts influence because he wants to establish or maintain a satisfying self-defining relationship to another person or group” (p.53). It means that the individuals may also feel the proudest while being part of the groups and respecting the accomplishment and values. It is same as to the affective commitment. 3) The concept of the internalisation may occur if “an individual accepts influence because the content of the induced behaviour-the ideas and actions of which it is composed-is intrinsically rewarding. The employees adopt the induced behaviour because it is congruent with their value system” (p. 53).

Therefore, as per the scholars (Perry and Hondeghem, 2008; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Mowbray *et al.*, 2020) the individuals accept the influences due to the values of the organisation. It is type of the normative commitment. The internalisation, compliance and identification are relevant to the individual beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours. Whereas internalisation is the greatest conformity level which becomes the foundation to commitment. In the organisational perspective, the employees change both their public behaviour (the way they act) and their private beliefs. However, research of Kelman (1958) created the ideas on behaviour of the employee and researcher could not follow these until forty years ago (Bagozzi, 2002; Hwang and Kim, 2007; Binyamin, 2020). The studies which explored the multiple dimensions of the organisational commitment were described by the Allen and Meyer (1984) which also utilised the sides bet theories of Becker (1960) who introduced the concepts of the continuance commitments along with the affective type of the commitment. It was reviewed thirty-two types of the studies of commitment by the Reichers (1985) and he could not establish a consistency in the definitions of the organisational commitment.

However, from the studies (Reichers, 1985, pp.485; Sen *et al.*, 2006; Grego-Planner, 2020), the organisational commitment is divided into three types:1) The sides bet recommend that the organisational commitment as a function of the costs and rewards connected to the membership of the organisation and they are increased due to increase in the tenure of working with the organisation.2) The attribution where commitment is bonded with the individual’s behaviour or act and is resulted by the attitude of the employee of the organisation for engaging oneself to the irrevocable, explicit and volitional type of the behaviour with the organisation (Wad dock and Parallel, 2004; Laguna *et al.*, 2015; Binyamin, 2020). 3) The organisational or

individual goals are congruent with the commitments of the individual who identify themselves with the values and goals of the organisation.

Moreover, it was observed by Reicher (1995) that, “coalitions and constituencies” (like work group, supervisors, customers, clients, and such as top management) with the values and goals of the each other and it may be compatible to the goal of the organisation. Chatman and O'Reilly (1986) who revised works on behaviour and attitude change of Kelman (1958) and emphasised that there exists strong bonding in three types of the commitment in the form of internalisation, identification, and compliance.

The scholars such as O'Reilly and Chatman (1986, p. 493) asserts that compliance occur to achieve the rewards which are specific and are not based on the self-beliefs; internalisation normally occur when the values of the employees and organisation are on the same track; also, the identifications are aroused when being in a group that respect values and accomplish the tasks of organisation by involving all the members (O'Reilly and Chatman, 1986; Caldwell *et al.*, 1990; Seele, 2020). It was also observed that the internalisation and identification are reversely attached to the intention of turnover while compliance are positively related to the turnover of the employees.

Hence, following the studies done by the scholars (McGee and Ford, 1987; Meyer and Allen, 1990; Fischer and Hyder, 2020) observed that continuance commitment was having main dimensions which are consisted of the ‘low perceived alternative’ and ‘high personal sacrifice’ (Muller, 2020).

The summary of the research study show that organisational commitment consists of multi-dimensional constructs. The purposes of the research of the organisational commitment revolve around three main aspects of the commitment known to be the affective commitment that reflect the psychological attachment of the employees to the organisation and identity in term of the organisation; the normative commitments which reflect moral and loyal obligations to be in the organisation; and continuance commitment about the recognition of the cost that is associated while resigning from the organisation (McGee and Ford, 1987; Meyer and Allen, 1990; Fischer and Hyder, 2020).

2.5. THE CONCEPT OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Organisational commitment is defined as psychological attachment of an employee to organisation (Lambert, 2007; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020) by devoting to the objectives of the organisation (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Doan *et al.*, 2020) to attach and involve in the organisation (Meyer, 1990; Utami *et al.*, 2021) considering perceiving cost while deciding to leave an organisation (Allen, 1990) to sustain environment of obligation in organisation (Meyer and Allen, 1990; Hawkins, 2019).

Despite of various studies which have been conducted on the area of organisational commitment, there is still a lack of consensus which was observed between organisational commitment definitions (Meyer and Allen, 1991; Jaros *et al.*, 1993; Hawkins, 2019; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020). The subject of organisational commitment has been extensively described as the measure, which is criticised due to lack of perception which have given inconsistency to the concept of the organisational commitment (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Hawkins, 2019; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020). It is described by the scholar (Mowday *et al.*, 1982, p.20) who initially researched on organisational commitment which developed further:

“Researchers from various disciplines ascribe their own meanings to the topic thereby increasing the difficulty involved in understanding the construct”.

The dimensions of the organisational commitment had increased confusion in the definitions and concepts (Meyer and Herscovitch, 2001; Hawkins, 2019; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020; Choudhury *et al.*, 2021). There are some research studies which made this concept as unidimensional (Porter *et al.*, 1974; Becker, 1960; Wiener, 1982; Hawkins, 2019) whereas others made it multi type of dimensional approach (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021).

The scholar (Morrow, 1983, p. 486; Mowbray *et al.*, 2020) described more than twenty-five dimensions of the organisational commitment and reported it as,

“The growth in commitment-related concepts has not been accompanied by careful segmentation of commitment’s theoretical domain in terms of intended meaning of each concept’s relationship among each other”.

The authors (O'Reilly and Chatman, 1986; Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021) noted that various terms have been used in describing the phenomenon which are known to be as psychological or affective attachment and or attachment to one's investment are also known to be the side bits. More confusions were aroused from existence of the two basic approaches which are defined as exchange and psychological approach or those which have been suggested to the behavioural and attitudinal school of thought (Scholl, 1981; Coopey and Hartley, 1991; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020). As an example, (Porter *et al.*, 1974) described the commitment as the psychological attachments to the values and goals of the organisations whereas Becker (1960) described it in term of cost associated while resigning from the organisation (Richers, 1985; Meyer *et al.*, 1991; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020).

Organisational commitment is an employee's passion to maintain its identification in the organisation. Therefore, it is the psychological relationship with the work and the organisation to stay and be identified due to the work (Haque *et al.*, 2019; Doan *et al.*, 2020). Klein and Park (2015) claimed organisational commitment as an attitude, is frequently defined as 1) a wish to stay as a member of the organisation (2) their wish to put efforts based on organisational desires (3) it is about beliefs, and acceptability of norms and goals of the organisation. It also refers to loyalty and love (Staw, 1977; Hardiningsih *et al.*, 2020; Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021).

This organisational commitment is relevant to be willing to stay inside the company as its part (Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Haque *et al.*, 2019; Choudhury *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, it is a relationship between an employee and the organisation psychologically where they work and associate themselves to it (Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020).

The authors (Meyer and Allen, 1991; Hawkins, 2019; Utami *et al.*, 2021) while responding to the dimensions and definitions of the constructs, described three common components of the organisational commitment which are reflected by the desires, needs and or obligations of the employees for maintaining the membership with the organisation. The lack in the consensus over the definition of organisational commitment, authors (Meyer and Allen, 1997, p. 11; Mowbray *et al.*, 2020) described it as:

“...no definition is more 'correct' or universally accepted than the others. The definitions are different; however, it can only confuse the issue if we speak of commitment without indicating which definition we are using”.

The study mentions three components which conceptualise the organisational commitment as described by (Meyer and Allen, 1991; Meyer and Allen, 1997; Hawkins, 2019; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020). It is described as employees in the organisations may be having various types of the commitment which ties them in the organisation but might not be psychological or affective in nature (Genty, 2017; Ko *et al.*, 2021). It meant that employees are likely to change their job because of the policies of the organisation. Thus, this type of the employees chooses to be in the organisation because of the lack of alternatives available or as to save the investment they made around the organisation (Nguyen *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, the single dimensional approach as described by Porter *et al.*, (1974) is not observed to be suitable for the research (Fenton-O’Creevy *et al.*, 1997; Meyer and Herscovitch, 2001; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020; Choudhury *et al.*, 2021). Hence, the multi-dimensional approach has been adopted to review the literature on organisational commitment critically.

2.6. FACTORS INFLUENCING ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

Organisational commitment is considered as an employee desire to be identified with the organisation as an integral part of it. Hence, it is determined as an employee and organisation’s psychological relationship where the employees associate themselves with the organisation (Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020).

Patchell (2009) has defined “work commitment” as alternative terminology for organisational commitment. Organisational commitment has been found as a behavioural aspect of employees which is used to examine as a tendency of the employees to sustain as dedicated members in an organisation (Ogbu and Ugwu, 2019; Supriya and Dadhabhai, 2020; Riyanto *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, “work commitment” or organisational commitment is a state where employees adopt the values, goals, and objectives of the organisation as their own goals and they feel highly involved and encouraged, therefore they aim to stay in the organisation (Soelton *et al.*, 2020; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020). However, there are factors which influence the commitment of the employees such as feeling of justice in the organisation, the positive outlook of firm by

employees, the overall working atmosphere and the innovative culture yields employee performance and they value the organisation (Yigit, 2016; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020; Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021).

2.6.1. Organisational structure

It is defined as the structure of interrelated events, the way people get organised and they are coordinated and divided (Katz, 1978; Tasic, 2019) by which work is divided in different tasks (Mintzberg, 1983; Toft and Liefermann, 2020) in order to formally allocate the work roles (Child, 1972; Turi and Sorooshian, 2019; Ehiorobo *et al.*, 2020) by formalisation, hierarchy layers, integration levels, authority centralisation and communication patterns in the organisation (Thompson, 1966; Ehiorobo *et al.*, 2020) to coordinate, conduct and control the activities of the organisation for responsibilities fulfilment and power distribution (Jackson, 1982; Sener and Balli, 2020; Alown *et al.*, 2020).

Walton (2005) on the other hand side, defined organisational structure as the initial point of organisation that involve positions in the company and roles on hierarchical levels, problem solving processes and mechanisms, communication, integration, and accountability (Ajagbe *et al.*, 2016; Noor *et al.*, 2020; Jonker and Treur, 2021). Lawrence and Lorsch (1967) pointed out that it is a technique to integrate and differentiate in the organisation. It has also been denoted as framework of relationships, tasks, and relationships of authority (Alshaheen, 2020; Obrist, 2020). Organisational structure is also defined as the structure of interrelated events (Katz, 1978; Tasic, 2019; Rao and Zaidi, 2020) by which work is divided in different tasks (Mintzberg, 1983; Toft and Liefermann, 2020) to formally allocate them (Child, 1972; Turi and Sorooshian, 2019) to coordinate, conduct and control the activities of the organisation (Jackson, 1982; Alown *et al.*, 2020).

The arrangement of tasks and jobs in the formal manner is also described as the organisational structure it also incorporates how the regulations and rules are implemented in the organisation after the allocation of responsibilities and authorities (Nahm *et al.*, 2003; Coulter and Robbins, 2007; Sener and Balli, 2020; Jonker and Treur, 2021). The research related to the organisational structures in lieu of the behaviour and attitudes of individuals in the organisation (Subramaniam *et al.*, 2002; Tasic, 2019) computed the relations between the organisational commitment and

decentralising structure and it has been observed that there exists a positive relation in between the organisational commitment and organisational structure (Auh and Menguc, 2007; Toft and Liefermann, 2020). Furthermore, Stroh *et al.* (2001) has asserted that structure demonstrates the connection in the organisation among various roles (Alblooshi *et al.*, 2020; Sener and Balli, 2020). Hence, these different definitions show that organisational structure is not a concentrated term and has many dimensions. Ajagbe (2016) emphasised that the formal systems of reporting relationships and allocating tasks which supports to coordinate and motivate the individuals to achieve the goals of the organisation (Alshaheen, 2020; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). Additionally, the formal ways to divide the job tasks and their formal divisions and grouping of tasks. The extent to which the rules and procedures to stipulate the behaviours is measured by formalisation is referred as the organisational structure (Komazec and Jevtic, 2012; Sener and Balli, 2020). In Pakistan the university organisational structure is hierarchical, matrix or flat depending on the type of the organisation.

A **hierarchical structure** is mainly prevalent in big organisations where there are different authority levels and various chains of command which connect management levels at varied levels. The decision-making process flows from top to bottom and is typically formal. In matrix structure there are more than one reporting line managers and it is usually applicable in the larger universities in Pakistan with bigger projects and large number of students and staff. On the other hand, flat organisational structure is almost free from middle management between employees and the executives, and the goal is to maintain as little hierarchy as possible (Rao and Zaidi, 2020).

Formalisation is the extent to which the employees are given procedures and rules which limits the autonomous working conditions (Esfahani *et al.*, 2021; Jonker and Treur, 2021). The explicit rules and procedures in the organisations with high levels of formalisations hinders the flexibility and innovation (Rao and Zaidi, 2020). Therefore, centralisation develops an environment of non-participation, reduced involvement in tasks and commitment to the organisation (Obrist, 2020; Sener and Balli, 2020). Centralisation refers to the decision-making authority on hierarchical levels whereas the decentralisation is related to decision making on lower levels in the organisation (Alblooshi *et al.*, 2020; Devinney and Dowling, 2020; Gaspary, 2020).

Thus, Germain (1989) illustrated the positive impact of **decentralisation** on organisational performance as it enhances the commitment through encouraging creative and inclusive environment (Walton, 2005; Lam, 2011; Maduenyi *et al.*, 2015; Jonker and Treur, 2021).

2.6.2. Organisational culture

Organisational culture refers to the assumptions about ways of working (Hampden-Turner, 1990; Tyagi and Moses, 2020) in an acceptable pattern ensuring internal integration and adaption to new ways (Bate, 1994; Syakur *et al.*, 2020) which encourages the members to contribute more to the organisation (Linstead, 1992; Alqadre, 2019) towards the problem solving (Schein, 1991; Wiley *et al.*, 2020; Hampden-Turner, 1990; Tyagi and Moses, 2020). It relates to a system of beliefs, behaviour and values which are shared among employees in the organisation (Deshpande and Webster, 1989; Ravasi and Schultz, 2006; Xiaoming and Junchen, 2012; Sunarsi, 2020; Chang *et al.*, 2021).

Schein (1991) defined the organisational culture as the outline of basic group assumptions that has been invented overtime (Lok and Crawford, 2004; Van Stuyvesant Meijen, 2008; Ahmad *et al.*, 2011; Belias and Koustelios, 2014; Putriana and Riady, 2015; Paaais and Pattiruhu, 2020). It could also be the assumptions which are discovered in learning process to address the problems related to internal integration and external adaptation. These ways of working have been working well which can be considered valid to be taught to the new employees. It is also perceived to be the correct working ways (Sunarsi, 2020; Syakur *et al.*, 2020; Sabuhari *et al.*, 2020; Anning, 2021). Contrarily, Claver *et al.* (2001 p. 248) defined it as:

“Organisational culture is a set of values, symbols and rituals, shared by the members of a specific firm, which describes the way things are done in an organisation in order to solve both internal management problems and those related to customers, suppliers and environment” (Lok and Crawford, 2004; Purnama, 2013; Chang *et al.*, 2021; Erlangga *et al.*, 2021).

Similarly, Schein (2004) defined organisational commitment more precisely as ‘a set of behaviours, values, norms, processes and routines which makes an overall working environment’ (Claver *et al.*, 2001; Putriana and Riady, 2015; Van Stuyvesant Meijen, 2008; Syakur *et al.*, 2020). The organisational culture includes the interactions, values, and goals of

the organisation with respect to the external environments. The cultures are based on the unwritten or written rules, customs, norms, beliefs, and feelings which normally converted into the policies and rules of the organisations (Schein,1991; Khan and Ansari, 2021). The culture of different organisations is not similar, and it keeps on varying based on the type of the organisation and it is very difficult to alter the cultures of the organisations.

The organisational cultures are of various kinds and categories that may measure the customs, norms, beliefs, and feelings existing in the organisation (Claver *et al.*, 2001; Belias and Koustelios, 2014; Paais and Pattiruhu, 2020; Sunarsi, 2020).

Organisational culture has various sets of its types; however, the main types in terms of goals and decision making of the organisation are task oriented, innovative, bureaucratic cultures and competitive (Ahmad *et al.*, 2011; Putriana and Riady, 2015; Anning, 2021). The cultures are based on the believes, values and perceptions of the organisations. Organisational culture is also one of the main processes by which various organisational aspects are covered in the working environments of the organisation as per perfect desired ways of the organisation therefore, Robbins and Coulter (2012), stated that organisational culture is associated with the organisation's core values which are developed, agreed upon and implemented by the individuals. (Matthew, 2010; Chang *et al.*, 2021; Erlangga *et al.*, 2021). The organisational culture is a systematic knowledge, that describes the standards within the organisation. It helps to evaluate, believe, and perceive the organisation and organisational culture also act as a service to relate employee communities with the external environment (Allaire and Firsirotu, 1984; Van Stuyvesant Meijen, 2008; Khan and Ansari, 2021). It is also observed in the literature that people of the organisation represent the culture of that organisation (Purnama, 2013; Putriana and Riady, 2015; Paais and Pattiruhu, 2020).

Therefore, the behaviours, perceptions, norms, and values of the organisational members together encompass the culture of the organisation. The cultures of the various organisations are distinguished by the members of the organisation (Belias and Koustelios, 2014; Sabuhari *et al.*, 2020). The cultures are one of terms, that may be difficult to explain, however after distinguishing the culture of the organisation by the members, it is very easy to describe among the staff of the organisation (Purnama, 2013; Erlangga *et al.*, 2021; Burns *et al.*, 2021). The supportive and innovative types of the cultures are employee and result oriented, while in such types of the cultures, the employees are encouraged and supported by the co-workers, managers

and supervisors and this environment also causes in bringing the new suggestions and ideas for the improvement of the organisations and in such environments, the employees also take part in the process of decision making, hence employee become happier and more self-motivated in as a result. Employees become highly satisfied with organisational environment and their jobs and responsibilities (Abraham *et al.*, 1997; Syakur *et al.*, 2020; Powell *et al.*, 2021).

The scholars (Awan and Mahmood, 2010; Putriana and Riady, 2015; Tyagi and Moses, 2020) examined the relations in between the organisational culture and employee commitment and the results of their studies showed that staff working under bureaucratic organisational cultures are not highly committed. As there is less job growth in that environment therefore, the employees are observed to be less satisfied with the organisation (Powell *et al.*, 2021). Hence, it is concluded that there exists a direct positive relationship between organisational culture and organisational commitment. A better organisational culture may result in the higher commitments of the employees to the organisation (Hardcopf *et al.*, 2021).

2.6.3. Organisational justice

Organisational justice is defined as a fair manner of resources allocation (Lee, 2001; Engelbrecht and Samuel, 2019) to reward the employees (Adams, 1963; Shahid *et al.*, 2020) to enhance the organisation-employee relationship (Bies and Tyler, 1990; Olowookere *et al.*, 2020) by correct decision making of the top management (Cropanzano *et al.*, 2001; Olowookere *et al.*, 2020) and normally divided into three types of interactional, procedural and distributive justice (Colquitt, 2002; Alsaree, 2020).

The **career development** and **training opportunities**, the **fair reward system** and the **empowerment** in the organisations makes a fair environment. Organisational justice is considered as a notion related to the individual's psychological perception of the effort and time investment in the organisation (Choi, 2013; Supriya and Dadhabhai, 2020). Hence, justice could also be the proportion of inputs and rewards based on the individual's expectation, and between individual and organisation (Ogbu and Ugwu, 2019).

Employees' justice perceptions are inspired by the received outcomes from the company. It includes the procedures, practices and policies and the features of the perceiving individual, such as the traits of personality and demographic traits (Cohen-Charash and Spector, 2001; Jang, 2021). The exchange theory has helped to systematise the organisational justice which has been proposed by Homans (1961) and it has also a connection with the individual motivational feelings (Adams, 1965; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). The organisation performance is an outcome of an individual's feeling of fairness and justice.

The investments and ratio of rewards are required to be on satisfactory level to generate feelings of justice (Adams, 1965; Malhota and Sharom, 2020). However, employees become dissatisfied, and their performance reduces which ultimately makes them aware of injustice when the ratio of rewards levels does not match their input levels (Waibo *et al.*, 2020).

Organisational justice is referred to the fairness which is perceived as the social and economic exchanging between individuals and their companies (Rai, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2015; Malhota and Sharom, 2020; Jang, 2021). Organisational justice is generally distributed into three categories of interactional, procedural, and distributive justice (Colquitt, 2002; Alsaree, 2020; Lopez *et al.*, 2021). The distributive type of justice is referred to fairness in context of the equal distributions of the outcome of the organisation between the members or staff (Jones, 1998; Colquitt *et al.*, 2001; Muchinsky, 2008; Alsaree, 2020). The distributive justice is also observed to be existing in the equal distributions of the rewards, benefits, and compensation as per the expectations of the employees in accordance with their inputs (Clay-Warner *et al.*, 2005; Chou, 2009; Ogbu and Ugwu, 2019). However, the distributive type of the justice focusses on the outcome, but procedural justice focuses on the processes which lead to the results required to the organisation (Konovsky and Cropanzano, 1991; Cropanzano and Greenberg, 1997; Olowookere *et al.*, 2020).

Other scholars also recommended that the procedural justice is important as the impact of the distributive justice is lower (Lind and Tyler, 1988; Tyler, 1990; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). The authors argued that "fair procedures are valued because they ultimately lead to favourable outcomes" (Lipponen *et al.*, 2004, p. 276). The summarised form of the previous research describes those perceptions of the individuals about the fair distribution of the outcome and confidence of the employees on the process of the distributions of the outcomes are interacted

with each other and it also affects the commitment level of the members of the organisation towards organisational goals (Taxman and Gordon, 2009; Lopez *et al.*, 2021). The authors Bies and Moag (1986) recommended that the interactional justice is another dimension of the organisational justice. The interactional justice is the distinct perception of a fair procedure adapted for resolving dispute and allocating the outcome equally (Bies and Moag, 1986; Bies, 2005; Pillai *et al.*, 1999; Waibo *et al.*, 2020). Thus, these perceptions of the interactions have significant impact on the level of commitment and job satisfaction of the employees (Colquitt, 2001; Loi *et al.*, 2009; Alsaree, 2020; Jang, 2021).

The conclusion of these studies proved that the procedural, distributive, and interpersonal justices were directly related in positive manner to the level of job satisfaction (Brockner and Wiesenfeld, 1996; Engelbrecht and Samuel, 2019; Malhota and Sharom, 2020). The employees utilise the perceptions of the interactional and procedural justices while determining or evaluating the distribution of the outcomes in a fair manner (Colquitt *et al.*, 2001; Brockner *et al.*, 2008; Ogbu and Ugwu, 2019; Malhota and Sharom, 2020). The research recommend that perceptions of the organisational justice are also correlated with the other factors such as organisational commitment (Kwong and Leung, 2002; Supriya and Dadhabhai, 2020), job satisfaction (Dowden and Tellier, 2004; Waibo *et al.*, 2020), legitimacies (Lines, 2005; Malhota and Sharom, 2020) and trust levels (Lambert *et al.*, 2007; Griffin and Taxman and Gordon, 2009; Jang, 2021).

Organisational justice despite the shift in ultimate responsibility and ownership, ensures the value of investing in the comprehensive career-development process is still widely recognised and informed by needs such as attracting and retaining high-performing employees and the need to instill a mindset of continuous learning and improving employee satisfaction with opportunities for career growth (Mason, Chua, Roux and Kaye, 1999) cited in Meyer (2002). Kaye (1999) states that for such company's career development is not a programme, but a process that integrates and supports ongoing activities and thereby maximising the value of on-the-job experiences with training and development.

2.6.4. Organisational climate

Organisational climate is defined as a sentimental, intellectual, and influential environment (Carr *et al.*, 2003; Goswami *et al.*, 2020) considerate of personal wellbeing of employees (Leigh, 1996; Ali *et al.*, 2020) to build ethical attitude and policies, corporate behaviour of employees (Vidaver Cohen, 1998; Jha and Singh, 2019) to enhance organisational commitment (Brown,1996; Shinde *et al.*, 2020) in instrumental, cognitive, and affective atmosphere of an organisation (Ostroff, 1993; Omole *et al.*, 2019; Malhota and Sharom, 2020).

Baumgartel (1971) expressed that organisational climate is a leadership practices' product. It involves the communication processes, and systematic features of working relationship among individuals and organisation (Reichers and Schneider 1990; Shinde *et al.*, 2020). On the other hand, Hoy and Forsyth (1986) has defined it as the perceptions of the individuals relevant to their working environment (Choudhary and Khan, 2021). They further elaborated it as a sustaining quality which employees experience influencing their behaviour, and it is established based on the employees' collective perceptions (Ho and Lin, 2021). Similarly, Owens (1987) defined organisational climate as the working environment related perceptions of the employees (Ostroff, 1993; Omole *et al.*, 2019). However, Recihers and Schneiders (1990) gave a new perspective to organisational climate. They referred organisational climate as the shared perceptions about the processes and practices in the organisation (Carr *et al.*, 2003; Goswami *et al.*, 2020). Contrarily, Rentsch (1990) defined organisational climate in terms of its reference as psychological meaningfulness to the practices, procedures and policies, which tend to stay longer in the organisation and are regarded as objective properties (Kahn, 1990; Brown and Leigh 1996; Ali *et al.*, 2020).

Katz and Kahn (1996) referred to the climate as an atmosphere where individuals help each other, judge the activities, reward, and find solutions for problems which influence moral values and attitudes of the individuals towards their work and the organisation (Chen and Komorita 1994; Jha and Singh, 2019). Thus, there is a variety in the views of scholars on the dimension of organisational climate (Hart *et al.*, 2000; Madhukar and Sharma, 2017; Al-Kurdi *et al.*, 2020). It is also because the organisational environment varies from one another and everyone in the organisation has diverse perceptions and knowledge about it. In an organisation and across various organisations each employee observes organisational climate from the personalised perspective and role in the organisation (Kras and Whatley, 1990; McKinnis and Natella, 1994; Goswami *et al.*, 2020; Iftikhar *et al.*, 2021). The scholars Brown and Leigh (1996, p. 360) illustrated the two characteristics as:

“a higher order level of meaning indicating an employee’s interpretation of the significance of the organisational environment for personal wellbeing” (McKinnis and Natella, 1994; Goswami *et al.*, 2020; Choudhary and Khan, 2021).

The concept of the “psychological safety” as a dimension of the organisational climate is referred to the feelings of the employees with her or his organisation which are pertaining to the aspects relevant to the perceptions of the supportive types of the managements. (Brown and Leigh 1996; Kahn, 1990; Ali *et al.*, 2020; Ho and Lin, 2021). The authors (Eisenberger *et al.*, 1986; Sopiyyana, 2020) described that the consequences of the supportive types of behaviours appear in terms of the favourable organisational climate while individual may have the feelings of reciprocating the favourable organisational treatments with positive behaviours and attitudes (Eustace and Martins, 2014; Riad and Nawar, 2016; Biswas *et al.*, 2020). The studies have shown that there exists a mentored relationship in between the “protégé” and “mentor” as for example, practices of support have positive relation with the loyalties of the employees to their organisations (Payne and Huffman, 2005; Sethibe, 2018; Loh *et al.*, 2019).

Moreover, authors (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Hawkins, 2019; Samsudin *et al.*, 2020) recommended that organisational commitment is increased by working in a supportive environment and it also increases the senses of personal freedoms of the employees at the workplace. Hence, in positive emotional related climates, the employees are perceived to be more supportive towards the objectives. Therefore, the employees shall have strong emotional bond with the organisation (Chen and Komorita 1994; Jha and Singh, 2019; Choudhary and Khan, 2021). Thus, it may be predicted that the psychological safety of the employee may contribute to the development of the organisational commitment of the employee (Schechter, 1985; Leana *et al.*, 1992; Ali *et al.*, 2020).

The employees having perceptions of supportive environment will have feelings of owing the goals and they would tend to perform as per the expectations of the organisation (Davis-LaMastro and Fasolo, 1990; Brown and Leigh 1996; Ali *et al.*, 2020; Ho and Lin, 2021).

2.6.5. Employee behaviour

A behaviour which construes the activities of the organisations (Birnbaum and Somers, 2000; Choi *et al.*, 2020) to integrate the individual attitudes with the motives of the organisation (Guest, 1987; Landers, 2019) by developing and integrating the values and (Arthur, 1994; Chaudhary, 2020) which connects employee's needs with organisational goals (Walton, 1985; Kim and Luengalongkot, 2020).

Employee behaviour is referred as the reaction of employees to certain situations in the organisation demonstrating the norms, values and overall culture of the organisation also adhering to the rules and regulations of the organisation at the same time (Lee, 1998; Gould-Williams, 2004; Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Mostafa *et al.*, 2019).

“High-commitment” system of management is capable of shaping the attitudes and behaviours of the employees as it evolves the “psychological links” between the goals of the employee and aims of the organisation (Gould-Williams, 2004; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Bysted, 2013; Mowbray *et al.*, 2020). However, the managers using the highly regulated human resource management system tend to have highly committed employees that may also be trusted while using their discretions in allocating duties in such a manner which is consistent to the goals of the organisation (Lee, 1998; Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Chaudhary, 2020). The author (Gould-Williams, 2004; Emerson *et al.*, 2020) also claimed that firms having “soft” and highly committed approaches induced in the human resource management system may increase the performance of the employees and it may also empower the employees by developing the trust level to achieve the goals of the organisation in mutual interest of self aims of the employees (Kim *et al.*, 2021). Thus, implication of this argument of highly committed human resource management practices shall yield the signals of trust of employees to the top management while in reciprocate, the employee shall be more committed to the organisation (Perry and Hondeghem, 2008; Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Mowbray *et al.*, 2020).

Therefore, it is evident that, the organisational commitment is the function of employee behaviour, their trust level and ultimately performance of the staff working in the organisation.

Thus, achieving the employee behaviours in the same manner to the characteristics of the organisation is the aim of the management (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Gould-Williams *et al.*, 2004; Veetikazhi *et al.*, 2021). The reasons which drive the organisational commitment are diverse in terms of the origin and nature (Bashir and Ramay, 2008; Fischer and Hyder, 2020).

It has also been argued that organisational mission and values drive the behaviours of the employees as it is claimed by the authors (Perry and Hondeghem, 2008, p. 3) that:

“Individual motives that are largely, but not exclusively, altruistic and are grounded in public institutions.”

Hence, in following up these authors it is recommended that the roles of human resource management practices may result in improving the employees’ behaviour and it also causes to improve the satisfaction level of the employees (Lee, 1998; Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Mowbray *et al.*, 2020). Hence, organisational mission plays a vital role in building organisational commitment by improving the employee behaviours (Gould-Williams, 2004; Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Snape and Redman, 2010; Fischer and Hyder, 2020).

Therefore, using a model which is comprised of both the high committed human resource management practices and motivational systems, the organisational commitment may be improved (Gould-Williams and Davies, 2005; Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Veetikazhi *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, the scholars (Brewster *et al.*, 2000; Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Bysted, 2013; Choi *et al.*, 2020; Veetikazhi *et al.*, 2021) concluded that to estimate the behaviours of the employees working in the organisation, it is necessary to consider the social aspects of the employees such as culture, values, concepts, languages and needs of the area where organisation is operating.

2.6.6. Management style

Management style is defined as success striving style of management (Mintzberg, 1980; Wirtz, 2019) which controls, co-ordinates, organises and plans activities (Henry, 1916; Saxena, 2019) in a team leading and power management manner (Thomas, 1994; Hastings *et al.*, 2019) for improving effectiveness (Margerison, 1979; Arsto *et al.*, 2019) through interpersonal characteristics of decisions making to achieve the main objectives of an organisation (Elwood, 1990; Titon and Pettan, 2019; Yin and Liao, 2020).

The management style determines the utilisation of authority which is the key factor in shaping the behaviours (Terzi and Kurt, 2005; Beydilli and Kurt, 2020). Likert (1961) has classified

the behaviour of managers as benevolent-authoritative, exploitative-authoritative, participative, and consultative. In Blake and Mouton's (1964, p. 21) proposed the managerial grid model:

“Management styles were classified as impoverished management, produce-or-perish management, middle-of-the-road management, country club management and team management”.

Başaran (2008) proposed a classification from autocratic to **democratic style** as **authoritarian**, **protective**, **supportive**, and **cooperative** management style. Hence, management style is a significant factor in the formation of employees' organisational behaviour (Başaran, 2008; Saeed *et al.*, 2014; Yin and Liao, 2020). The management styles significantly contribute to the failure or success of the organisation. The management styles are directly related to the motivation level and performance of the employees (Bass, 1990; Iverson and Roy, 1994; Arsto *et al.*, 2019; Titon and Pettan, 2019). The participative type of the management style is also related to the flatter type of the organisational structure where there is less distance between the low powered and high-powered employees (Chen, 2001; Saeed *et al.*, 2014; Yin and Liao, 2020).

In bigger universities particularly government sector universities the bureaucratic management system is prevalent, and it is one sided top to bottom communication. In participative management style the employees are involved in the decision-making process.

Conversely, the firms being operating in many developing countries are bureaucratic and hierarchical where decision making is central, and decisions are also made on the bases of the standard defined policies of the organisations (Cavone and Manzini, 2000; Quang and Vuong, 2002; Anwar and Chaker, 2003; Alanoglu, 2020). The management responsibilities tend to be distributed on the bases of seniority, authority, and position in such types of organisations. (Cavone and Manzini, 2000; Chen, 2001; Yin and Liao, 2020). These types of organisations are often managed by the persons dominant in the organisation due to the political scenario created in the organisation (Beydilli and Kurt, 2020). Therefore, the management style is affected by the types of structure of the organisation (Chen, 2001; Saeed *et al.*, 2014; Malkoc and Dal, 2021). Hence, literature proves that job satisfaction and commitment is enhanced due

to participative management style (Purcell, 1987; Cavone and Manzini, 2000; Quang and Vuong, 2002; Abun, 2021).

It is evident that the age, tenure, and position of the leader having certain management style have high relationship with the level of commitment of the employees (Saeed *et al.*, 2014; Anwar and Chaker, 2003; Beydilli and Kurt, 2020). The employees with high level of position who have been working in the same type of the jobs for a longer period are more experienced and higher aged, therefore the level of commitment is observed to be very higher (Sommer *et al.*, 1996; Saxena, 2019; Alanoglu, 2020). The authors (Chen and Francesco, 2000; Arsto *et al.*, 2019) collected data of the three hundred thirty-three employees working in the People Republic of China and deduced that job positions are positively related with the level of commitment of the employee while other demographic factors such as tenure and age were not considered in this research study. (Chen, 2001; Arsto *et al.*, 2019; Malkoc and Dal, 2021).

The culture of the organisations may have influences on how people aim their professional and personal goal, perform the task, and use the resource to achieve the goals as per the style of management given to them (Saeed *et al.*, 2014; Anwar and Chaker, 2003; Beydilli and Kurt, 2020). The culture of the organisation also impacts unconsciously and consciously on the perceptions, decision making and ultimately management style of the organisation by which feeling, acts and perception of the employees is affected (Schein, 1990; Titon and Pettan, 2019; Abun, 2021). Thus, the organisational culture influences the management style, commitment, and performance at large (Goffee and Jones, 1998; Wallach, 1983; Hastings *et al.*, 2019; Alanoglu, 2020).

2.7. OUTCOMES OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

The consequence of the organisational commitment is organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) as per the previous research studies conducted the relationship of these factors and proved the positive relationship between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour (Rao and Kamel, 2021). The discretionary employee behaviour which is referred as organisational citizenship behaviour is an outcome of the antecedents of organisational commitment (Organ, 1988; Van *et al.*, 2001 Stanley *et al.*, 2002; Rao and Kamel, 2021). The committed employees and characterised to volunteer extra activities at

workplace which is considered as organisational citizenship behaviour and is this relation may also be enhanced by the formal reward system in the organisations (Meyer and Allen, 1996; Herscovitch and Meyer, 2001; Ryan and Organ, 1995; Jameel *et al.*, 2020).

Organisational citizenship behaviour can arise from various factors in the organisation, including job satisfaction and employee commitment (Bies and Organ, 1989; Capaldi, 1992; Rao and Zaidi, 2020; Zeinabadia, 2010; Tasar *et al.*, 2020) Hence, when employees feel satisfied with the organisation overall it will result as improved performance. Likewise, employees who have a high commitment towards the organisation will put all the efforts to progress the firm as they believe in their performance at work (Qing *et al.*, 2019; Dubey *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, when employees already have a high commitment to the company, they wholeheartedly have satisfaction at work. The scholars (Purnama, 2013; Kazemipour *et al.*, 2012; Djaelani *et al.*, 2020, and Supriyanto *et al.*, 2020) found that organisational commitment has a direct influence on organisational citizenship behaviour of employees.

2.7.1. Organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB)

Organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is the engagement to the work which is expressed by an individual outside the expected duties (Organ, 1988; Podsakoff *et al.*, 2000; Lambert, 2003; Jameel *et al.*, 2020) by devoting the efforts towards the objectives of the organisation to an extra mile (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Hall *et al.*, 2009; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Teng *et al.*, 2020) to be attached and get identified in the organisation (Organ and Bateman, 1983; Meyer, 1990; Hawkins, 2019; Ahmad and Kaleem, 2020) without any expectation of formal rewards (Allen, 1990; Appelbaum *et al.*, 2004; Kuncoro and Wibowo, 2019) that results in increase in effectiveness and performance of the organisation (Meyer and Allen, 1990; Kloutsiniotis and Mihail, 2020; Rao and Zaidi, 2020).

Rika (2018) defined organisational citizenship behaviour as a behavioural form that is not regulated by the organisation rather it is an individual's choice and self- initiative and not related to any official reward system as a result increases overall organisational effectiveness (Teh and Sun, 2012; Emami *et al.*, 2012; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). Dimitriades (2007), asserts that organisational citizenship behaviour as an individual behaviour which enhances the functioning in the organisation by volunteer employee behaviour

without any explicit rewarding (Tsai and Wu, 2010; Kaur and Sharma, 2020; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). Similarly, organisational citizenship behaviour explains a set of volunteer group of behaviours which are not the formal responsibility of an employee; but it helps to enhance their roles in organisation (Engelbrecht and Schlechter, 2006; Mohammad *et al.*, 2011; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Rao and Zaidi, 2020).

2.7.2. OCB a discretionary behaviour

Discretionary effort is often called ‘going the extra mile’. If your employee is committed to your organisation, it’s something they’re likely to be doing on a regular basis. It’s the difference between what you have to do, and what you want to do in the workplace. Engaged employees will go beyond the call of duty in order to get the best possible results from their work. They’re ready to put in the hard graft for the business and do more to help you succeed.

Dennis Organ (1988, p. 148) defined it as, “organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) refers to discretionary, nonrequired contributions by members to the organisations that employ them” (Mohammad *et al.*, 2011; Emami *et al.*, 2012; Teh and Sun, 2012; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). The organisational citizenship behaviour was also defined by Organ (1988) as, “Individual behaviour that is discretionary, not explicitly recognised by the formal system and that in the aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the organisation (Tsai and Wu, 2010; Mohammad *et al.*, 2011; Khaola and Rambe, 2020; Maamari *et al.*, 2021). By discretionary, we mean that the behaviour is not an enforceable requirement of the role or job description, that is, the clearly specifiable terms of the person’s employment contract with the organisation; the behaviour is rather a matter of personal choice, such that its omission is not generally understood as punishable” (p. 4).

2.7.3. The trigger factors for a discretionary behaviour (OCB)

Yes, meaning is an essential part of creating an engaging employee experience. In a 2016 report, Deloitte also found there are four other main elements for managers to focus their attentions on:

2.7.4. Motivation

It's best to concentrate management efforts on the aspects that can be influenced and controlled. To truly focus on improving performance, employees need to know their work really makes a difference. A sense of accomplishment is vital to instil to create meaningful people engagement. Maslow proposed that motivation is the result of a person's attempt at fulfilling five basic needs: physiological, safety, social, esteem and self-actualization. According to Maslow (1954), these needs can create internal pressures that can influence a person's behaviour (Emami *et al.*, 2012; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Fischer and Walker, 2020).

Figure 2. 1: Maslow's hierarchy of needs

Source: Maslow (1954) Hierarchy of needs

2.7.5. Growth opportunities

The managers can set specific goals and tasks and give feedback to boost performance and engagement in a measurable way. They can give recognition where it's due by telling employees that they matter and providing them career growth opportunities alongside giving rewards and incentives can help engage the employees which works as a catalyst to the discretionary behaviour OCB (Emami *et al.*, 2012; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Fischer and Walker, 2020).

2.7.6. Positive work environment

The positive work environment is a product of many organisational factors such as the structure of the organisation, the culture, climate, management style and justice. These factors cover almost all the features within the organisation to create a positive working environment (Organ *et al.*, 2006; Jameel *et al.*, 2020; Ismael and Andrea, 2021). Hence each of these factors contributes to OCB and hence these will be examined in detail in this research through qualitative study findings.

However, this behaviour might be negatively affected by affective disposition, poor organisational climate, and organisation commitment. The scholar (Katz, 1964) observed that the organisations require cooperation to enhance the efficiency and performance of the organisation and it was described as, “an organisation which depends solely upon its blueprints for prescribed behaviour is a fragile social system” (Katz, 1964, pp. 132; Emami *et al.*, 2012; Engelbrecht and Schlechter, 2006; Morales and Pasamar, 2019). The organisational citizenship behaviour is very necessary for the survival of the organisations. It is also mentioned by the Katz (1964) that, “Within every work group in a factory, within any division in a government bureau, or within any department of a university are countless acts of cooperation without which the system would break down. We take these everyday acts for granted, and a few, if any, form the role prescriptions for any job” (p. 132). Thirdly, the organisation may show, “innovative and spontaneous behaviour performance beyond role requirements for accomplishments of organisational functions” (Jameel *et al.*, 2020).

The scholars (Organ *et al.*, 2006; Jameel *et al.*, 2020; Ismael and Andrea, 2021) observed that employee he who cooperate with other employees to enhance or protect the system of the organisation causes promotion of the favourable working environment. “Organisational citizenship behaviour is a group of organisationally beneficial behaviours and gestures that can be neither enforced on the basis of formal role obligations nor elicited by contractual guarantee of recompense” (Organ, 1990, p. 46; Nazarian *et al.*, 2020).

Thus, the above-mentioned definition of the organisational citizenship behaviour has three main aspects; firstly, the job requirements of the employee may not be compromised by the citizenship behaviours (Rao and Zaidi, 2020; Rao and Kamel, 2021; Ismael and Andrea, 2021). Secondly, there is no formal reward system for the citizenship behaviour. Thirdly, the

citizenship behaviours are contributing to the effectiveness of the organisation when accumulated across time and peoples (Emami *et al.*, 2012; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Fischer and Walker, 2020). The organisational citizenship behaviour is a type of extra-roles which are based on the assisting the colleague or displaying the conscientiousness for organisation (Finkelstein and Penner, 2004; Ahmad and Kaleem, 2020; Maamari *et al.*, 2021). The managers or employers may not impose this type of behaviour and may not prompt the immediate or specific rewards to the employees for performing as per requirements of the organisational citizenship behaviour (Organ *et al.*, 2006; Jameel *et al.*, 2020; Ismael and Andrea, 2021).

2.8. OUTCOMES OF ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR

The literature review proves that the consequences of the organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) are appeared in terms of the individual as well as organisational performance. OCB is explained as the attitude that “go above and beyond the call of duty” (Rao and Zaidi, 2020; Soelton *et al.*, 2020; Utami *et al.*, 2021). OCB is described as “individual behaviours that are discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognised by the formal reward system, and that in aggregate promote the effective functioning of an organisation” (Organ, 1988; Hassi, 2019; Rawabdeh *et al.*, 2019; Rao and Kamel, 2021). These attitudes are considered to “lubricate the social machinery of the organisation” (Organ and Bateman, 1983; Khaola and Rambe, 2020; Khan and Khan, 2021).

Soelton *et al.*, 2020 explained OCB as the follows,

“According to Organ in Melinda, Rika (2018), organisational citizenship behaviour is a form of behaviour that is an individual choice and initiative, not related to the organisation's formal reward system but in the aggregate increases organisational effectiveness. Dimitriades (2007), defines OCB as individual behaviour that is free, is not directly or explicitly related to the reward system and can enhance the company's effective functioning”.

Birnbaum and Somers (1998) and Munene (1995) analysed the direct relationship between individual performance and OCB and observed high correlation between OCB and individual performance (Dubey *et al.*, 2020). The research work also shown the positive relationship between individual performance and OCB by the scholars (Diefendorff *et al.*, 2002; Somech

and Bolger, 2004; Chu *et al.*, 2005; Moberg and Rotenberry, 2007; Dubey *et al.*, 2020; Maamari *et al.*, 2021). The perception of individual about duties assigned to them is influenced by the OCBs (Ryan and Organ, 1995; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Manezhe and Ngirande, 2021). The individual job performance is referred to the job involvement of the employee which is the psychological identification of an individual in an organisation to his job commitment (Kanungo, 1982a; Hassi, 2019; Soelton *et al.*, 2020). Individual performance is also defined as extent to “which one is cognitively preoccupied with, engaged in, and concerned with one’s present job” (Paullay *et al.*, 1994, p. 224; Rawabdeh *et al.*, 2019). The high performance of an employee is the measure of self-esteem of an individual of an organisation (Kejner and Lodahl, 1965; Kaur and Sharma, 2020). Hence due to this, individual those who are good in job involvement generally concerned about duties given to them (Kanungo, 1982b; Hawkins, 2019; Nazarian *et al.*, 2020).

The scholars described that the OCB is a type of employee’s behaviour by virtue of which employee perform the duties beyond the responsibilities assigned to him. Van Dyne *et al.* (1994) described that OCBs are main driving factors of behaviours of employees which cause consolidation between the employee and goals of the institute, and thus this realisation of the main goals of the institute causes an enhanced performance of the organisation (Hag and Jahangir, 2004; Fischer *et al.*, 2020; Dubey *et al.*, 2020). Hence, OCB is a series of admirable and positive organisational behaviour which transmits the multi-dimensional correlations with the performance and consequences of organisation in a positive manner (Jahangir and Hag, 2004; Tasar *et al.*, 2020), and the core functional behaviour of organisations are justified by OCB (Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Dubey *et al.*, 2020; Pratono and Han, 2021). Organ *et al.* (2006) introduced the main theme of the OCB in the era of 1980’s (Yu and Hua, 2011; Hassi, 2019; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). It was observed by Organ (2006) that organisational citizenship behaviour is an optional activity which is not directly defined in the reward system of an organisation, but it improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the performance of organisation (Appelbaum *et al.*, 2004; Hall *et al.*, 2009; Fischer *et al.*, 2020). The word “optional”, meant that the behaviour of organisational commitment is not formally described in the job descriptions of the employees, and OCB is not part of contract of employment for people, therefore it is defined to be the optional activity, and there will no consequences of non-following of behaviour for organisational commitment of the employee (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2000, p. 541; Kaur and Sharma, 2020).

2.8.1. Individual performance

Individual performance is defined as the state of employees fulfilling the job requirements (Lodahl, 1965) to the extent that it enhances job commitment and involvement (Kanungo, 1982a; Febrina and Syamsir, 2020) to engage and pre-occupy to the responsibilities given (Paullay *et al.*, 1994; Fontannaz and Osthuizen, 2007; Truss *et al.*, 2013; Bakotic, 2016) by indulging and involving effectively and efficiently with the work yielding required results (Kanungo, 1982b; Tenrisau *et al.*, 2019; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020).

Similarly, to conceptualise individual performance the scholar Soelton *et al.* (2020) has emphasised on the below dimensions,

“According to Sedarmayanti (2011) revealed that performance that means the work of a worker, a management process or an organisation, where the results of the work must be demonstrated concrete and measurable evidence (compared to predetermined standards). Simamora's opinion (Mangkunegara, 2009) which says that performance is influenced by three factors or dimensions, namely individual factors / dimensions (individual attributes), psychological factors / dimensions (work effort), and organisational support factors/dimensions.”

The individual performance is mainly divided into two broad categories known as the contextual performance and the task performance as observed from the previous studies (Truss *et al.*, 2013; Yuniawan and Udin, 2020). The contextual performance occurs due to the distinct task-oriented activities (Borman and Motowidlo, 1997; Loan, 2020; Yuniawan and Udin, 2020). However, the task performance is referred to the efficiency of the individual to perform those activities that are contributing to the main goals of the organisation (Truss *et al.*, 2013; Bakotic, 2016; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020; Dorta-Afonso *et al.*, 2021). The purpose of the organisation may also be achieved even part of the activity is performed by the employee in the operational process of the organisation, or it may be performed indirectly due to provision of the required resource to the organisation by the employee (De Araujo and Lopes, 2014; Semedo *et al.*, 2016; Febrina and Syamsir, 2020).

Therefore, the contextual performance reflects the behaviour which do not support the technical cores or main operations. The employees assist the organisation in the broader way in its

psychological and social environment (Fontannaz and Osthuizen, 2007; Brown *et al.*, 2011; Truss *et al.*, 2013; Yuniawan and Udin, 2020; Salas-Vallina *et al.*, 2021). Hence, the contextual performance is distinct from the task performance by the following three main reasons (Borman and Motowidlo, 1997; De Araujo and Lopes, 2014; Bakotic, 2016; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020). Firstly, the task behaviour keeps changing on the bases of the job responsibilities, while the contextual behaviours remain consistent across various types of the jobs (Febrina and Syamsir, 2020; Yuniawan and Udin, 2020). Secondly, the task behaviour is prescribed on the bases of the roles while contextual behaviour is not prescribed on the bases of the roles assigned to the employees (De Araujo and Lopes, 2014; Semedo *et al.*, 2016; Sahertian and Sunaryo, 2020). Thirdly, antecedent of the task performance is based on the cognitive abilities, while antecedent of the contextual performances is based on the personality traits (Truss *et al.*, 2013; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020).

The arguments for isolating the task performance from the contextual performance are given as 1) Both task and contextual performance may contribute to the overall individual worth of the organisation. 2) Each task and contextual performance may correlate to various characteristics and abilities of the individuals working in the organisation (Semedo *et al.*, 2016; Loan, 2020; Febrina and Syamsir, 2020; Han *et al.*, 2021).

However, Organ (1997) acknowledged that it is observed there is no clarity in between the “social and psychological environment” and “supporting environment” which promotes the individual performance. The performance as provided by the individual have the psychological and social impacts. Therefore, the definition of the OCB may correlate and create confusion to the definition of the individual performance as narrated by the authors (Borman and Motowidlo, 1997; Truss *et al.*, 2013; Bakotic, 2016; Nadeak *et al.*, 2021).

2.8.2. Organisational performance

Organisational performance is defined as the capability of an organisation to attain its main objectives (Daft, 2000; Bakotic, 2016; Moneva *et al.*, 2020) of economic efficiency and effectiveness (Chandler, 1993; Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019; Haque, 2020; Bhuiyan *et al.*, 2020) as an aspect of productivity in consistent and quality control manner (Hefferman and Flood, 2000; Pinho *et al.*, 2014; Asif *et al.*, 2019; Moneva *et al.*, 2020) which indicates the

consistency, quality, and other aspects (Waggoner *et al.*, 1999; Wade, 2001; Ongori, 2009; Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019; Haque, 2020).

Pinho *et al.* (2014) emphasised that evaluation of business performance is an important management aspect that outlines the steady improvements in the business. Therefore, administrators have understood importance of continuous evaluation of performance as they are applying different methods to performance evaluation in the organisations (Fernandes *et al.*, 2006; Boxall and Macky, 2007; Chandrasekar, 2011; Pinho *et al.*, 2014; Kopp *et al.*, 2020). Hence, according to the scholars (Waggoner *et al.*, 1999; Ongori, 2009; Rasula *et al.*, 2012; Haque, 2020; Bhuiyan *et al.*, 2020) from 1850 to 1975, organisations had assessed performance solely as financial criterion, as they had been disparaged for a reason for example this encourages the short-term effectiveness, but on the other hand it is lacking in strategic concentrations and lacking ability in provisions to quality, responsiveness, and flexibilities. Hence, it also fails in establishing the ideas of customers' desires, feedback, and competitor analysis (Kaplan and Norton, 1992; Shahin *et al.*, 2012; Alsayyed *et al.*, 2020; Liu and Kianto, 2021).

2.8.3. Job satisfaction

The relationship of organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction in the organisations have been proved by many researchers. Thus, many scholars have investigated a favourable relationship among there constructs, greater commitment results in higher performance (Abdul Rashid *et al.*, 2003; Rotenberry and Moberg, 2007; Fu and Deshpande, 2014; Nwibere, 2014; Loan, 2020). The satisfaction of employees with the work promotion, fair treatment and overall support at work tends to increase their performance (Eslami and Gharakhani, 2012; Tuu and Liem, 2012; Anh and Dao, 2013; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020).

Job satisfaction is defined as an effective orientation of employee towards the role assigned (Vroom, 1964; Orgambidez and Extremera, 2020; Saputra and Riana, 2021) to the extent by which employee is rewarded (Moorman *et al.*, 1993; Statt, 2004; Indarti *et al.*, 2017; Candelario *et al.*, 2020) in suitable environmental, psychological, and physiological conditions (Hoppock, 1935; Madhukar and Sharma, 2017; Romi and Ahman, 2020) by fulfilling both psychological

and material needs of an employee (Moorman *et al.*, 1993; Aziri, 2008; Prasetio *et al.*, 2017; Asgari *et al.*, 2020; Moustofa and Muafi, 2021) to get sum of believes and feelings that employee have about their job at workplace (George *et al.*, 2008; Kanimozhi, 2019; Silitonga *et al.*, 2020; Karuna, 2021).

Similarly, Aziri (2011) defined job satisfaction as a feeling which is the result of the perception of the psychological and material needs achievement from job (Nwibere, 2014; Loan, 2020; Romi and Ahman, 2020). In other words, Lee (2009), defined job satisfaction as the perceptions of employees about the work and their feelings about the experience at work as well (Teh and Sun, 2012; Chhabra and Mohanty, 2014; Fischer *et al.*, 2020). Lee and Kim (2006) referred it as the perception of employees to the extent their expectations and needs at work are met (El-Nahas *et al.*, 2013; Prasetio *et al.*, 2017; Candelario *et al.*, 2020). However, Kim *et al.* (2011) extended this further and critically expressed that the feelings of employees are subjective, and it is not easy to measure it. It has been also analysed that job satisfaction is not only relevant to the unique features of the job role, but it is related to the dimensions of organisational compensations, that includes salary, promotion chances and career development (Schappe, 1998; Indarti *et al.*, 2017; Moustofa and Muafi, 2021; Saputra and Riana, 2021).

Thus, to assess the employees' attitudes managers have turned out to be increasingly attuned to it. Therefore, the mental and physical health of employees is influenced by job satisfaction. Overall, job satisfaction has been found to be an imperative element of the individual's quality work life. Hence, it is the component of the organisational social responsibility (Chhabra and Mohanty, 2014; Indarti *et al.*, 2017; Ali *et al.*, 2020; Soelton, 2020; Silitonga *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, according to the scholars (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Foote and Tang, 2008; Nwibere, 2014; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020) employees' loyalty to the organisation is denoted as organisational commitment. However, scholars emphasised that (Mohammad *et al.*, 2011; Indarti *et al.*, 2017; Asgari *et al.*, 2020) the members' desires to stay in the organisation willingness of members to remain in an organisation and the high-level commitment employees have a strong believe in the organisation and employees associate their individual identity to the visions, values, and objectives of the organisation. The employees with higher commitment levels exert more effort towards the organisation which consequently used as an indicator of overall beliefs and work climate (Prasetio *et al.*, 2017; Soelton, 2020; Djaelani *et al.*, 2021)

Hence, job satisfaction may vary and impact the organisational commitment in many ways, but commitment tends to stay comprehensively (Romi and Ahman, 2020; Motalebi and Marsap, 2020; Saputra and Riana, 2021). Organisational commitment affects to the organisation fully, whereas as a single aspect job satisfaction might be a response to certain activities only (Zeinabadi, 2010; Teh and Sun, 2012; Indarti *et al.*, 2017; Ali *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, job satisfaction relatively varies as compared to commitment which tends to be stay stable. The highly committed employees value the organisational worth and make considerable performance for the organisation (Kim *et al.*, 2011; El-Nahas *et al.*, 2013; Romi and Ahman, 2020).

Employees make efforts to tackle the challenges in the organisations which constitutes the vital components. Therefore, according to scholars (Berman, 2006; Prasetio *et al.*, 2017; Asgari *et al.*, 2020) employee performance is used to gain the set organisational results. Job satisfaction plays a critical moderating role in increasing organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour. It revives the need for practitioners and academics to discover for the important construction (Mallick and Lalatendu, 2015; Sani *et al.*, 2018; Motalebi and Marsap, 2020). Considering the crucial role of OCB in improving the individual and organisational performance (Hassi, 2019; Rawabdeh *et al.*, 2019; Rao and Zaidi, 2020; Pratono and Han, 2021), this study aims to examine the influence of organisational commitment on OCB through observing the moderating role of job satisfaction towards the performance.

2.9. THE RELATIONSHIP OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT WITH ITS INFLUENCING FACTORS

2.9.1. Organisational structure and organisational commitment

The behaviour and actions of the employees are controlled through the systematic manner of tasks and authority relationship for coordination and controlling the employees to gain the aims of the organisation is determined as the organisational structure (Schminke *et al.*, 2002; Al-Rasheed, 2003; Menguc and Auh, 2007; Jones, 2013; Tasic, 2019; Ehiorobo *et al.*, 2020). The arrangement of tasks and jobs in the formal manner (Coulter and Robbins, 2007; Komazec and Jevtic, 2012; Alblooshi *et al.*, 2020; Esfahani *et al.*, 2021) also describes how the regulations and rules are followed by the staff of an organisation after the allocation of responsibilities and

authorities (Nahm *et al.*, 2003; Ajagbe *et al.*, 2016; Noor *et al.*, 2020). The organisational structure emphasises on standardisation, formalisation, and centralisation as suggested by most of the literature (Obrist, 2020; Sener and Balli, 2020; Esfahani *et al.*, 2021).

The organisational structure has been very handy to control the staff of an organisation to get the required work outputs and to make sure that the tasks are being performed efficiently and effectively and are in line with the objectives and goals of an organisation (Walton, 2005; Katsikea *et al.*, 2011; Maduenyi *et al.*, 2015; Alblooshi *et al.*, 2020). The internal properties of a firm are indicated by the organisational structure (Daft, 1995; George, 2019; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). These internal properties get the attention which are crucial for success or failure of an organisation (Menguc and Auh, 2007; Zheng *et al.*, 2010; Alown *et al.*, 2020) and one of these major properties is organisational commitment. The employees are dedicated to achieving the objectives of the organisation by organisational commitment (Grawe *et al.*, 2012; Ajagbe *et al.*, 2016; Noor *et al.*, 2020). The commitment of employees and its sustainability is a key factor to gain effective and efficient performance of an organisation. The positive behaviour and attitudes of the employees is achieved using high levels of commitment of the staff (Martin and Shore, 1989; Sinclair *et al.*, 2005; Zafar and Chughtai, 2006; Srivastava, 2013; Ehiorobo *et al.*, 2020).

The literature related the organisational commitment and organisational structure proves that major studies are aiming to evaluate the direct relation of organisational structure and organisational commitment (Komazec and Jevtic, 2012; Alblooshi *et al.*, 2020; Sener and Balli, 2020; Esfahani *et al.*, 2021). However, few studies have analysed the relationship between organisational structure and organisational commitment particularly in different types of the firms or sectors. A little struggle has been made to find out the relationship of organisational structure with the outcomes of work in the Arab countries and particularly in Jordan (Al-Rasheed, 2003; Alown *et al.*, 2020).

2.9.2. Organisational culture and organisational commitment

The system of knowledge that “describes the ethics by virtue of which employees evaluate, believe, and perceive things is regarded as organisation culture which act as to relate the communities of the employees within the settings of environment” (Firsirotu and Allaire, 1984,

p. 198; Tyagi and Moses, 2020). The positive organisational culture of a company may result in the motivation of the employees that enhances the satisfaction level of the employees at workplace (Abraham *et al.*, 1997; Alqadre, 2019; Sunarsi, 2020). The motivated and satisfied employees tend to be committed with the organisation, therefore the positive organisational culture results in enhanced organisational commitment (Abraham *et al.*, 1997; Ravasi and Schultz, 2006; Xiaoming and Junchen, 2012; Sunarsi, 2020). The scholars (Putriana and Riady, 2015; Paais and Pattiruhu, 2020) studied the relationship between employee commitment, organisational culture, management style and job satisfaction. They found a direct relationship between organisational culture and employee commitment. However, their results show that there exists no significant relationship in the organisational commitment and organisational structure due to the bureaucratic leadership style of the top management.

Similarly, (Lok and Crawford, 2004; Asree *et al.*, 2010; Purnama, 2013; Chang *et al.*, 2021; Erlangga *et al.*, 2021) conducted the study to check the relationship between the organisational culture, organisational commitment and job satisfaction and it was observed the direct relation between organisational culture and organisational commitment. However, further study is required to be conducted to analyse organisational culture in terms of employee's satisfaction and organisational commitment (Chang *et al.*, 2021).

2.9.3. Organisational justice and organisational commitment

Organisational justice is referred as how the employees are treated in an organisation and the theoretical model is widely distributed in two types of main dimensions known as distributive and procedural justice of an organisation (Muchinsky, 2008; Engelbrecht and Samuel, 2019; Supriya and Dadhabhai, 2020). The equal distribution of the output profits of the organisation as per the employee's level of performance through a fair method is said to be the distributional justice (Jones, 1998; Chen *et al.*, 2015; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). While procedural justice is regarded as the main process of an organisation which leads to the outcomes of an organisation (Cropanzano and Konovsky, 1991; Greenberg and Cropanzano, 1997; Colquitt, 2002; Alsaree, 2020).

The attachment of an employee in a psychological manner to the organisation is described to be the organisational commitment that may be described in different types of the indicators

which are regarding the dedication of the employee to the aims of the organisation, feeling of internalising by the employee about the aims of the firm and loyalty of the employee with the organisation (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Wall and Cook, 1980; Chou, 2009; Olowookere *et al.*, 2020). There exists a linear significant relation in between organisational commitment, organisational justice and job satisfaction which is observed in the studies of the previous literature (Lambert *et al.*, 2007; Griffin *et al.*, 2010; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). However, the job satisfaction is assumed to be the mediating variable which is not generally considered in relationship between the organisational commitment and organisational justice (Ogbu and Ugwu, 2019; Malhota and Sharom, 2020; Jang, 2021).

Furthermore, the researchers recommended that the organisational justice's perception is directly related to the factors of an organisation such as commitment (Tellier and Dowden, 2004; Rai, 2013; Chen *et al.*, 2015; Malhota and Sharom, 2020), the legitimacy of an employee (Lines, 2005; Taxman and Gordon, 2009; Supriya and Dadhabhai, 2020), the trust of an employee (Lincoln and Kalleberg, 1990; Waibo *et al.*, 2020) and organisational citizenship behaviour of the employees (Hepburn, 2005; Lambert *et al.*, 2007; Griffin and Taxman and Gordon, 2009 Alsaree, 2020). The scholars (Farmer *et al.*, 2003; Loi *et al.*, 2009; Jang, 2021) evaluated the relation between organisational outcomes such as organisational citizenship behaviour and job performance with the organisational factors i.e., organisational justice and organisational commitment and upon survey of 271 participants, it was concluded that there exists a direct relationship between organisational justice and organisational commitment. Thus, the researchers (Lipponen *et al.*, 2004; Dollery and Currie, 2006; Muchinsky, 2008; Waibo *et al.*, 2020) observed that the perception of the employees about the support of organisation through organisational justice have positive relationship with organisational commitment level.

2.9.4. Organisational climate and organisational commitment

The scholars (Ostroff, 1993; Carr *et al.*, 2003; Omole *et al.*, 2019; Jha and Singh, 2019; Goswami *et al.*, 2020) conducted the research study as per the meta-analysis of the constructs of the organisational climate and described the climate of an organisation in three types of major dimensions which are instrumental, cognitive, and affective dimensions. These three dimensions of organisational climate are also endorsing the definition of organisational

commitment by the Leigh and Brown, (1996) defined the organisational climate as “a higher order level of meaning indicating an employee’s interpretation of the significance of the organisational environment for personal wellbeing.” (p. 360). As per the comprehensive definition of Leigh and Brown (1996) about organisational climate it is evident that the organisational climate is related to behaviour and attitudes of the employees and causes an enhanced organisational commitment (Hart *et al.*, 2000; Madhukar and Sharma, 2017; Al-Kurdi *et al.*, 2020; Goswami *et al.*, 2020; Iftikhar *et al.*, 2021).

Eisenberger *et al.* (1986) described that the management style of a supportive category may results in a positive organisational climate and favourable organisational climate may result in positive behaviours and attitudes of the employees that result in an increased organisational commitment of the employees (Kahn, 1990; Brown and Leigh 1996; Ali *et al.*, 2020; Ho and Lin, 2021). Thus, the latest studies prove a relationship of ‘mentor’ and ‘protégé’ which enhances support from the top management and results in an enhanced loyalty of the employees with the organisation and this enhanced loyalty caused an increase in organisational commitment (Payne and Huffman, 2005; Eustace and Martins, 2014; Riad and Nawar, 2016; Biswas *et al.*, 2020).

Similarly, Allen and Meyer (1997) recommended that support by the organisation to the employees in terms of organisational climate causes a sense of freedom of employees at site of work which increases organisational commitment (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Hawkins, 2019; Samsudin *et al.*, 2020). This perceived environment of support from the organisational climate strengthened the bond of employee with the organisation (Payne and Huffman, 2005; Sethibe, 2018). The workplace freedom of expression also plays a vital role in the improvement of the outcomes. It also acts as driving force for the commitment of the individual with the organisation because of feelings of employees that they might not be rejected or embarrassed while expressing themselves (Chen and Komorita, 1994; Jha and Singh, 2019; Ali *et al.*, 2020; Ho and Lin, 2021).

2.9.5. Employee behaviour and organisational commitment

The employee behaviour and attitudes are shaped using the sophisticated human resource management system which links the psychological needs of an employee with goals of the

organisation (Walton, 1985; Arthur, 1994; Gould-Williams, 2004; Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Mostafa *et al.*, 2019). It is also recommended that the employees' behaviour is used to interpret the actions of the organisation such as practices of HRM and trustworthiness of top management which act as an indicator of organisational commitment of employees (Birnbaum and Somers, 2000; Davies and Gould-Williams, 2005; Redman and Snape, 2010; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Mowbray *et al.*, 2020). Arthur (1994) also viewed that high committed HRM practices to boost the employee behaviour increases the trust of the employee on the organisation and employees become committed to the goals of the organisation (Fischer and Hyder, 2020). Davies and Gould-Williams (2005) argued that an organisation improves the employee behaviour using soft or highly committed HRM system to increase the trust of employee on organisation and to empower the employees to improve the performance and mutually interact their needs with the goals of organisation to achieve the required level of employee commitment (Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Perry and Hondeghem, 2008; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Emerson *et al.*, 2020).

The previous studies have indicated a direct link between the demographic variables of employee commitment and employee behaviour (Zajac and Mathieu, 1990; Schmidt, 2009; Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Choi *et al.*, 2020). The personal properties of work experience, education and age also act as mediator to strengthen the relationship between the organisational commitment and employee behaviour (Steers, 1977; García and Vila, 2005; Kattara *et al.*, 2008; Alfes *et al.*, 2013; Chaudhary, 2020). Guest (1987) also recommended that strong work ethics, lower education, job tenure and age correlate the positive relation of organisational commitment and employee behaviour (Bysted, 2013; Choi *et al.*, 2020; Veetikazhi *et al.*, 2021).

2.9.6. Management style and organisational commitment

In the earlier studies, many antecedents of organisational commitment and job satisfaction have been considered by the scholars (Hazer and Williams, 1986; Zajac and Mathieu, 1990; Francesco and Chen, 2000; Wirtz, 2019). For instance, management style (Hazer and Williams, 1986; Saxena, 2019; Yin and Liao, 2020) and culture of organisation (Beyer and Trice, 1993; Chen, 2001; Saeed *et al.*, 2014; Arsto *et al.*, 2019; Alanoglu, 2020) are described to influence both the organisational commitment and job satisfaction (Crawford and Lok, 1999, 2001; Terzi and Kurt, 2005; Beydilli and Kurt, 2020).

The latest research studies have explored those managerial styles may be affected by the culture (Posner and Westwood, 1997; Cavone and Manzini, 2000; Alanoglu, 2020) and affected by the behaviour of the employee in the context of organisational commitment (Francesco and Chen, 2000; Miroshnik, 2002; Hastings *et al.*, 2019).

The variables of management styles and the culture of an organisation are determinants of organisational commitment as proved by the current studies (Cavone and Manzini, 2000; Quang and Vuong, 2002; Anwar and Chaker, 2003; Alanoglu, 2020). The firms from Australia and Hong Kong were selected in which the characteristics of management style were considered and analysed their impact on organisational commitment directly as a positive relationship (Hofstede, 1981, 1991; Phatak, 1986; Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1998; Chen, 2001; Saeed *et al.*, 2014; Yin and Liao, 2020).

2.10. OUTCOMES OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT

The main aspects which are influencing the relationship in between the organisational commitment and the OCB are employee's turnover (Herscovitch and Meyer, 2001; Utami *et al.*, 2021) discrete employee behaviour (Gautam and Wagner, 2001; Rao and Zaidi, 2020) and the formal reward system (Organ, 1988; Hassi, 2019). The job satisfaction is an important moderator of the organisational commitment and OCB (Ryan and Organ, 1995; Zeinabadi, 2010; Romi and Ahman, 2020). The previous research evidence shows that there exists a direct positive relationship between job satisfaction and OCB as described by the author Penner *et al.* (1997) in his research study where he described that the job satisfaction is a vital factor of the OCB (Soelton, 2020). While various authors (Mathieu, 1990; Spector, 2003; Brown, 1996; Muchinsky, 2006) described that the organisational commitment and the OCB are directly related with each other in a positive manner (Karuna, 2021).

2.10.1. Organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour

The relationship in between the employer and employee has been enhanced using the central construct of organisational commitment for many years (Meyer and Allen, 1996; Nwibere, 2014; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). The courses of action and organisation both are bonded together using the constructed definition of the organisational citizenship behaviour which also targets

the organisational commitment (Herscovitch and Meyer, 2001; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). The correlations between the employee turnover and organisational commitment are enhanced as per consistent analysis by Randall (1990). Further relationship in between the organisational commitment and employee behaviour and discretion in employee was concluded by scholars (Herscovitch and Meyer, 2001; Saputra and Riana, 2021) as well as direct relationship was observed in between organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational commitment (Ryan and Organ, 1995; Fischer *et al.*, 2020).

Dimitriades (2007), asserts that organisational citizenship behaviour as individual behaviour which enhance the functioning in the organisation by volunteer employee behaviour without any explicit rewarding (Tsai and Wu, 2010; Kaur and Sharma, 2020; Khaola and Rambe, 2020). Similarly, organisational citizenship behaviour explains a set of volunteer group of behaviours which are not the formal responsibility of an employee; but it helps to enhance their roles in organisation (Engelbrecht and Schlechter, 2006; Mohammad *et al.*, 2011; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). The discretionary employee behaviour is an outcome of the antecedents of organisational commitment (Van Dick *et al.*, 2001; Morales and Pasamar, 2019). The committed employees and characterised volunteer extra role of employee at workplace is resulted due to the organisational citizenship behaviour and is this relation may also be enhanced by the formal reward system of the organisation (Organ, 1988; Nazarian *et al.*, 2020). The relationship between the organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour have been explored in detail by scholars (Meyer and Topolnytsky, 2002; Ahmad and Kaleem, 2020).

2.10.2. Organisational commitment, OCB and job satisfaction

Penner *et al.* (1997) emphasised conclusion on job satisfaction as a factor of job attitudes with the organisational citizenship behaviours which is remarked as “there is little question that the affective and cognitive components of job attitudes are causally related to [organisational citizenship behaviours]” Rawabdeh *et al.* (2019). Ryan and Organ (1995, p. 791) determined that “evidence from the collective body of data supports a modest overall relationship between job satisfaction and various measures of organisational citizenship behaviour”. Ibrahim and Tang (1998) and Hassi, (2019) concluded the relationship in between the organisational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction. Chu *et al.* (2005) and Kaur and Sharma (2020)

studied the effect of job involvement and job satisfaction on the organisational citizenship behaviour and observed a direct relationship in between job satisfaction and organisation citizenship behaviours. Podsakoff *et al.* (2000, p. 532) also reported that “... job attitudes ... including job satisfaction and organisational commitment... appear to be more strongly related to organisational citizenship behaviour] than the other antecedents”.

The job satisfaction and organisational commitment is also positively related as per the research study of the previous literature. Thus, as per the meta-analysis by Zajac and Mathieu (1990) and Spector (2003) referred correlation value in between the organisational commitment and job satisfaction of 0.49 (Dubey *et al.*, 2020). In the same way, meta-analysis done by Brown (1996) and Muchinsky (2006) gives average value of correlation in between organisational commitment and job satisfaction was observed to be 0.53 (Mohammad *et al.*, 2011; Nwibere, 2014; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, these studies approve the favourable relationship between organisational commitment and citizenship behaviour moderated by job satisfaction. Hence, we can develop the following hypothesis:

2.11. OUTCOMES OF ORGANISTIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR

The literature related to OCB, individual and organisational performance of various scholars studying in different working environments of the organisation had revealed that there exists a direct positive relationship in between the individual and organisational performance. The scholars (Organ and Bateman, 1983; Organ, 1988; Diefendorff *et al.*, 2002; Somech and Bolger, 2004; Chu *et al.*, 2005; Moberg and Rotenberry, 2007; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020) had proved a direct positive relationship between the OCB and the individual performance. While the literature review also proved that the OCB and the organisational performance are directly linked with each other in a positive way as per research studies of the various authors such as (Van Dyne *et al.*, 1994; Ehrhart, 2004; Hag and Jahangir, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Febrina and Syamsir, 2020).

2.11.1. Organisational citizenship behaviour and individual performance

The individual job performance is referred to the job involvement of the employee which is the psychological identification of an individual to the organisation (Kanungo, 1982a; Mohammad

et al., 2011; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). Individual performance is also defined as extent to “which one is cognitively preoccupied with, engaged in and concerned with one’s present job” (Paullay *et al.*, 1994, p. 224; Soelton *et al.*, 2020). The high performance of an employee is the measure of self-esteem of an individual of an organisation (Kejner and Lodahl, 1965; Chelagat *et al.*, 2015; Gunay, 2018). Hence due to this, individual those who have high job involvement are generally concerned about duties given to them (Kanungo, 1982b; Hermawan *et al.*, 2020).

Organisational citizenship behaviour is explained as the attitude that “go above and beyond the call of duty.” OCB is described as “individual behaviours that are discretionary, not directly or explicitly recognised by the formal reward system, and that in aggregate promote the effective functioning of an organisation” (Organ, 1988; Ridwan *et al.*, 2020). These attitudes are considered to “lubricate the social machinery of the organisation” (Organ and Bateman, 1983; Tsai and Wu, 2010; Kaur and Sharma, 2020). The scholars (Birnbaum and Somers, 1998; Munene, 1995) analysed a direct relationship between individual performance and OCB and observed high correlation between organisational citizenship behaviour and individual performance. The research also proved the positive relationship between individual performance and OCB (Diefendorff *et al.*, 2002; Somech and Bolger, 2004; Chu *et al.*, 2005; Moberg and Rotenberry, 2007; Febrina and Syamsir, 2020). The perception of individual about duties assigned to them is influenced by the OCB (Ryan and Organ, 1995; Loan, 2020).

2.11.2. Organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational performance

Organ *et al.* (2006) introduced the main theme of organisational citizenship behaviour (Yu and Hua, 2011; Kopp *et al.*, 2020). It was observed by Organ (2006) that organisational citizenship behaviour is an optional activity which is not directly defined in the reward system of an organisation, but it improves the efficiency and effectiveness of the performance of organisation (Appelbaum *et al.*, 2004; Hall *et al.*, 2009; Abror and Patrisia, 2020). The word “optional” meant that OCB is not formally described in the job descriptions of the employees, therefore it is defined to be the optional activity and there will no consequences of non-following such a behaviour by the employees (Podsakoff *et al.*, 2000; Ardi *et al.*, 2020).

The scholars (Emami *et al.*, 2012; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Nazarian *et al.*, 2020) described that organisational citizenship behaviour is a type of employee’s behaviour by virtue of which

employee perform the duties beyond the responsibilities assigned to them. Van Dyne *et al.* (1994) described OCB as the main driving factor of behaviours of employee which causes consolidation between the behaviour of employees and goals of the institute, and thus this realisation of the main goals results in an enhanced performance of the organisation (Hag and Jahangir, 2004; Tsai and Wu, 2010; Morales and Pasamar, 2019). Hence, OCB is a series of admirable and positive organisational behaviour which transmits the multi-dimensional correlations with the performance and consequences of organisation in a positive manner (Maamari *et al.*, 2021) and the core functional behaviour of organisations are enhanced by OCB (Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Fischer and Walker, 2020).

2.12. SUMMARY

In this era, the concept of organisational commitment has been realised important by both researchers and professionals and its impact on organisational citizenship behaviour has been understood to examine the influence on organisational and individual performance. Organisational commitment lies at the centre of human resource management and employee behavioural analysis by many academics. The importance of organisational commitment and its significance for organisational success have been demonstrated in several research studies. Organisational commitment is viewed from two perspectives: attitudinal and behavioural approaches (Meyer and Allen 1991; Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Doan *et al.*, 2020).

This literature review critically analysed different theories related to organisational commitment namely social exchange theory, behavioural theory, and psychological approaches. The *social exchange theory* concerns the individuals' perception of themselves, or 'self-concept,' is influenced by their affiliation with social groups and employees strive to build a positive self-concept and they like to be identified with the organisation. The *behavioural theory* under its behavioural approach centres on "side-bet" and asserts that individuals are committed to the organisation as far as they hold their positions and accumulate better benefits (or incur greater costs at departure), this may dissuade them from seeking alternative employment and the attributional approach focuses on attitudes that result in the attribution of commitment. The *psychological approach* is about employee's intrinsic emotional attachment that reflects itself in the attitudes and association toward the organisation.

This chapter also defines the key concepts and constructs related to organisational commitment. The next chapter is regarding the research's conceptual framework which would be described there, and the hypotheses development would also be explained. Subsequently, the relationship between organisational commitment and its various variables would be explained.

CHAPTER III: METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1. INTRODUCTION

Research design is “the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose with economy in procedure” (Sellitz, Jahoda, Deutsch & Cook., 1965 p.50, quoted in Terre Blanche & Durrheim, 1999 p.29). Planned nature and conscious design of observations differentiates research from other forms of observations. Research design included details of study regarding its type, settings, time horizon and unit of analysis which are discussed below. This chapter will outline the qualitative data collection methods used, describe the analytic techniques employed as well as presenting the findings from this phase of the research study. The findings will be fully discussed with links to current literature identified in Chapter 2.

3.2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researcher collected data from 15 respondents with semi structures interviews. This exploratory qualitative study used one method of data collection which is semi-structured interviews. This was chosen in order to allow university employees to tell their perceptions and experiences in their own words and to uncover areas and ideas that were not anticipated at the beginning of the research (Pope & Mays, 2000).

Paradigms are the interrelated systems of epistemological, ontological, and methodological assumptions (Guba *et al.*, 1998; Rawluk *et al.*, 2019). Paradigm has been classified in various ways, including ontological paradigm, which is the social realities and natural approach, and epistemology is the linkage developed by people between the phenomenon and the researcher (Guba and Lincoln, 1998; Sheth and Parvatiyar, 2002; Rawluk *et al.*, 2019).

The methodology paradigm is the approach or technique which is adopted by scholars to reveal the reality, and it is related to the means or mode of data-collection and validating the evidence, which is empirical (Saunders *et al.*, 2012; Scotland, 2012; Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020). These claims can be referred to as the research methodologies (Lincoln and Guba, 2000; Scotland, 2012; Davies and Fisher, 2018). The social research area has two main epistemological assumptions, interpretivism which is also known as idealism or phenomenology, and positivism (Deshpande, 1983; Cassell and Symon, 1994; Balmer, 2001; Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2002 Corbetta, 2003; Majeed, 2019). The terms naturalistic and scientific were adopted by Guba and Lincoln (1988), whereas positivist and constructivist were embraced by scholars (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998; Majeed, 2019; Abeza and Selvaratnam, 2021).

- Interpretivism aims to develop social life's understanding and investigate how people perceive and construct meanings naturally (Neuman, 2003; Johnston and Green, 2018). Interpretivism is about addressing the process of interaction between people with a consideration that their backgrounds impact their advocacy, to help marginalised people interpretation advocates, to deal with actions, pragmatism helps with various situations, consequences and actions instead of antecedent situations (Creswell, 2003; Premji *et al.*, 2018). Phenomenology observes the world in the form of a qualitative paradigm (Deshpande, 1983; Majeed, 2019), while the interpretive approach is related to developing inductive hypotheses, reviewing phenomena by directly experiencing in a view to understanding the world around (Bryman, 2004; Lanka *et al.*, 2020).
- Positivism is defined as an approach related to natural science and is used widely as one of the oldest approaches. It helps to enhance comprehension by the adoption of different methods such as the scientific deductive method, which is used to conduct quantitative research that is empirical in nature (Creswell, 2003; Premji *et al.*, 2018). The quantitative paradigm is a view of the world that is logically positivist, and both are synonyms (Deshpande, 1983; Majeed, 2019). Moreover, inferential statistics procedures are related to positivist research employed in experimental designs, hypotheses testing, and quasi-experimental

designs. Positivism believes that the reality of society is external, and it needs objective methods to be measured (Creswell, 2003; Premji *et al.*, 2018).

To select the most accurate paradigm that can lead to more valid investigations according to the nature of research objectives, questions and aims must be considered. Deshpande (1983) suggested that management studies mainly adopt inductive approach. The studies related to organisational commitment and OCB has been conducted using a qualitative approach to explore different factors and to understand the perceptions of employees (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Cohen, 1996; Meyer & Allen, 1997; Meyer, Irving & Allen, 1998; Somers & Birnbaum, 1998; Ali, 2018; Ayesha, 2019). Interpretivist should enable the researchers to explore further-depth of individual's experience through formal discussions and interviews. The interpretivist approach aid the exploration of humans' experience would be in-depth by adopting qualitative designs and methodologies (Moustakas, 1994; Pisarik *et al.*, 2017). As a result, based on the given features, the interpretivism paradigm enables the researchers to use qualitative methods for gaining preliminary insights on the perception of employees about organisational commitment and its impact on organisational citizenship behaviour.

So, the quantitative approach should enable the researchers to more generalise and describe a concept more clearly for measuring numbers instead of in-depth wording (Thanh and Thanh, 2015). For that reason, the research's nature and contexts could be influenced to select the most suitable paradigm.

3.3. RESEARCH APPROACH

To understand the research problem as mentioned in the first chapter, a more comprehensive 'pluralisms has been the best fit as the approach in this research (Deshpande, 1983; Mingers, 2001; Pisarik *et al.*, 2017). Mingers (2001) mentioned that "various methods of research (particularly from various paradigms) focusing on various reality aspects, and it helps to develop a deeper comprehension of a research in a single study" (p. 241). The current problem of research has been understood by including many methods into one research. The author (Deshpande, 1983; Mingers, 2001; Pisarik *et al.*, 2017) suggested that the contribution of different methods relevant to the non-positivist approach (such as in-depth qualitative interviews) might be limit the authors' understanding when they adopt a positivist approach.

In the research, the examination of qualitative data was done by employing a content analysis technique. Bryman (2006) recognised two approaches for amalgamating qualitative and quantitative research founded on content analysis. The first approach was developed by Greene *et al.* (1989) in the research assessment context.

This research applied qualitative approaches, including in-depth interviews with academic (teaching faculty) and administrative staff of the universities. The qualitative methodology was principally used due to a limited comprehension of the concept ‘organisation commitment’, requiring a more in-depth definition.

3.3.1. Research strategy

3.3.1.1. Semi-structured interviews

One-to-one interviews were chosen in preference to focus group interviews to maximise participation as university staff have a very busy and different schedule so it can be very difficult to bring groups of employees together. Semi structured interviews are defined as an interview within which the interviewer asks key questions and probes for further information (Arthur & Nazroo, 2003). Compared with unstructured interviews semi-structured interviews provided a more structured approach to interviewing to ensure the coverage of topics whilst allowing the employees the use of their own words in order to explore and discover their experience and perceptions (French, 1993). The semi-structured interviews involved a number of broad questions around specific topic area giving me the opportunity to probe and clarify responses whilst encouraging each participant to take the lead and shape their own narrative (Rubin & Rubin, 1995).

Qualitative research is related to a process and meaning, and it may not be examinable by quantities or amounts. Qualitative research aims to provide specific understandings for the phenomenon based upon one’s experience with a lesser number of generalisations. However, qualitative research has aimed to attain understanding deeply for the specific cases within the relevant topic in the exploratory type of the research (Biggam, 2008; Creswell, 2002; Easterby, 2008; Tran *et al.*, 2018).

3.3.2. Time Horizons

The cross-section research data implies observing the variables available from many years, quarters, months, or many days. This refers to time frames of research, and generally, observation may have two faces based on the time horizon, named cross-section and longitude. The longitudinal data are used when the observation is for the single point of the time like many surveys and longitude time horizons select the data from the multi-points of the research. Here in this research work, the cross-section time horizon is selected.

3.3.3. Type of Study

The research study under consideration is the rational study by which the effect of the organisational commitment on the organisational citizenship behaviour is measured in lieu of the individual and organisational performance in the context of the university setting operating in Pakistan. The constructs of this research study are measured based on the self-reporting perceptions of the interview respondents of various educational institutes operating in Pakistan.

3.3.4. Study Settings

The field of study is based on the participants, who are the university administration and the teachers who will be contacted as per the jobs they are doing in the universities, and qualitative interviews will be taken from them. The research questionnaire for the qualitative study is finalised based on the interviews conducted from the university faculty and administration working in the various universities of Pakistan. The variables considered are not controlled or manipulated, while no other artificial setting was created to study them.

3.3.5. Unit of analysis

The main unit for analyses in the research study is the individuals (university faculty and administrative members working in Pakistan) because research ascertains an individual's attitude (the organisational commitment) and the behaviour (the organisational citizenship behaviour) with references to the performances (individual and organisational performance) and the organisational factors (such as organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate, employee behaviour, management style, organisational corporate social responsibility and job satisfaction) as the variables.

3.4. QUALITATIVE FIELDWORK

The resources of information such as discussions and interviews (Ritchie *et al.*, 2003; Palmerr and Gallagherr, 2007; Kalu and Bwalya, 2017) are valuable to get perspectives on the information gathered during the research study (Ritchie *et al.*, 2003; Kalu and Bwalya, 2017). The data collected from the interviews provides the information for understating the relationships of different research constructs. In exploratory research, the wide range of samples is not considered. Therefore, in-depth interviews are used to examine the relationship of the undertaken variables (Malhotra and Birks, 2000; Abdullah and Kamaruddin, 2019). However, to enhance the quality of this research, it is important to use the qualitative method of research by formulating a questionnaire (Churchill, 1979; Wang *et al.*, 2018).

Churchill (1979) recommends that an exploration study is based on a sample of people who can give insights into different ideas and phenomena, and it is also called an 'experience survey'. The exploratory study starts with a range of knowledge to develop a particular study having its own objectives (Saunders *et al.*, 2007; Mak and Ip, 2017). The scholars (Churchill, 1979) recommended using the technique of creating items of its selected sample and then representing the constructs. Therefore, this study adapts the technique to measure organisational commitment by conducting interviews.

3.4.1 Recruitment of candidates for interviews

Due to the outbreak of COVID-19, an online process is initiated to recruit the participants for qualitative interviews to ensure social distancing. The personal contacts have also been used to recruit participants in interviews. A form is developed in the recruitment process to get the profile of the respondents (see Appendix-I). This is sent to the participants through an online advertisement to various universities. The appropriate candidates are short listed based on their job role, education, experience, and relevant knowledge. The demography table below shows the information collected from the respondents in Table 4.6.

Table 3. 1: Demographic profile for candidates participated in the process of recruitment

Main constructs	Sub-constructs	Numbers
Gender	Male	38
	Female	37
Type of university	Government university	47
	Private university	28
Qualification	Below bachelor	8
	Master or sixteen years of education	49
	PhD or post PhD	26
Experience	5 to 10 years	28
	5 years or less	34
	Greater than 10 years	12

Source: The researcher

3.4.2. Overviews of the planning, management and data interpretation of the qualitative stage

There are various qualitative data analysis approaches that have been discussed widely by different authors (Silverman, 1993; Bryman and Burgess, 1994; Bazeley, 2007; Bonello & Meehan, 2019). The concept of open code interpretations is adapted. The data is categorised based on the constructs of research. The open coding starts with the review of the text (transcript of the interview) and highlights the data where the constructs of research such as organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour, individual and organisational performance are present. The interviews' transcript is studied deeply to examine the pattern of the text in correspondence to literature.

The statements are compared with each other to determine the coddle relationship in between the parameters of research. The similar codes are separated out and labelled as per the research construct. The purpose of the coding pattern is to examine the texts with similar or dissimilar coding groups. Moreover, the researcher identified that start codes to address the research questions, s and key variables that the researcher brings (Miles and Huberman, 1994, p. 58; Palmer and Gallagher, 2007; Hellwege *et al.*, 2017). The research questions were empirically tested through a rigorous methodology (Guba, 1990; Sheth and Parvatiyar, 2002; Kelly *et al.*, 2018). The open coding of the transcript of the interview as determined by the scholars with memos and comments analysis process is deliberated, which result in the development of the axial codes.

The data of the axial coding is analysed in the subsequent stage of the research study. The relationships in between the constructs are tried to set up with the help of axial coding. The sub-categories and core categories are also identified within the text of the qualitative data. The scholar (Balmer, 1996) described the systematic type of axial code. The data analysis is not misleading by using the method of axial coding. The open codes are taken into account of axial loading. The comparison of constants is the base of the axial coding process. The axial codes are generated based on the similarities and differences (Strauss and Corbin, 1998; Charmaz and Thornberg, 2020). The axial code is generated after a comparison of the open coding with each category of coding. The process of axial coding also allows the scholar to generate a code of the required category (Spiggle, 1994; Bianchi *et al.*, 2020). The existing codes may also be upgraded as per the requirements of research, and the coding can be merged with each other.

For analysing the data, it may be utilised in the main framework of the qualitative interpretative analysis (Merriam, 2002; Stewart, 2019). This qualitative interpretation technique is related to the narrations and statements of the participants who recorded by using digital online audio recording tools such as Skype. Each interview may be replayed, and the voice recordings may be transcribed (i.e., to convert into text). The interviewers may be selected as per the respective objects of research, and for this purpose, the university faculty and staff members shall be requested to participate in the qualitative study. Then after transcription, the transcribed interview may be compared as well. In the end, the interview themes as per the hypotheses shall be themed in terms of the research questions as per the theme strategy of the scholars Ivernois and Gagnayre (1995). The narrative statements shall be used in organising the specific

relationships between the different variables of the research study. The investigator shall get the interviews unless and until saturation may be achieved, which means that the interviews may be conducted till subsequent interviewees shall not produce new types of information. The consolidating criterion to report the qualitative study is followed (Tong *et al.*, 2007).

The codes may also be generated in multiple stages for the purpose of checking the reliability of the data (Weber, 1985). The technique of content analysis is also very useful for the purpose of valid reference and removal of replicable data. The scholar (Patton, 2001) describes in this context, “the qualitative analyst’s effort at uncovering patterns, themes, and categories is a creative process that requires making carefully considered judgements about what is really significant and meaningful in the data” (p. 406).

The quality of data is necessary for the social investigation using the methodological and philosophical methods for studying activities of human beings (Ritchie *et al.*, 2003). The research study is judged through the factors of reliability and validity. The reliability is considered the “trust worth” of the data. The determination of validities and reliabilities is the main construct of the trustworthiness of data (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). It is stated by Seal (1999) that, “trustworthiness of a research report lies at the heart of issues conventionally discussed as validity and reliability” (p. 266). Instead of considering the statistical random sample, it is focused to select the theoretical sample because it “maximise opportunities for comparing concepts along with their properties for the similarities and differences enabling researchers to define categories to differentiate among them and to specify their range of variability” (Strauss and Corbin, 1998, p. 149).

It is also stated by Lincoln and Guba (1985), “there is no validity without reliability, an expression of the former validity is sufficient to establish the latter reliability” (p. 316). While reliability is referred to the sustainability of data, and validity is referred to the strengths of the data. The reliability determines how exact the methods and techniques of production of data in consequences with the validity of the research (Patton, 2001; Arora, 2020). It is important to determine the reliability and validity of the research study to quantify how the perception of the qualitative survey is affected by the quantitative data and to determine the respondent biases, and increase the truthfulness of the research study. The qualitative research work is based on the triangulation approach. Creswell and Miller (2000) expressed the triangulations by “a validity procedure where researchers search for convergence among multiple and

different sources of information to form themes or categories in a study” (p. 126). The method of triangulations improves the reliability and validity of the research study, and it also evaluates the research observations. As a result, triangulation, validity and reliability are related notions of research study, and it is essential from standpoints of qualitative work, which reflect various approaches of establishing truths (Welsh, 2002). Table 4.8 represents the techniques used in the research study to enhance trustworthiness.

The coding technique of content analyses is used to verify reliabilities of the research questionnaire, while the stabilities were also ascertained by scholars when contents were coded at more than one point (Weber, 1985; Kalemci and Tuzun, 2019). Moreover, the assessment of the reliabilities of the emerging types of corporate identity, the independent coders with necessary qualitative experiences of research is required that was not familiar with the employed study.

Table 3. 2: Meeting the criteria of trustworthiness

		Axial codes and exemplar open presenting separately Interviews are transcribed word by word The interview contacts and records are accurately kept Journal research writing
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Source: Based on Lincoln and Guba (1985)

3.4.3. Interviews

In this research, to meet the objectives and to operationalise the main elements that are necessary for a deeper understanding of organisational commitment. In-depth interviews have been conducted with university staff. Online advertisement has helped to recruit seventy to eighty participants who filled the forms to show their interest to take part in the research interviews. The researcher selected fifteen participants based on their education, experience, and background knowledge. Five participants have been taken through reference, and they also have the relevant profile. The research data has been aimed at collecting attitudinal and behavioural data (Yin, 1984; Palmer and Gallagher, 2007; Shiu *et al.*, 2009).

The interviews have been conducted online using Skype or Google Meet applications to develop a clear overview of organisational commitment and achieve the research objectives.

The interviews took place through the medium adopted by the participants (Ritchie *et al.*, 2003). The time and medium were opted by the interview. Each interview took on an average fifty to sixty minutes, which had been recorded and transcribed as it is to ensure its reliability (Andriopoulos and Lewis, 2009).

The in-depth interviews helped to discover the personal motivation, experience, and attitude of the interviewees towards the topic. The interview protocol has been designed to ensure all the areas have been covered during the interviews (see Appendix 4.1) A professional dress code has been adopted by the researcher (Easterby-Smith *et al.*, 2002; Robinson *et al.*, 2021). Different approaches for developing the trust and confidence of the interviewees have been adopted, such as ensuring data protection and confidentiality. It is important to conduct in-depth interviews to uncover new dimensions of any phenomenon based on personal opinions and practical experiences (Burgess, 1982; Allan, 2020). Personal interviews are extensively useful in behavioural studies as it serves as a direct method to seek any clarifications (Sekaran, 2003).

The non-quantified data such as opinions, perception and attitude are the basis for qualitative study. The approach of individuals towards anything or any phenomenon is attitude. It is used to understand people's reactions (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; Albloushy and Hiller, 2019). Moreover, attitude is also a way to measure the organisational commitment and its impact on other factors (Weston *et al.*, 2001; Husaeni, 2018). A direct questioning method is instrumental for more reliable responses (Malhotra and Birks, 2000; Abdullah and Kamaruddin, 2019). Meyer (2002) suggested that management scholars can pay more attention to exploratory research through interviews (Churchill, 1979; Melewar, 2001; Wang *et al.*, 2018). The qualitative approach is adopted by management scholars for in-depth exploration of issues in a comparatively less structured way to accumulate the experiences, beliefs, and feelings of the research respondents (Malhotra and Birks, 2000; Abdullah and Kamaruddin, 2019). The qualitative research aims to collect more information for an in-depth comprehension of organisational commitment. The details of the research interviewees have been shown in Table 3.7 (Appendix 3.1 for the protocol of interview).

Table 3. 3: The details of in-depth interviews

University employees, including academic and non-academic staff

Interview Date	Interview position	Organisation	Interview approx. duration
12.7.2021	Professor	University of the Punjab	130 min
15.7.2021	Lecturer	University of the Punjab	45 min
18.7.2021	Lecturer	University of Information and Technology	60 min
22.7.2021	Student Affairs officer	Beacon house University Lahore	90 min
5.8.2021	Human Resource Manager	University of Management Sciences Lahore	60 min
7.8.2021	Professor	Gomal University DIK	40 min
12.8.2021	Lecturer	Comsat University Abbottabad	60 min
5.9.2021	Lecturer	University of Sahiwal	90 min
15.9.2021	Assistant Professor	University of Sargodha	40 min
16.7.2021	Administrator	Government University Faisalabad	60 min
21.7.2021	Human Resource Manager	University of Information and Technology	80 min
25.7.2021	Assistant Lecturer	University of Central Punjab	45 min
16.7.2021	Public Relations Manager	University of Management Sciences Lahore	90 min
21.7.2021	Lecturer	Comsat University Abbottabad	60 min
25.7.2021	Lecturer	University of Gujrat	50 min
Topics discussed			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The understanding of organisational commitment. - The factors that influence organisational citizenship behaviour. - The experience of the employees of what they perceive about organisational commitment 			

Source: The researcher

3.4.4. Population and sample

3.4.4.1. Sampling Methods

Sampling procedures include a variety of procedures that allow the researcher to collect information from a sub-group rather than the whole population (Saunders et al., 2009; Bhattacharjee, 2012). While doing the study, it is vital to acquire primary data to supplement the secondary data; however, since the researcher cannot gather data from the whole population, a sample must be chosen (Wilson, 2010; Saunders et al., 2012). However, Pitney and Parker (2009) noted that, though qualitative research employs a small number of participants, sample size is still critical for answering the research question, since sample size helps the researcher to pick people who can provide the information necessary to answer the issue. Blaxter et al. (2006) classify sampling strategies into two categories, which are summarised in Table 3. Table 3: Sampling methods Source: Blaxter et al. (2006). The probability and non-probability sampling are included in research sampling section (Orcher,

2016; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Probability sampling is acceptable when the sample is drawn at random and when all known prospective samples within the studied population can be identified (Orcher, 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Non-probability sampling relies on personal opinion, reduces randomly sampled selection, and often imposes constraints on the sample population's structure and shape (Orcher, 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Generalisation of study findings has been predominantly related with probability sampling, since the selections are deemed typical of the population (Sarstedt et al., 2016). Transferability refers to the extent to which research results from one area may be applied to other situations (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Research approach is often limited to certain businesses and is often generally applicable only to comparable conditions and settings (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Despite the tradition of generalising research via the use of probability sampling, the literature indicates that research employing non-probability sampling may be generalisable via replication studies (Sarstedt et al., 2016; Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Sarstedt et al. (2016) discussed the value of replication studies in enhancing the validity and generalisability of research using non-probability sampling in the advertising industry. Replication recommendations may be made as proposals for additional investigation by scholarly researchers (Sarstedt et al., 2016), and were included in this research as a suggestion.

On the one hand, random sampling, cluster sampling, and stratified sampling are all probability sampling procedures (Creswell and Poth, 2017; Sarstedt et al., 2016). When all segments of the community have an equal probability of being picked for the sample population, random sampling is used (Creswell and Poth, 2017; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Cluster sampling is categorising the individuals into pre-set groups called classes based on their features and the study variables (Orcher, 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Simple random entails segmenting the population according to several characteristics, such as age and gender (Orcher, 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2016). While data collection and sampling methods are distinct, they have a similar characteristic in their use of random sample components (Orcher, 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Individual strata and stratified sampling are used to pick random selection, while random patches within cluster sampling are used to pick random clusters (Banerjee and Chaudhury, 2010; Orcher, 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Probability sampling techniques could not be applied in this research. As noted above, probability sampling techniques need the use of random sampling (Palinkas et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Random sampling was not applicable for this study since the research question indicated that a particular type of persons should be sampled (Palinkas et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Individuals who have been involved in

succession planning inside the investigated hospitality and tourism industry fall under this group.

Probability sampling would allow for the inclusion of persons who had not been involved in this industry planning within the sector under study. This potential may result in the inclusion of persons who are not qualified in the sample population. As such, the sampling technique would not provide an answer to the study question. On the other hand, convenience sampling, quota sampling, and purposeful sampling are all examples of non-probability sampling procedures (Creswell and Poth, 2017; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Convenience sampling is often related with the ease with which research subjects may be recruited and accessed (Palinkas et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2016). The researcher selects representative samples depending on ease of access to prospective members (Palinkas et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2016). To answer the research question and to accomplish the study's objective, data had to be gathered from persons who have encountered the examined phenomena. Because the researcher could not pick research participants merely on the basis of chance and availability, this sampling technique was not used in this study (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

Quota sampling comprises the construction and administration of pre-set feature controls within the population being studied (Palinkas et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Controls for quota sampling are often created based on the researcher's judgement (Palinkas et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Due to the fact that particular proportions would not have permitted for the exclusive identification of persons who encountered the investigated occurrence, quota sampling was not used in this study.

Purposeful sampling entails choosing sample participants who are competent to contribute to the resolution of the research issue and the completion of the study (Creswell and Poth, 2017; Palinkas et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2016). The researchers construct criteria that aid in identifying individuals of the sample population who are suitable (Creswell and Poth, 2017; Sarstedt et al., 2016). Non-probability sampling techniques are often used in qualitative research and are acceptable for this investigation (Bryman and Bell, 2015). As the research aims to explore and analyse the phenomenon of micro businesses concerning their characteristics and the practices and opinions of their owners, the researcher chose purposive sampling as a method of sampling.

The population of the study is university teachers from Pakistan. As the researcher belongs to Pakistan and is primarily interested in studying organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour in Pakistani university teachers that is why Pakistan has been taken as a developing country. The reason for the ease of data collection is the personal contacts of the researcher with the university employees. Following table shows the existing literature sampling size and choice of methodology.

Table 3. 4: Qualitative study and sampling

Authors	Research Topic	Year	Methodology	Sample size (Interviews)	Sources of secondary research
A. Arian	OCB-Organisational identification	2014	Qualitative	15 Managerial interviews	Academy of Management Journal
Marielle Payaud	Organisational structure and organisational commitment	2015	Qualitative	20 Managerial Interviews	Journal of Ethics
Caroll	Management style and organisational commitment	2016	Qualitative	16 Managerial Interviews	Academy of Management Review
Kim and Yang	Employee commitment	2017	Mixed method approach	240 employee surveys -15 interviews	Journal of organisational behaviour
Turner & Mayer	Relationship satisfaction b/w and organisational commitment	2018	Qualitative method	18 managerial interviews	Public relations review
Warren & Roess	A conceptual framework of the components of commitment	2019	Qualitative method	15 managerial interviews	Journal of business Ethics

Wegner & May	Organisational commitment-An impact-based perspective, initiative, characteristics, and employee engagement.	2021	Qualitative method	15 managerial interviews	Strategic Management Journal
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Source: Researcher

There are 133 universities in Pakistan out of which 73 are public sector universities and 60 are private sector universities. All 133 universities make up the population of the study in Pakistan. These universities are geographically dispersed throughout the country in its seven political regions which are Azad Jammu Kashmir, Baluchistan, Federal Capital Islamabad, Gilgit-Baltistan, Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa, Punjab and Sindh. A mix of public and private sector universities has been selected from the before mentioned regions to collect data. Based on the previous studies (Mowday, Steers, and Porter, 1982; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020) fifteen respondents were selected for interviews.

3.4.5. Pilot testing

Pilot testing is a pre-interview practice that happens with persons who have the same qualities and characteristics as those for whom the interview is prepared. Pilot testing enables the identification of issues with established questions, such as their language, comprehension, and time commitment, as well as questions pertinent to the subject (Waltz, 2010). According to Saunders et al. (2009), a pilot test helps the researcher to modify the questions in order to make them simpler to answer for the responder. Nevertheless, Tylor et al. (2006) made an important point in their analysis that the pilot test should be conducted under identical circumstances to the main interview since it allows both the interviewee and the researcher to gain feedback from each interviewee. Consequently, the researcher ran a pilot study with some of her work colleagues and acquaintances, and based on their input, some terms were changed and certain questions were eliminated to make the inquiry more understandable.

3.4.6. Validity and reliability

Wood and Boss-Kerr (2011) recognised that reliability and validity in research are terms that relate to the measurement of data that will be used to answer the research question; the data obtained may be valuable only if it is measured using a suitable instrument. According to Klenke (2008), the purpose of validity in qualitative research is to ascertain the extent to which the researcher's knowledge corresponds to reality. From the other perspective, the term "reliability" may be substituted by the terms "credibility", "trustworthiness", "consistency" and "dependability" (Cohen et al., 2007). Validity is critical because it demonstrates to the researcher that the selected measure will accurately assess the intended outcome and not something else. Similar to quantitative research, dependability is critical in qualitative research since it establishes the researcher's trust in the measurements used (Goodwin, 2010). With reference to this research, the researcher verifies the validity and reliability of the data obtained using an interview-based qualitative technique. The researcher performed all online interviews and then analysed the data to determine whether or not this methodology is dependable for answering the study question. To enhance the validity and quality of the findings, the researcher used Lucy Yardley's (2000) validity standards, as suggested by other researchers (Heffron and Gil, 2011; Smith et al., 2009). Yardley's work outlines a comprehensive set of quality standards that may be used to a range of qualitative research, including those conducted under the IPA (Smith et al., 2009). Yardley (2000) noted that four criteria for evaluating the qualities of qualitative work: sensitive environment, dedication and consistency, transparency and coherence, and effectiveness and significance, emphasising that these criteria are adaptable in implementation but should align with qualitative approaches. Yardley's (2000) standards are utilised to verify that the study is trustworthy, both in terms of procedure and assessment, and that the findings accurately reflected the perceptions of employees.

3.5. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The researchers have considered the ethics behind the research intervention. The guidelines have been prescribed by University of the West of Scotland. It is important to understand the effects of the research on the stakeholders and participants. There are many concerns shared by social researchers and businesses (Jowell, 1986; Torres *et al.*, 2021).

The research has been conducted in an appropriate manner following the code of conduct relevant to the subject. The four basic considerations are isolated in this study. Firstly, the subject rights are considered, which is about protecting the rights of the investigation and social groups, which helps to avoid any interruption and to ensure the privacy of these groups. Secondly, it is needed to mention the research question objectively as per the ethical conduct of the research. Thirdly, it is essential to be aware of cultural and social differences. Fourthly, the participants increase their trust and confidence in the research methodologies and their reliability. The personal details taken during the interviews are kept confidential, as mentioned in the covering letter of the interview protocol (see Appendix 4.3).

3.6. CONFIDENTIALITY

It is very important to protect the identity of the person from whom the researcher is gathering information (Bhattacharjee, 2012; Brikci and Green, 2007). According to Mack *et al.* (2005), qualitative research is conversational, and it gathers a lot of personal information from participants. Therefore, they may expect similar information in return. The researcher needs to ensure that no information will be shared among the participants, as it could damage their confidentiality. One of the most important points the researcher must remember is not to make any incidental comments about other interviewed participants (Mack *et al.*, 2005). Moreover, the researcher needs to ensure that no personal information will be disclosed in a public forum, report or paper (Bhattacharjee, 2012). Researchers also need to obtain formal ethical approval before starting to collect data (Brikci and Green, 2007). Thus, with regard to the present study, the researcher ensured that the formal ethical review had been confirmed before collecting data for the research. The researcher submitted an ethical approval application form to the University of the West of the Scotland before collecting data and the university ethics committee accepted and approved the application.

The sessions are recorded if agreed by the respondents. The approval has been granted by the University of the West of Scotland based on the above considerations.

CHAPTER IV QUALITATIVE STUDY FINDINGS

4.1. INTRODUCTION

The previous chapter described the significance of the methodology adopted to conduct this research study. The current chapter is related to the qualitative findings, which are based on the unstructured approach of enquiring that is encouraging the interviewees for selecting their interpretations: it is also enabling the provision of higher possible insights (the present section represents the results from the interviewees that have been conducted from various faculty members of different universities, in term of focusing the research study objectives.

This chapter, which is a crucial part of the thesis, discusses the research's findings on the impact of organisational commitment constituents on employees' perceptions of organisational commitment, despite the fact that many employees see organisational commitment as an important part of developing organisational citizenship behaviour. In other words, this chapter tells the story that emerges from the data, thus it is critical to present them in a way that is compelling and appropriate to the following research questions.

RQ-1: What are the factors that are impacting the organisational commitment among employees in university settings in Pakistan?

RQ-2: How organisational commitment impacts organisational citizenship behaviour in the organisations?

RQ-3: How organisational citizenship behaviour impacts organisational performance?

RQ-4: What are the steps that can be taken by the management to enhance employee perceptions regarding organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour?

Thus far, part of the first query has been addressed in Chapter 2's literature review. As a consequence, this chapter presents the findings of the interview data analysis in order to respond to the study's research questions. In addition, quotes were picked based on frequency to highlight the variety and applicability of the data. The interview transcripts were lightly edited in order to eliminate word repetition and hesitations. In order to ensure that the original context and notions are still reflected in the interpreted data, significant emphasis was given to maintaining the precise language. In-depth, open-ended interviews with 15 different members

of staff from various universities in Pakistan were used to gather this data. Therefore, the next table shows the background of the interviewees.

Table 4. 1: The participant’s characteristics

Participants	Age	Years of Experience	Profession	University	City
P01	40	15	Prof	Comset university lahore	Lahore
P02	41	14	Senior lec	PU	Lahore
P03	50	20	Prof	QU	Isl
P04	40	10	Manager	RU	Isl
P05	45	15	lec	PU	Lahore
P06	50	20	Senior admin	BU	Karachi
P07	35	5	Senior Lec	SU	Sargodha
P08	60	35	Senior Prof	SU	Sahiwal
P09	40	12	Academic manager	KU	Peshawar
P10	37	7	Lecturer	LU	Lahore
P11	34	5	Manager	GC	Lahore
P12	30	2	Lecturer	GU	DIG
P13	36	4	Senior lecturer	UCP	Lahore
P14	42	9	Senior admin	BU	Isl
P15	32	3	Lecturer	Pes U	Peshawar

Source: Researcher

4.2. SYNTHESISING THE FINDINGS

This section addresses the respondents' primary concerns. This exemplifies the overarching tendencies revealed by the interviews. Saldaña (2013) noted that there is no one technique to report qualitative findings. As a result, this part synthesises the findings in order to tell the story. To highlight the diversity and relevance of the data, direct quotations were carefully picked based on frequency, significance, and distinctiveness.

In contrast, the findings illustrate the developing themes of how the fundamental organising phenomenon and essential categories evolved. Additionally, the analysis of data is standard: detected patterns in data were tagged (Concepts), then emergent concepts were divided into

Table 4. 2: Summary of the emerged themes

1- What are the factors that are impacting the organisational commitment among employees in university settings in Pakistan?			
Themes	Frequency	Meaning	Evidence
Communication	17	Although communication with co-workers makes employees feel committed to their company, communication from upper management has a stronger correlation with commitment.	“Hence, the effectiveness of communicating back to the employees is very slow and this is a major barrier affecting the employee's interest in the organisation's affairs. It also leads to boredom and creates a culture of disengaged employees with a poor attitude towards the organisation.”
Psychological Needs	16	Psychological condition that defines the employee's relationship with the company and has an impact on the choice of whether to remain a member or leave the company.	“Yes, I feel the psychological need of the employees are fulfilled when the climate of the organisation is positive and there is what's a diff culture and teamwork within the organisation.”
Learning Opportunities	15	Employees that participated in the learning programmes demonstrated more organisational commitment and work satisfaction than other employees.	“I attend regular seminars and conferences. I got training for my job role which was outsourced to another training provider. I learned effective teaching practices through this training. I think there should be more updated training. I get regular opportunities for my CPD and it improves me as a person and as an employee. I am grateful for these learning opportunities.”
Motivated to progress within their organisation	11	The most significant factor affecting your level of motivation at work is typically the business environment. A positive, encouraging environment that puts you "in the zone" where you need to be to succeed makes you thrive.	“A culture of care and motivation and appreciation will have a huge impact on employees' performance and commitments when the employees feel they are part of the overall achievements then they will feel is their responsibility to do their best and become motivated and this will increase their performance.”
Strive to be an integral part of the organisation	3	Company's success depends on effective communication. According to survey after study, employees frequently criticise their organisation for inadequate communication.	“In meeting agendas, we do get the information regarding the core values. I think these core values, mission, and vision need to be discussed in an induction session and there should be refresher training on it.”
Think creatively	1	Businesses may use creativity to promote more friendly and collaborative work environments or to come up with novel solutions. Creativity encourages employee	“Then there is freedom in the working atmosphere to try new ideas the employees feel worth staying committed to the company.”

		experimentation and thinking beyond the box.	
2- How organisational commitment impacts organisational citizenship behaviour in the organisations?			
Theme	Frequency	Meaning	Evidence
Employee satisfaction	43	Employee satisfaction measures how comfortable or happy workers are with their positions and working conditions.	“Job satisfaction is like a bridge between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour. If an employee is not satisfied it is hard to be committed. There will be always this idea of leaving the organisation. Sometimes the risk of losing the job and the risk of not finding the desired job can be a factor to stay. So only satisfied employees show OCB which is a psychological attachment to the organisation.”
Management Style	29	Management style has an impact on KPIs, decision-making speed, employee morale, and productivity. Successful leaders do a comprehensive analysis of the problem, evaluate the skill levels of their subordinates, weigh their options, and reach an informed conclusion.	“A management style is the particular way managers go about accomplishing these objectives. It encompasses the way they make decisions, how they plan and organize work, and how they exercise authority. Management styles vary by company, level of management, and even from person to person.”
Organisational structure	27	Organisational structures assist companies in ensuring that all duties required for efficient operations are delegated to the appropriate individuals. Additionally, they assist managers and workers in understanding their responsibilities within the company, including who they report to and who they oversee.	“So, an effective structure can impact the attitude and behaviours of employees positively as a manager can act as a role model to show the desired attitudes and behaviours.”
Organisational Culture	26	Organisational culture has an influence on all aspects of your business, from contract terms and employee incentives to punctuality and tone. When your workplace culture fits their tastes, your employees are more likely to feel at ease, supported, and respected.	“I think for the success of an organisation, culture is the utmost important factor. A more supportive culture, less power distanced, more innovative and more productive brings more work satisfaction and commitment to the work.”
Improves the Behaviour of Employees	17	Employees should behave properly at work in order to sustain a positive workplace culture as well as earn the respect and admiration of their co-workers.	“The culture or climate of the organisation motivates the employees similarly if the organisation does not recognise the effort of employees, then it can demotivate them. Thus, if there is a positive culture in the organisation then it can create commitment among employees.”
Perform the Tasks in The Organisation Beyond Formal Responsibilities	15	Directing the behaviour of others; and by exceeding expectations, they show that they value it when a team member	“I think I do not limit myself to the usual responsibilities. I go the extra mile and take initiative to contribute to helping my

		takes the initiative and goes above and beyond a goal.	colleagues. I train the newcomers, I support the students additionally for their employability skills, career counselling, and personal development.”
Committed to The Organisation	13	Work commitment, usually referred to as dedication to one's job, is the enthusiasm with which a person accepts the obligations assigned to him or her at work. It refers to a person's sense of obligation to uphold the goals, objectives, and mission of the organisation to which they are connected.	“I am loyal to the organisation. I feel emotionally attached to the organisation and my students. I am not in a position to quit the job as I am not going to get the same level of satisfaction, trust, and respect. I have invested time to earn this status which has ultimately made me committed to the organisation.”
Well-Being of Employees	11	Employee well-being expenditure may result in higher performance and productivity, better engagement, fewer sick days, and increased resilience. However, because wellness programmes are isolated from daily operations, they frequently fall short of their promise.	“If I overall feel good I would love to go to work every day. I would be able to keep a work-life balance, a happy mood and satisfaction, and an overall good mental state”
Organisational Climate	10	Employees' perceptions of how the workplace impacts them personally are reflected in the organisational environment.	“Organisational climate is important as it is the perception of the employee of the work environment. A positive climate encourages employees' productivity, and motivation and decreases turnover.”
Participate in Meetings and Discussions	7	Meetings provide you and your team members the chance to connect, share information, resolve issues or disagreements, improve performance, promote collaboration, and move initiatives forward.	“For my particular institution, all the employees are not fully free to take decisions, but they are involved through departmental meetings. The decisions are finally to be approved by the board of directors or vice-chancellors”
Employee Engagement	3	Evaluate and manage your employees' opinions on important areas of your workplace culture by encouraging employee involvement.	“The managers highly emphasise employees' and subordinates' involvement and participation, particularly in key decision-making. That is offering an employee voice on the matters concerning the organisation, and as such employees feel valued and are more committed.”
3- How organisational citizenship behaviour impacts organisational performance?			
Theme	Frequency	Meaning	Evidence
The Additional Activities You Perform Contribute to Your Performance	15	A successful self-evaluation should focus on certain tasks and endeavours that highlight your best work. To prove their value to the company, employees should emphasise the impact such victories have on the whole organisation while describing them.	“My performance depends on the key job roles which I am expected to do as per my job description. The extra activities are not part of my job but my colleagues and students get benefited from them.”
The Employees Performing Volunteer	15	Employees are more likely to show a better level of passion and connection	“Yes, the volunteer activities also contribute towards the

Activities for The Organisation Help to Improve Organisational Performance		to their employment and stay for a longer amount of time if they engage in volunteer activities at work.	achievement of the goals. The employees who perform additional activities feel highly motivated and involved in the organisation emotionally as well so it adds value to the organisation.”
Employee Productivity	3	A number of variables, including as engagement, effective people management techniques, the work environment, the right tools, and the use of technology as a competitive advantage, can have an impact on productivity.	“High levels of organisational commitments are related to superior business performance, increased profitability, improved productivity, employee retention, customer satisfaction metrics, reduced customer churn, and above all improving the workplace culture.”
Improved Organisational Performance	3	Organisational improvement should be considered by businesses that want to improve their risk management and the quality of their goods and services.	“The employees do beyond their duties because of their commitment. They will be aimed at achieving organisational goals. If the employees are treated fairly by providing them equal opportunities for growth and development, they tend to be committed and have OCB.”
Increase an Employee’s Chances of Staying with That Organisation for A Longer Period	3	As a sign of your confidence in them, give your team responsibilities that will help them develop. Encourage them to pick up new skills. Give students a choice of continuing education opportunities. Hire internally whenever possible and provide big promotions when it makes sense.	“Yes, when the employee feels committed to the organisation they always try beyond their duties because they show gratitude towards their employer”
Lower Absenteeism	1	Absenteeism occurs when an employee repeatedly skips work. This excludes instances when a corporation has granted an employee time off or paid leave.	“Employees could engage in this type of organisational citizenship behaviour by speaking favourably about the organisation to those outside of it, participating in charity projects the company participates in, and planning or attending company-sanctioned social events.”

Source: Researcher

4.2.1. Organisational commitment (focal construct)

It is evident from the previous research studies that organisational commitment is conceptualised in terms of a multi-dimensional research construct. The findings of different qualitative research studies (i.e., interviews) provided immediate insight into current research problems. These have also been used to establish a reasonable scale for measuring organisational commitment.

Following is the significant quotation received from the interviewee related to the relationship between the organisational commitment and the organisational structure, which is also confirming the qualitative results where the extent of organisational structure is observed to be improving the attitude and behaviour of employees for organisational commitment. The example shows:

“[The] Structure improves organisational commitment, but it depends on the position of an employee in the organisation. Commitment is defined and developed by the actions of management. If a level of professionalism and commitment is higher in the individuals up in the hierarchy, it will go downwards. The structure of an organisation can be responsible for employee development and progression in the organisation, which brings more energy, motivation and commitment as they see themselves progressing both in terms of personal development and financial rewards. If allocated according to employees’ capabilities, the tasks help yield better performance, increased morale, and associate with the job role and the organisation.” (AK)

Therefore, this investigation confirms that the organisational structure is one of the critical elements to organisational commitment, making the employees perform in a more task-oriented manner where they link their identity with the organisation. They work towards the attainment of the goals of the organisation.

The main element to the organisational commitment in current research has been exploring the employees’ perspective regarding treatment at work (organisational justice). As described in prior studies, organisations try their level best to achieve the best performance from the employees through the activities of organisational justice (Polatacan and Cansoy, 2019; Tayyaba and Shenlei, 2020). Therefore, the interviewees referred to organisational justice as the equal opportunities given to the employees as per the policies, which helps enhance organisational commitment and performance. Organisational commitment relates to the individuals’ desire to remain part of an organisation and their loyalty (Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Romi and Ahman, 2020). The acceptance of the goals and values of the organisation and a passion for putting extra efforts to attain them refers to the three components of commitment. The affective commitment relates to employees’ emotional attachment to the company;

continuance is related to the cost of leaving the organisation, and normative is relevant to the sense of obligation to remain in the organisation (Muchinsky, 2006; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020). The university students judge the organisation's performance through the grades and jobs obtained by the students. At the same time, organisational commitment plays an essential role in motivating the employees and that employees by their best performance yield good students' grades. On this concept of did the university organised an exploratory visit to other international universities to improve the values of the organisation, the two-university professor commented as:

“Yeah, interestingly, our entire faculty, and I mean, not currently because we have the pandemic here. But interestingly, we have a very well-travelled faculty. Our faculty has been doing is they've been going to international destinations. We have people who are doing art exhibitions worldwide. We have people who will engage with international counterparts to gain experience. So, it's again part of the university's culture and policies. They must explore the world; they have to visit counterparts worldwide. We are the only university in Pakistan with students from eight different countries. We have students from India, Bhutan, Nepal, Maldives, Bangladesh, Afghanistan. These people come from other countries and cultures. We have faculty from Europe, faculty from the United States, students travelling to the United States, and faculty travelling to Europe.” (ZK)

“Yes, there was a visit to China through the China Student exchange program. University has organised an international visit for students under the mentorship of the faculty members [to enhance employees' commitment].” (RK)

From, above quotations, it has been revealed that organisational commitment is the efficient managing tool for orchestrating desired aspects of the organisation. It is used in improving the performance of the employees (Muchinsky, 2006; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020), and it also plays a vital role in making it efficient and effective with increased satisfaction of employees (Grawe *et al.*, 2012; Fischer *et al.*, 2020; Djaelani *et al.*, 2021). The organisational commitment is associated with the emotional attachment of employees, identification with the organisation, and involvement in the organisation. (Ryan and Organ, 1995; El-Nahas *et al.*, 2013; Prasetio *et al.*, 2017; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020). The organisational commitment has dual functions of fulfilling the psychological needs of employees and attaining the organisation's goals (Ryan

and Organ, 1995; El-Nahas *et al.*, 2013; Prasetyo *et al.*, 2017; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, while asking do you think the psychological needs of employees are fulfilled to obtain organisational goals, the university staff member responded:

“Yes, in an organisation, [the] emotional, social and mental health is very much important and if the employee is disturbed or is facing any trauma or any kind of physiological disturbance then obviously the working towards [the] attainment of the organisational goals is affected. So, I guess mental and emotional health has been ignored in organisations in the past. Still, things are changing; they give importance to this aspect and raise awareness among employees. It develops a sense of loyalty and commitment, of course.” (SK)

The quote above from the qualitative study emphasises meeting the psychological needs and their significance towards goals of the organisation (employee behaviour), and the organisational commitment as recognised through qualitative research is also confirmed through quantitative findings that employee behaviour is a substantial factor in measuring the organisational commitment.

Studies through the authors (Phatak, 1986; Hofstede, 1991; Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1998; Sani *et al.*, 2019) emphasise management style influences organisational commitment. The finding illustrates that the management style directly influences the employee’s commitment level (Sani *et al.*, 2019). The example from the interviewee has been described below:

“[The] Management style influences the commitment a lot. Some managers are bosses to give orders only, and some are leaders to inspire. Leadership is about inspiring the employees to gain organisational objectives by increasing employee commitment. The bureaucratic managers tend to demotivate the employees. On the other hand, the participative management style includes the employees increasing their job involvement, engagement, and commitment. If they are leaders, there is more commitment. If they are bosses, there is less commitment [in employees].” (RR)

These findings are consistent with prior research (Ryan and Organ, 1995; El-Nahas *et al.*, 2013; Prasetio *et al.*, 2017; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020). It referred to motivating the employees through management style to increase their commitment. It is considered significant in improving the individual's performance for generating a positive response towards the goals and objectives of the organisation (El-Nahas *et al.*, 2013; Prasetio *et al.*, 2017; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020). Hence, employee behaviour in fulfilling the employees' psychological needs is the central aspect.

While another factor of the construct of the organisational commitment in this research study is related to the 'The organisational commitment improves the organisational citizenship behaviour' which is also identified and confirmed through the qualitative research.

It is also suggested that organisations vary in the perception, execution and interventions of actions and activities based on the context to trigger organisational commitment among employees. The preceding sections discuss the results gained from qualitative research .

Various dimensions are present regarding the organisational commitment that determine the stakeholders' perceptions towards the organisational commitment (Bakker and Leiter, 2010; Supriyanto *et al.*, 2020; Choudhury *et al.*, 2021; Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021; Riyanto *et al.*, 2021). Though the main scope of the inquiries related to the various dimensions of organisational commitment is broad, few critical dimensions are selected as per relevant literature and the participants of the interviewees. The present research also supports the main dimensions considered by the previous findings and research studies (Hallberg and Schaufeli, 2006; Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019; Choudhury *et al.*, 2021; Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021).

The findings regarding the qualitative study revealed that organisational commitment has various main elements, i.e., organisational commitment is having a direct relationship with other factors associated with the employees. It plays a vital role for the employees while deciding to stay or leave the organisation (Pio *et al.*, 2018; Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, the textual analysis of all the interviewees reveals that the university's performance is improved with improved organisational commitment and improved organisational citizenship behaviour. These behaviours also affect the employees' perceptions while working in an organisation (Meyer *et al.*, 2006; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020;

Orgambidez and Benitez, 2021). Here are the critical comments provided by the university faculty members regarding the organisational commitment:

“The employees who strive hard to fulfil the organisation’s commitment will automatically be able to complete the tasks on time with better quality. So, organisational climate also impacts an employee’s behaviour to be committed to an organisation; otherwise, the employee would not be able to feel happy and satisfied at work.” (DZ)

In the same manner, the main comments given regarding the organisational commitment by an assistant professor are:

“...there are certain rules and certain commitments which defines the roles and limitations of employees. I think this is how any organisation can set the desired goals...” (RK)

Organisational commitment (OC) is identified as a bridge to maintain an employee’s relationship with the organisation (Genty, 2017; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Haque *et al.*, 2019; Naz *et al.*, 2020). The former research analysis shows that there is a relationship between turnover intentions and organisational commitment (Ababneh, 2020). The component of each type of organisational commitment may have various antecedents. Still, they all lead to less attention on leaving the organisations and result in additional commitment to job behaviour at work (Meyer *et al.*, 1991; Salanick, 1977; Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Paramaatha *et al.*, 2019; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, the assistant professor at the university described organisational commitment in the following manner.

“It is crucial for the management to understand that only a committed employee can yield additional performance. The less committed employees who are unsure whether to stay in the organisation or leave can be inspired through the vision. The committed individuals in my university always tend to stay behind to perform additional duties. I believe this behaviour is beneficial for increased performance.” (BSK)

These types of various observations described above are also cohering with previous studies of multiple authors (Paramaatha *et al.*, 2019; Banwo and Du, 2020; Erum *et al.*, 2020; Xiong and Wen, 2020). Hence, by keeping in view the organisation's outcome, Bae *et al.* (2020) recommended that the normative commitment was proved to be less convincing than affecting the employees' empowerment (Meyer and Allen 1991; Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Doan *et al.*, 2020). However, both continuance and affective commitments are based primarily on the association of the individuals with the organisation's normative commitment as per the organisation's interactions. The familial and cultural socialisation process allows individuals to learn and develop self-interest, obligation, and loyalty based on organisational commitment. Scholars such as Thirumalai *et al.* (2020) suggested that the increased significance of the normative type (feeling of obligation to stay in the organisation) of commitment and the cultural values enhances the social group performance (Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Doan *et al.*, 2020). It plays a vital role in improving the attachments and attitudes of the individuals with the organisation. Therefore, on this concept, the assistant lecturer at the university stressed in the manner given below.

“I think people who are committed intrinsically are productive. Their level of belongingness to the organisation is more related to emotional attachment and a lack of a better alternative. They cannot find good jobs or a job that pays them that well. They acknowledge the organisation's good practices that could also be CSR and stay in the organisation. They feel like they belong to the organisation and stand towards the values, rules, and missions. They believe in the organisation and how it is working. Also, they feel satisfied with how the organisation treats them fairly and think that the organisation is interested in their growth and development professionally. I think yes, it would have a very positive effect on their citizenship behaviour.” (MZ)

In this regard, an assistant professor has given similar comments on the organisational commitment, which are described as:

“The strong work ethics impact the employee behaviour and organisational commitment. If there are no strong work ethics, employee behaviour will be disturbed. Similarly, organisational commitment will also be affected. Strong work ethics help establish a work climate and culture by inculcating the core values. It

improves the perspectives of organisational commitment the employee behaviour in the workplace.” (DZ)

Main Themes

Sub-Themes

4.2.2. The factors that are impacting the organisational commitment

An organisation's ability to succeed depends on a number of important factors, one of which is the dedication of its workforce, which will help it achieve its objectives and improve organisational effectiveness and efficiency. Research has revealed that one of the most important aspects of human resource management today is employee commitment, and that these aspects are largely related to work values, motivation, and engagement.

When asked about how employees are managed to gain organisational commitment, most of the participants highlighted that organisational commitment is employee identification and involvement with the organisation may be used to assess employee commitment. They put forth more effort to be independent, have loftier goals, and get more done. The dedication of the organisation boosts productivity. Additionally, committed employees have a favourable effect on their co-workers' and team members' productivity. To achieve shared objectives, they exhort everyone to put out their best effort (P01, P03, P04, P05).

According to participants (P10, P15): When the commitment of a company is established, additional qualities such as employee satisfaction, engagement, leadership distribution, job performance, and job insecurity may be anticipated. From a management standpoint, understanding a worker's level of commitment to his or her work is crucial in order to measure their level of dedication to the daily activities that are given to them.

While participants (P06, P08) noted that It is crucial to understand that commitment levels differ from person to person and depend on a number of factors. As an illustration, the person could have affective commitment, in which case he or she is happy to stay with the company, but may also have continuation commitment, in which case they do not want to give up the comfort and income that their position gives. Last but not least, due to the nature of the profession, the person would feel obligated to stay on the work, leading to normative commitment.

Figure 4. 2: Illustration of the the association between participants and developed themes concerning research question 1

Source: Researcher

4.2.2.1. Organisational structure

Organizational structures help businesses make sure that all tasks necessary for successful operations are delegated to the right staff members. They also assist staff members, from entry-level employees to executives, in understanding their roles within the company, as well as who they report to and who they oversee. The results of the study show that organisational structure has an impact on employee performance. A poorly constructed organisational structure is

associated with low productivity, less task delegation, no incentives, and centralised decision-making. Participants gave the following answers when asked how organisational structure impacts organisational commitment:

P05 discussed that:

“Organisational commitment and organisational structure both are very much related to each other because whatever the structure is, it has got the triple down effect over everybody that is working in that institution. So, their commitment to the institution depends on how the organisation is structured, and how they are managed by the higher-ups. The structure also determines the chain of communication, the reporting mechanism, the freedom and liberty, the chain of command, and the culture in the organisation. A structure is an important factor when it comes to the company's success, growth, and profit. It gives clear goals and makes sure that responsibilities are clearly defined.”

P01 mentioned that:

“There is a complex structure of managers and middle managers which makes the communication harder, more complex, and takes more time to conclude. It ultimately impacts the behaviours and attitudes towards work and organisation negatively. So every decision that is taken by the teachers and managers is included but there is no freedom of decision due to the hierarchical structure. Everything needs to be discussed through this complex hierarchical channel. I think more freedom of communication; less hierarchy and a comparatively flatter structure can improve the attitudes of the employees positively.”

P04 suggested that:

“The structure determines the flow of information, decision making, reporting channels and hierarchy. For some employee's autocratic way is useful but some employees are self-motivated and they can be managed through a participative style. Commitment cannot be forced or instilled it comes with the overall personal experience the employee gets from an organisation such as its structure, management style, motivation, vision and personal goals.”

P07 argued that:

“An organisational structure outlines how certain activities are directed to achieve the goals of an organisation. Successful organisational structures define each employee's job and how it fits within the overall system. Leaders should consider a variety of factors before deciding

which type of organisation is best for their business, including the business goals, industry, and culture of the company.”

P08 asserted that:

“Now if an organisational structure influences the performance and attitude of employees organisations should study these problems and make use of new structures to improve employees, to give them a productive and innovative working team to achieve a competitive edge and advantage.”

P11 further elaborated:

“The commitment is affected by the structure. for example, hierarchal structure the employees will take certain procedures to reach a higher level or lower level in that hierarchy however in another structure then there are different procedures and ways to communicate and process their work therefore the structure of the organisation will affect the process of the work and the commitment of employees.”

4.2.2.2. Communication

Organisational commitment refers to the psychological relationships that attach a person to a company. Furthermore, organisational scientists have developed a number of methods to assess organisational commitment, as well as numerous sophisticated definitions of it. Meyer and Allen's commitment model, which was developed to encompass numerous frequently used definitions of commitment in the literature, is an example of this method.

When questioned about the significance of effective communication may help you and your employees develop a healthy working relationship, which can boost morale and efficiency.

P01 said:

“Core values, mission, and vision are crucial elements of organisational culture. I did not directly get any communication from the management but there are certain occasions and meetings from the administration.”

While P02 replied:

“I strongly believe that the core values and mission should be discussed during the induction that plays a crucial role in the course's start”

Similarly, P05, expressed his perspective:

“Yes, I have received communication about the value of the policy and the target of the organisation I work with.”

P06 put it:

“Communicating with managers and decision-makers will also affect the commencement and that's also part of the structure of the organisation.”

P07 reported that:

“Yes, I have received communication about the value of the organisation”

Also, P08 said:

“When there is a strict hierarchy for communication and decision-making, the employees feel controlled, and this makes them less enthusiastic to work. As a result, it affects the behaviour negatively.”

P09 expressed his concern about missing direct communication:

“Every organisation follows certain core values and ethics. I did not receive any direct communication from the management on the core values of the university.”

P03, however, consider communication as an essential method:

“However, I believe it must be certain to communicate the values of the organisation.”

P11 called attention to the significance of not receiving a direct communication:

“No, I did not receive any direct communication from the management. However, I believe there must be sessions at the beginning of the course to acknowledge this.”

P01 referred to:

“There is effective communication in the team and mutual respect between managers and the team.”

P15 discussed that:

“Hence, the effectiveness of communicating back to the employees is very slow and this is a major barrier affecting the employee's interest in the organisation's affairs. It also leads to boredom and creates a culture of disengaged employees with a poor attitude towards the organisation.”

According to P13:

“With clearly defined job roles, the scope of work and a clear line of communication, employees are very clear about the expectation and boundaries. This climate focuses more on the achievement and meeting of the goals or targets that have been set. As such, employees are not confused and understand the level of organisational commitment required to shoulder their responsibilities effectively and efficiently.”

P02 explained:

“I believe in effective communication and including subordinates in decision-making will create a high sense of connection with the management which in turn creates commitment from the employees.”

P04 said:

“For example, top to bottom communication in an organisation will take a lot of time to reach the lower-level employee, especially for a decision to reach the lower employees take a lot of time. Thus, this structure can create boredom and lower favourable attitudes towards the organisation.”

P09 stated that:

“The university always tries to run on its core values and beliefs. It emphasises these core values and ethics during meetings and training sessions. Thus, it reaches everyone and helps to build the organisation always functions and practises these values.”

Finally, P06 reflected her views on communication:

“I believe in effective communication and including subordinates in decision-making will create a high sense of connection with the management which in turn creates commitment from the employees.”

4.2.2.3. Strive to be an integral part of the organisation

Organizing is a critical component of management when it comes to defining work activities and dividing work into departments, establishing job positions, distributing tasks, and so on to accomplish organisational goals. Something vital is critical or necessary. Participants were interrogated, If you are a vital part of the team, the team cannot operate without you. An important component is required to complete the whole. In this sense, the term "essential" is virtually a synonym.

P05 argued that:

“In meeting agendas, we do get the information regarding the core values. I think these core values, mission, and vision need to be discussed in an induction session and there should be refresher training on it.”

P03 said:

“Yes, I did, and it helped me to align my personal goals and values with my organisations.”

Also, P08 stated:

“Yes, I have and I understand the goals and mission of the company.”

Finally, the ability to come up with original, imaginative ideas and bring them to life is referred to as creativity. Businesses may use employee creativity to create innovative solutions or more positive, collaborative work environments. Employees that are creative are more likely to think outside the box and take risks.

P07 elaborated:

“Then there is freedom in the working atmosphere to try new ideas the employees feel worth staying committed to the company.”

Organisational commitment is the degree of a person's participation and dedication to their specific line of work and the organisation. It also covers the numerous explanations for why professionals choose to remain in their existing positions rather than look for better

opportunities. Examples of OCB include organisational participation, organisational loyalty, and organisational conformity. Organizational climate, leadership, and job satisfaction are all factors that affect OCB. Participants underlined the following aspects when questioned about how organisational commitment affects organisational citizenship behaviour.

P02 explained that:

“Job satisfaction is like a bridge between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour. If an employee is not satisfied it is hard to be committed. There will be always this idea of leaving the organisation. Sometimes the risk of losing the job and the risk of not finding the desired job can be a factor to stay. So only satisfied employees show OCB which is a psychological attachment to the organisation.”

P02 said:

“For example, if an employee is being permanently monitored and there is no freedom of thinking outside the box this will bring down the satisfaction and there would not be any commitment to the organisation. I am satisfied with my job as I love what I do. I always wanted to teach so my passion comes true.”

P05 elaborated:

“It enhances the self-confidence and commitment of employees and reduces job stress and improves the ethical behaviour of the employees. I am happy with my work role, the policies of the organisation, the working relationships, my financial rewards and the overall support. I am satisfied and motivated towards my work.”

P09 said:

“Satisfaction is the catalyst toward organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour. A satisfied employee shows dedication, lower absenteeism, higher productivity and attachment to the organisation. I am satisfied with my job that is why I love to perform extra work sometimes I have to stay after my job or work an extra day for some volunteer project and I am happy to do that.”

It enhances the self-confidence and commitment of employees and reduces job stress and improves the ethical behaviour of the employees. I am satisfied with my job. I am getting more flexible and good working environment. (P01, P03, P04)

P01 stated:

“Job satisfaction is a very high impact on job performance and the effectiveness of the organizational citizenship behaviour. The greater the level of job satisfaction, the higher the level of organizational citizenship behaviour.”

While P07 explained:

“It enhances the self-confidence and commitment of employees and reduces job stress and improves the ethical behaviour of the employees. Organisational Commitment has also a positive effect on job Satisfaction. I am extremely satisfied with the job. I feel motivated to work every single day.”

According to P08:

“Job satisfaction is a measure of an employee's contentedness with their job, the feeling of enjoyment or fulfilment that a person derives from their job. It is measured in behavioural, cognitive and affective components. I am satisfied with the role and the way the team motivates.”

P03 stressed that:

“Employee effort is an important factor that determines an individual performance will be. When an employee feels satisfaction about the job, he/she is motivated to put greater effort into the performance. Then it tends to increase the overall performance of the organisation.”

P03 stated:

“Employees can be managed by acknowledging their needs, once their needs are fulfilled by their employers. Their employees will be committed more to the organisational target they will feel they are appreciated for every effort they put into the organisation, and they will know that they will be rewarded and acknowledged once they achieve their targets so according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs the employer has to know what is the need employees and acknowledging then motivate them.”

P08 indicated:

“The more satisfied employees the more productive they become this will also be an effective motivation. When employees feel satisfied in the job they are feeling more secure appreciated

motivated creative and innovative. I am very satisfied with my job as a teacher and I enjoy working in a team I enjoy my organisation and credit goes to the culture within it.”

In further elaboration, P08 said:

“Yes, I think I am committed to the organisation and actively collaborating with the team to achieve its goals. Sometimes additional activities contribute to my role as a teacher such as researching and reading, watching documentaries or reading the news will increase my knowledge of the market change but sometimes I tend to have a break and do some irrelevant activities such as cooking a new dish, sports or visiting new places over the weekend.”

On the other hand, P01 argued that:

“I cannot completely agree with that because job satisfaction is achieved more when the employer is passionate and have skills for the job. When the employee provides freedom and motivation, they feel more satisfied and committed to the job and organisation respectively.”

P01 added:

“Job satisfaction is crucial because if an employer can provide a job where the employee finds it satisfactory then they will start loving the organisation as well which shows their commitment, and they perform extra duties which shows their emotional and psychological attachment to the company.”

4.2.2.4. Participate in meetings and discussions

Originated from the data Meetings enable you and your team to engage, share information, handle issues, improve performance, create cooperation, and develop projects, to mention a few benefits. When asked how participation in a meeting environment indicates a cooperative effort to offer input, make decisions, solve issues, and assign activities collectively, participants replied as follows:

P01 said:

“For my particular institution, all the employees are not fully free to take decisions, but they are involved through departmental meetings. The decisions are finally to be approved by the board of directors or vice-chancellors.”

P09 explained that:

“We did receive an overview of the core values and mission of the university. It would be best if it is discussed during the team meeting and get suggestions from the employees.”

The information about the university was supplied and re-iterated to ensure core values are living and practising values as opposed to values just being displayed or communicated once or twice. All the core ethics are re-iterated during meetings and training to ensure sufficient attention is offered to these key elements which drive the organisational commitment and success. (P02, P05, P06)

P07 suggested that:

“When the employees are respected and given chances to explicit their opinion before management takes a decision impacts the employer in a way to develop a more inclusive and valued team. This creates a feeling of expression and hence they will be more loyal to the employer.”

P03 stated:

“When the employees are respected and given chances to explicit their opinion before management takes a decision impacts the employer in a way to develop a more inclusive and valued team. This creates a feeling of expression and hence they will be more loyal to the employer.”

4.2.2.5. Organisational structure and organisational commitment

The organisational structure indicates the internal processes and levels of authority as well. It determines the activities, tasks, control and roles (Daft, 1995; George, 2019). These internal processes get attention which is crucial for the success or failure of an organisation (Menguc and Auh, 2007; Zheng *et al.*, 2010; Nahma *et al.*, 2011, Abdul Hameed *et al.*, 2012; Nienaber and Martins, 2020), and one of the significant factors that get affected by the internal processes is organisational commitment. The employees are desired to be dedicated to achieving the organisational objectives by the organisational characteristic ‘commitment’ (Grawe *et al.*, 2012; Hawkins, 2019). The commitment of employees and their sustainability is a key to the success of an organisation. The positive behaviour and attitudes of the employees are achieved using high levels of commitment of the staff (Martin and Shore, 1989; Sinclair *et al.*, 2005;

Zafar and Chughtai, 2006; Srivastava, 2013; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Astuty and Udin, 2020).

Many interview respondents have been showing consensus regarding the centralised and well-designed forms of organisational structures for correctly managing the activities within an organisation. Major descriptions of the arguments as given through different interviewees from the staff of the university are given below:

“So, in any organisation, there are some such rules for employees to control systematically. If I go towards the rules, these are the punctuality and timings. There is a timeline defined for an employee for each task. So, I think this is very important for any organisation to work systematically because handling different kinds of employees is very difficult. Especially when in organisations all the employees are on different levels of commitment. So yes, bureaucratic management is also important in some circumstances, particularly with less committed employees.”

(RK)

The other interviewees were also observed to be consistent while asking to what extent organisational structure improves the attitude and behaviour of employees for organisational commitment:

“So as the commitment is concerned, there are two paths. One is how the organisation has a strategy and plan to fulfil certain goals. The second thing is personal commitment, so as far the strategy and plans are considered, they are clear usually quite impactful. All employees have different levels of commitment. Some may commit to the tasks, but others may be looking for the additional financial rewards.” (RR)

Some other employee responses were recorded from the interviewees:

“So far, the employees’ perceptions are concerned; usually, there are surveys which reflect these. There are interviews, and there is an informal discussion and usually asked how they feel. They give feedback, and most of the members from the various department give positive feedback.” (RR)

“Organisational commitment and organisational structure both are very much interlinked, so their commitment with the institution comes under how they are structured, how the higher-ups manage them.” (ZA)

Therefore, as per the above discussion, it is evident that there is a direct positive relationship between organisational commitment and organisational structure as described by the authors (Martin and Shore, 1989; Sinclair *et al.*, 2005; Zafar and Chughtai, 2006; Srivastava, 2013; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020; Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021).

4.3. Organisational justice

4.3.1. The psychological needs of employees are fulfilled

when asked to explain the relevance of anything that came from the data analysis Building a positive working connection with your staff via effective communication may improve morale and productivity. any requirement for psychological well-being that is not biological in nature It might develop purely inside the person, as in the case of the want for pleasure, or it can develop as a result of interactions between the person and their environment, as in the case of the desire for social acceptance, justice, or career fulfilment.

Three participants highlighted the importance of the psychological need of employees:

“Employees should be motivated by determining their psychological needs such as financial rewards, job security or promotion at work etc. These needs are fulfilled on a basic level but there should be a more personalised plan and review with individual employees.” (P01)

“Employees feel more satisfied and motivated with a reliable income. Employers offering higher compensation for the same job titles can retain more qualified employees. Especially during the pandemic in uncertain economic situation job security is the biggest factor to stay in a company.” (P11)

“Yes. Engagement and motivation are often team-based attitudes, so a team of individuals

who feel their needs are being met can create a more positive, engaging culture within the workplace. Employers with low engagement rates often have higher turnover rates, as well as issues with low morale and unhappy employees.” (P15)

While P02 said:

“Allow employees to shape their roles. Not to follow the micro-management in the team.”

P03 thought:

“Recognise and reward. Outside financial remuneration. Drive communication and transparency with the employees.”

P04 specified that:

“I feel the psychological need of the employees are fulfilled when the climate of the organisation is positive and there is what's a diff culture and teamwork within the organisation.”

Accordingly, P07 asserted that:

“The management style in my organisation is motivational in a democratic and laisses fair style where everyone can be involved in decision making and the whole team has mutual respect are they all deal with respect and tolerance to each other's opinion the whole team is self-motivated and everyone doing his role in his best ability the leadership has laziest fair as all equal level of expertise and everyone's doing his role in the best of his ability.”

P09 commented:

“Employees are psychologically motivated through various means including employee voice, financial rewards and career progression. These are part of what our organisation provides and positively influence our employees' organisational commitment.”

P12 said:

“Employees are not only motivated to work for monetary benefits. Some employees value recognition or career progression. Thus, it is mandatory to satisfy the psychological needs of employees to build commitment in them.”

P03 alluded to the notion of:

“The psychological needs of employees can be financial benefits, career goals or less control and more decision power. If a company can meet the psychological needs of an employee then as human nature, the firm will be always valued by the employee too.”

P07 commented:

“The psychological needs of employees can be financial benefits, career goals or less control and more decision power. If a company can meet the psychological needs of an employee then as human nature, the firm will be always valued by the employee too.”

4.3.2. Learning opportunities

The relationship between learning opportunities, work satisfaction, and organisational commitment was examined in the current study. Participants who were asked about this link said that learning programme had higher degrees of work satisfaction and organisational commitment than others.

P07 commented:

“Yes, I attend regular seminars and conferences. I got training for my job role which was outsourced to another training provider. I learned effective teaching practices through this training. I think there should be more updated training. I get regular opportunities for my CPD and it improves me as a person and as an employee. I am grateful for these learning opportunities.”

Also, P10 elaborated:

“Yes, I had many pieces of training such as professionalism, career building, best teaching practices and conflict management. It has helped me to improve my skills and practices. I effectively use them in my teaching practice. I feel more empowered and valued in the organisation and that is one of the reasons that I want to continue the job or you can say I am committed to the organisation.”

P10 stated:

“An organisation can support their employees by providing them with learning opportunities, cross-training, and any other interactive method that support their overall development.”

P07 said:

“Yes, I have received personal development training and time management training session from University.”

P01 and P03 also stated:

“Yes, we receive training sessions on personal development activities. We attend webinars and receive newsletters every month from different providers.”

P 15 acknowledged that:

“The university provides various training sessions to improve employability. I received training sessions on the best practices followed for effective teaching. This helped me to improve my teaching skills.”

P09 commented:

“I reckon that the proper training and improvement sessions will be supportive for the employees and this working climate which brings development to the employees, in turn, creates commitment in them.”

Also, P05 noted:

“Yes. I received many opportunities to update my CPD for receiving various seminars and conferences. I received manager job role training which helped me to transform into a better supervisor.”

P05 asserted that:

“As part of our regular continuous professional development, the university provides us with a lot of opportunities to develop ourselves through training, seminars, workshop and events.

We are also networking with other universities which have been facilitated by our organisation to share good practices.”

P07 noted that:

“The university provides us with many workshops, events, training, seminars etc. the university aims at our progression or our continuous professional development. This encourages the staff as they are developing along with the organisation which builds

commitment among them.”

Finally, P04 argued that:

“The training and seminars along with some workshops and events are some of the continuous professional developments I received from the university. The university tries to further bring quality to this by collaborating with other universities.”

4.3.3. Well-being of employees

Employee wellness refers to your employees' overall mental, physical, emotional, and financial well-being. It is influenced by a variety of factors, including their relationships with co-workers, their decisions, and the tools and resources available to them. Investing in employee wellbeing may result in increased employee engagement, reduced sick leave, improved performance, and increased output. When asked why employee well-being is important, the following comments were given. However, because wellness programmes stand apart from everyday business, they usually fall short of their promise.

P03 said:

“Climate is the overall perception of employees about the organisation. The overall values, communication, relationships and space for personal growth in the workplace comes with the climate of the organisation and it contributes to the mental health and well-being of employees positively. I feel committed to the organisation when the culture supports me to grow and improve my skills.”

P06 mentioned:

“The importance of organisational climate components, which enhance job performance and work engagement. Thus, they must fully master all of the employee-related processes of the organisation.”

P01 indicated that:

“The perception of an organisation's employees about the company's processes, policies, and practices. Understanding how the climate is in your company contributes significantly to retaining talent and reducing absenteeism.”

P05 said:

“I firmly believe that our organisational practices, culture and current climate contribute to the well-being of everyone, with significant emphasis on staff welfare, and personal and professional development. As an individual, everyone wishes to improve and become better in their job. Everyone would like to develop new skills and competencies.”

P08 described it:

“A positive organisational culture will create less stress and comfort for the employees to work with the organisation. This results in staff welfare. This culture will develop professionalism in the organisation too. The personal development achieved for the employees creates greater gratitude and commitment from the side employees.”

P02 recognised:

“A healthy organisational culture reduces stress and makes it easier for employees to work with the company. As a result, staff morale improves. Employees express greater gratitude and commitment as a result of the personal development they have received. Professionalism will be developed in the organisation because of this culture. Thus, it brings overall growth to the organisation and satisfies employees with quality.”

4.3.4. Organisational justice and organisational commitment

The researchers recommended that the organisational justice perceptions are directly related to the factors of an organisation such as job satisfaction (Cropanzano *et al.*, 2001; Tellier and Dowden, 2004; Olowookere *et al.*, 2020; Jang *et al.*, 2021), the legitimacy of an employee (Lines, 2005, p. 12), the trust of an employee (Lincoln and Kalleberg, 1990; Ogbu and Ugwu, 2019; Khaola and Rambe, 2020) and organisational commitment of the employees (Leung and Kwong, 2002). Farmer *et al.* (2003) evaluated the relationship between the organisational outcomes, job satisfaction and job performance with the organisational factors, i.e., organisational commitment (Jones, 1998; Colquitt *et al.*, 2001; Muchinsky, 2008; Alsaree, 2020). When asked that ‘did you receive any communication regarding the core values of the university from the management’, many of the interviewees have given positive responses as described here.

“Yes, we received communication regarding the university’s core values from the management, and then we react accordingly, as directed by the higher-ups in routine meetings. Apart from the major hierarchy, we have different directors, such as the academics and directors of the quality enhancement. Similarly, there are the research, innovation and commercialisation office or business incubation centres. So, all these directors have communications. All these communications must bring together to enhance the contact with social masses and the stakeholders like students. In my university, the fairness in the communication is always considered.” (DZ)

“Yes, everything is written in the policy fairly, and of course, when we start our job, we have the oath that what we have to do and what we will acquire in the coming years in the career. So, everything is written and documented in the policy for effective communication.” (DS)

Universities were also observed to be conducting the events or public programmes to build the reputation, identity and values of the organisation as described by various interviewees to enhance the employee commitment:

“Yes, it does from time to time; the university is holding alumnae dinner, farewells, charitable events, they have charitable concerts, then we have certain open days. I have already told you, Aids awareness day, Anti-tobacco day, to bring awareness among the students and bring them to the attention of the people from the outside. These events are cheered by ministers and media persons also invited as part of the institution’s marketing strategy.” (BSK)

“There were many events, but it got hit badly by the pandemic. There were events like sports gala, the cultural events in which different students represented their own culture in the past. Unfortunately, the COVID-19 hit hard, and at the moment, there are no activities but hopefully soon.” (DF)

Hence, this discussion emphasises that organisational justice and organisational commitment are positively related, supporting the concepts of previous authors (Leung and Kwong, 2002; Farmer *et al.*, 2003; Lines, 2005; Chou, 2009; Ogbu and Ugwu, 2019).

4.4. Management style

4.4.1. Motivated to progress within their organisation

To unlock and realise one's full potential, motivation is necessary, yet different people have different motivational triggers. The relationship between learning opportunities, work satisfaction, and organisational commitment was examined in the current study. Participants said that learning programme participants had higher levels of work satisfaction and organisational commitment than other participants when asked about this link. Considering that it is the force that propels the entire firm and has an impact on its performance, motivation in the workplace is a crucial issue in today's business world. Favourably motivated employees work significantly more effectively and efficiently to reach organisational objectives.

P01 explained his viewpoint as follows:

“There should be clear expectations communicated to the employees. Employees need to be trusted, respected and motivated to increase their commitment. Factors that motivate staff include realistic goals, good lines of communication, a clear workplace structure and a sense that their manager values their skills and personal qualities.”

P01 continued his reflection and said that:

“A culture of care and motivation and appreciation will have a huge impact on employees' performance and commitments when the employees feel they are part of the overall achievements then they will feel is their responsibility to do their best and become motivated and this will increase their performance.”

P09 and P11 implied that:

“Recognition and appreciation are considered to be valuable strategies to inbuild commitment in employees toward the organisation. While monetary benefits motivate employees, the sincerity toward an entity could be attained with the emotional bond created within the organisational culture.”

While P10 said:

“When the leaders of the organisation encourage to achieve goals and when the level of enthusiasm of the employee has raised the commitment will be more by the employees.”

In the same vein, P12 mentioned:

“When the employees feel that it’s their own company, then definitely it creates commitment among employees. This could be achieved by supporting the employees in different ways that ease their stress or it could be attained when the employees are also given minor shares of the company.”

P14 indicated that:

“The employees feel more motivated when they are given the freedom to take decisions and work on their decisions. When some of the sincere ideas or ways may not be approved by the superiors can create a negative attitude and the loss of interest will impact the output of the employees.”

Also, P13 recognised the following:

“They are motivated and more committed to the organisation as they feel the organisation is looking after them, therefore, in return, they look after the organisation enhancing the organisational commitment.”

Finally, P03 argued that:

“I believe this will create commitment among employees because after all the university creates its employees a chance to progress to the next level. This encourages the staff as they are developing along with the organisation which builds commitment among them.”

4.4.2. Management style and organisational commitment

The variables of the management styles and the culture of an organisation are determinant of the organisational commitment as proved by the current studies of present era. The management from the Australia and Hong Kong were selected as dichotomy in which they considered the characteristics of the management style and analysed the organisational commitment directly in positive relationship to the management style (Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1998; Hofstede, 1981, 1991; Phatak, 1986). Because as asking of How management style influences the organisational commitment, many interviewees give the consistent remarks:

“Management style is good constructive definitely it will impart a good impact and when people will have much more committed relation to the organisation, but if it is vice versa people are seeing there each and every one is not performing their duty well, they are kind of selfish towards the institute everyone is looking for their own personal benefits then overall environment will get destroyed.” (DF)

“The management style influences the organisational commitment in cent by cent. If the management style is not corporative if management have no control over its employees, its management is not taking the account to ... if the management is not valuing the surrounding people if the management does not pay attention to its stakeholders then the organisational commitment cannot be fulfilled and the organisational commitment it also depends on the vision and mission of the organisation. So, the management style it creates the mission, vision and the objectives of the management and those objectives are fulfilled by following a particular line of work and that line of work decides to which extent the organisation is committed for its corporate social responsibility. If the management have weak control over the employees if the management is not visionary, there will be very weak vision and mission and there will be no objectives and the whole setup will be destroyed. So, management style has great influence over the organisational commitment.” (DZ)

Accounting for the question of to what extent management style improves employee behaviour to be committed with organisation, the interviewees gave the steady replies such as:

“It has 100 % control over the employee’s behaviour. if it has weak control over the employee’s behaviour and if the management is not giving attention to its employees then there will be low chances to fulfil the commitment and if it is paying attention and if it is paying weightage to its employees and it is improving the status of their employees then there will be a speedy completion of the tasks.” (DZ)

“If you have a good management, you will have a good employee. So basically, all the tasks and activities are organized and processed by the management style, management structure or management style. So, if your management style is strong so definitely the employees must be committed and dedicated towards the organisation.” (RK)

The opinions given by several interviewees as described above illuminate that the management style have direct positive relationship with the organisational commitment as narrated by various researchers (such as Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1998; Hofstede, 1981, 1991; Phatak, 1986).

4.5. Organisational culture

Organisational culture is the collection of values, expectations, and practices that guide and inform the actions of all team members.

4.5.1. Think creatively

The results show that work satisfaction has a significant impact on organisational commitment, and that the organisational culture trait ‘innovation and creativity’ have a positive effect on employee happiness. As a result, work satisfaction serves as a connecting factor between dedication and company culture. When a firm has a strong culture, employees know what is expected of them and what they are aiming towards. Engaged employees are more likely to be content, driven, and committed to your company. An engaged employee is more likely to be: Associated with your company's goal. Participants' answers to the question on how corporate culture influences employee satisfaction were as follows:

P01 reflected his view and said:

“A goal-oriented climate is always better than a people-oriented climate where personal relationships are preferred over the mission and goals. I think the climate becomes more supportive if employees are given particular tasks with standard KPIs. There should always be room for improvement and betterment.”

P03 stated:

“The culture creates the environment in the organisation and influences the nature of the long-term plans that move the organisation toward its vision. Culture also dictates the policies and processes that enable the organisation to live its mission every day. So, the employees who get adjusted to a particular organisational culture also potentially become

more committed and own their work roles and the workplace.”

P07 said:

“The culture within an organisation is very important, playing a large role in whether it is a happy and healthy environment in which to work. In communicating and promoting the organisational ethos to employees, their acknowledgement and acceptance of it can influence their work behaviour and attitudes.”

P06 thought:

“In communicating and promoting the organisational ethos to employees, their acknowledgement and acceptance of it can influence their work behaviour and attitudes. When the interaction between the leadership and employees is good, the latter will make a greater contribution to team communication and collaboration and will also be encouraged to accomplish the mission and objectives assigned by the organisation, thereby enhancing job satisfaction.”

P04 specified that:

“The organisation of culture will create a general atmosphere for work. The environment and the culture will determine the relationship between the team. Employees become more productive when there is a positive atmosphere then the employees will feel save appreciated and motivated and this will improve performance amongst the team and relation with the managers.”

P07 asserted that:

“Organisation culture is certainly one of the elements of full success within the organisation, Culture of care and motivation and appreciation will have a huge impact on employees' performance and commitments when the employees feel they are part of the overall achievements then they will feel is their responsibility to do their best and become motivated and this will increase their performance.”

4.5.2. Employee engagement

Employees' dedication to and enthusiasm for their work and workplace You may evaluate and

manage your employees' opinions on important areas of your workplace culture by encouraging employee involvement. According to the literature, successful employees are those that come to work with a sense of purpose, a strong commitment to the company, a commitment to doing well, a collaborative attitude, effective communication with co-workers and leaders, and the capacity for giving and receiving constructive feedback. Participants provided the following information when asked for more details:

P03 stated:

“Employees will be committed more to the organisational target they will feel they are appreciated for every effort they put into the organisation, and they will know that they will be rewarded and acknowledged once they achieve their targets so according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs the employer has to know what is the need employees and acknowledging then motivate them.”

P05 elaborated:

“The managers highly emphasise employees' and subordinates' involvement and participation, particularly in key decision-making. That is offering an employee voice on the matters concerning the organisation, and as such employees feel valued and are more committed.”

Finally, P09 noted that:

“Organisational citizenship is about how the employees feel connected to the organisation, the level of belongingness, the level of engagement and contribution towards the organisation. All of these are key aspects of organizational commitment; therefore, it is clear there is a direct relationship between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship. The organisational commitment creates a platform for organisational citizenship and the higher the commitment, the stronger the belongingness and organisation commitment.”

4.5.3. Organisational culture and organisational commitment

The positive organisational culture may result in the employee's motivation that enhances the employees' satisfaction level at the workplace and impact the environment of the organisation

(Abraham *et al.*, 1997, p. 620; Alsaree, 2020; Jang, 2021). Motivated and satisfied employees tend to be committed to the organisation. Therefore, the positive organisational culture enhances organisational commitment (Abraham *et al.*, 1997; Valentine *et al.*, 2002; Rustiarini *et al.*, 2019). Mahmood and Awan (2010) studied the relationship between employee commitment, organisational culture, leadership style, and job satisfaction in the universities of Pakistan. They found a direct relationship between the organisational culture and employee commitment (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Visamitanan *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, inconsistent with the above descriptions while asking about the relationship between organisational culture and organisational commitment, the interviewees showed the following consistent perceptions:

“... so, the organisational culture is a major contributing factor towards satisfaction and to become more committed. It might be challenging to develop a culture of shared beliefs and values. The culture of any organisation shapes the behaviours and attitudes of employees. A positive culture can flourish organisational citizenship behaviour. The culture to raise commitment is also developed through motivating the individuals and taking care of their well-being which is part of CSR activities.”
(AK)

“...The organisational culture undoubtedly contributes to shaping employee behaviours. For example, in my university, the head of department shares ethical values, philosophy and the history of achievements with the employees. The employees take ownership of their work being part of the big ambition. Employees also feel committed when they see themselves associated with an organisation that has an ethical culture where employees are considered in the decision-making process.” (ZK)

In the same manner, while asking about to what extent organisational culture satisfies the employees to enhance organisational commitment, similar types of responses were observed:

“Yes, I guess if any faculty member is having some attitude or behavioural issue, the top management will call for its inquiry, so I guess there are many things which

are reflected here. The overall cultural values are reiterated with employees to keep them reminding of the expected attitudes and behaviours.” (DS)

“Culture can be adapted, and it can be innovated as with growing times. During pandemic the online work ethics have been introduced with new values and ethics.” (BSK)

As a result of the perceptions from employees of universities, it may be concluded that the direct positive relationship between the organisational culture and the organisational commitment exists as per the research studies of the authors (Abraham *et al.*, 1997; Mahmood and Awan, 2010; Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Nguyen *et al.*, 2020).

4.6. Job satisfaction

Organisational commitment is the degree of a person's participation and dedication to their specific line of work and the organisation. It also covers the numerous explanations for why professionals choose to remain in their existing positions rather than look for better opportunities. Examples of OCB include organisational participation, organisational loyalty, and organisational conformity. Organizational climate, management style, and job satisfaction are all factors that affect OCB. Participants underlined the following aspects when questioned about how organisational commitment affects organisational citizenship behaviour.

P02 explained that:

“Job satisfaction is like a bridge between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour. If an employee is not satisfied it is hard to be committed. There will be always this idea of leaving the organisation. Sometimes the risk of losing the job and the risk of not finding the desired job can be a factor to stay. So only satisfied employees show OCB which is a psychological attachment to the organisation.”

P02 said:

“For example, if an employee is being permanently monitored and there is no freedom of thinking outside the box this will bring down the satisfaction and there would not be any commitment to the organisation. I am satisfied with my job as I love what I do. I always

wanted to teach so my passion comes true.”

P05 elaborated:

“It enhances the self-confidence and commitment of employees and reduces job stress and improves the ethical behaviour of the employees. I am happy with my work role, the policies of the organisation, the working relationships, my financial rewards and the overall support. I am satisfied and motivated towards my work.”

P09 said:

“Satisfaction is the catalyst toward organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour. A satisfied employee shows dedication, lower absenteeism, higher productivity and attachment to the organisation. I am satisfied with my job that is why I love to perform extra work sometimes I have to stay after my job or work an extra day for some volunteer project and I am happy to do that.”

It enhances the self-confidence and commitment of employees and reduces job stress and improves the ethical behaviour of the employees. I am satisfied with my job. I am getting more flexible and good working environment. (P01, P03, P04)

P01 stated:

“Job satisfaction is a very high impact on job performance and the effectiveness of the organizational citizenship behaviour The greater the level of job satisfaction higher the level of organizational citizenship behaviour.”

While P07 explained:

“It enhances the self-confidence and commitment of employees and reduces job stress and improves the ethical behaviour of the employees. Organisational Commitment has also a positive effect on job Satisfaction. I am extremely satisfied with the job. I feel motivated to work every single day.”

According to P08:

“Job satisfaction is a measure of an employee's contentedness with their job, the feeling of enjoyment or fulfilment that a person derives from their job. It is measured in behavioural, cognitive and affective components. I am satisfied with the role and the way the team

motivates.”

P03 stressed that:

“Employee effort is an important factor that determines an individual performance will be. When an employee feels satisfaction about the job, he/she is motivated to put greater effort into the performance. Then it tends to increase the overall performance of the organisation.”

P03 stated:

“Employees can be managed by acknowledging their needs, once their needs are fulfilled by their employers. Their employees will be committed more to the organisational target they will feel they are appreciated for every effort they put into the organisation and they will know that they will be rewarded and acknowledged once they achieve their targets so according to Maslow's hierarchy of needs the employer has to know what is the need employees and acknowledging then motivate them.”

P08 indicated:

“The more satisfied employees the more productive they become this will also be an effective motivation. When employees feel satisfied in the job they are feeling more secure appreciated motivated creative and innovative. I am very satisfied with my job as a teacher and I enjoy working in a team I enjoy my organisation and credit goes to the culture within it.”

In further elaboration, P08 said:

“Yes, I think I am committed to the organisation and actively collaborating with the team to achieve its goals. Sometimes additional activities contribute to my role as a teacher such as researching and reading, watching documentaries or reading the news will increase my knowledge of the market change but sometimes I tend to have a break and do some irrelevant activities such as cooking a new dish, sports or visiting new places over the weekend.”

On the other hand, P01 argued that:

“I cannot completely agree with that because job satisfaction is achieved more when the employer is passionate and have skills for the job. When the employee provides freedom and motivation, they feel more satisfied and committed to the job and organisation respectively.”

P01 added:

“Job satisfaction is crucial because if an employer can provide a job where the employee

finds it satisfactory then they will start loving the organisation as well which shows their commitment, and they perform extra duties which shows their emotional and psychological attachment to the company.”

4.7. Management style

The management style of a manager is their approach to attaining their goals. The management style of a manager refers to how they plan, organise, decide, delegate, and manage their team. The study's findings show that organisational features have a substantial impact on employee commitment. Pay, the company's historical performance, training and development, management and leadership style, the work environment, teamwork, organisational structure, and job redesign are among these variables. When asked how management style influences organisational commitment, participants responded as follows:

P01 replied:

“The management style in my organisation is somewhat bureaucratic which sometimes works well when it comes to the timely completion of the tasks, strict deadlines and dealing with those kinds of employees who perform under supervision. I think the participative style would be required on a strategic level to involve the academic staff directly in the decision meeting process such as for extra curriculum activities, the course content and assessments.”

P05 said:

“A management style is a way in which a manager works to fulfil their goals. Management style includes the way that a manager plans, organizes, makes decisions, delegates, and manages their staff. Management styles vary by company, level of management, and even from person to person. I think managers need to adopt a situational style that sometimes is rigid and sometimes adaptive and flexible depending on the situation.”

P03 expressed his view:

“A management style is the particular way managers go about accomplishing these objectives. It encompasses the way they make decisions, how they plan and organize work, and how they exercise authority. Management styles vary by company, level of management, and even from person to person.”

P02 put it:

“The management style is the key to organisational success when the organisation leads and motivates its team democratically then everyone will feel responsibility there in their role and do their job to the own best of their ability.”

P07 reported:

“I work in a permissive style of management, where the managers and top authorities trust and support us as employees and keep less strict rules and less control which results in no micromanagement. Thus, employees are more creative and self-motivated.”

P06 said:

“The organisation I work, for mostly manages employees in a motivating leadership style. The employees are recognised and rewarded at the same time those who fail to meet the company standards are encouraged with effective guidance. This helped us to create a sense of bondedness towards the management.”

P04 argued that:

“My organisation follows a leadership style to influence the employees where the employees are recognised and rewarded for their performance. Thus, the management also takes necessary actions if someone fails to meet the requirement.”

P03 said:

“The organisation I work, for mostly manages employees in a motivating leadership style. The employees are recognised and rewarded at the same time those who fail to meet the company standards are encouraged with effective guidance. This helped us to create a sense of bondedness towards the management.”

P01 mentioned that:

“My organisation follows a leadership style to influence the employees where the employees are recognised and rewarded for their performance. Thus, the management also takes necessary actions if someone fails to meet the requirement.”

4.7.1. Management style and organisational commitment

The variables of the management style and the culture of an organisation are determinants of organisational commitment, as proved by the current studies of the present era. The management from Australia and Hong Kong were selected as a dichotomy. They considered the characteristics of the management style and analysed the organisational commitment directly in a positive relationship to the management style (Hofstede, 1981; Phatak, 1986; Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1998; Yin and Liao, 2020). As asking of ‘how management style influences the organisational commitment’, many interviewees give the consistent remarks:

“Management style, if constructive, will impart a good impact, and people will have a much more committed relationship to the organisation. I think commitment is an emotional attachment of an employee to the organisation. The management can influence the behaviour in all the ways.” (DF)

“The management style influences the organisational commitment. Suppose the management style is not corporative, with no control over its employees. If management is not taking the employees’ concerns into account... if the management is not valuing the surrounding people, if the management does not pay attention to its stakeholders, then the organisational commitment cannot be gained—the organisational commitment is linked to the vision and mission of the organisation. So, the management creates the mission, vision, and objectives. Those objectives are fulfilled by following a particular line of work. If the management has weak control over the employees and is not visionary, there will be a lack of employee contribution towards the objectives. So, management style has great influence over the organisational commitment.” (DZ)

Accounting for the question ‘to what extent management style improves employee behaviour to be committed with organisation,’ the interviewees gave steady replies such as:

“It [management style] has 100 % control over the employee’s behaviour. If the employees. The management of the university controls the behaviours. Employees

behave and respond to activities in a certain way. They feel committed and engaged if they are involved in the decision-making process.” (DZ)

“If you have good management, you will have a good employee. So basically, all the tasks and activities are organised and processed by the management. So, if the management style is strong, the employees must be committed and dedicated to the organisation.” (RK)

The opinions given by several interviewees as described above illuminate that the management style has a direct positive relationship with the organisational commitment as narrated by various researchers (Phatak, 1986; Hofstede, 1981, 1991; Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1998; Goswami *et al.*, 2020; Choudhary and Khan, 2021).

4.8. Organisational culture

Organizational climate, in the participants' opinion, has to do with how long-term employees perceive their workplace's culture and working conditions. Environment and personality are similar in that every individual has a particular personality and every organisation has a specific climate. In a positive workplace environment, you and your co-workers may be more motivated, productive, and morale may be greater. The following are some of the most significant aspects that affect the organisational environment of a workplace: At all levels, faith in leadership is necessary. When asked to elaborate on the relationship between people and organisations, participants gave the following answers:

P05 argued that:

“A goal-oriented climate is always better than a people-oriented climate where personal relationships are preferred over the mission and goals. I think the climate becomes more supportive if employees are given particular tasks with standard KPIs. There should always be room for improvement and betterment.”

P03 said:

“In my workplace, the organisational climate which is the overall atmosphere is supportive and innovative. I feel happy when my Dean trusts my abilities and gives me additional higher

responsibilities. I strongly assert that the supportive environment at work impacts personal life as well such as less stress, quality of life, and more family time. I would like to stick with this company as I feel the environment is supportive and I am going to continue progressing here.”

A great organisational climate in the workplace motivates employees, boosts morale, improves the company's profile and attracts new talent. The properties of the climate can have a powerful effect on every aspect of the workplace, from productivity to interpersonal relationships. (P01, P06)

P08 explained that:

“To improve this factor of your workplace’s organisational climate, you can evaluate each employee’s assignments and reassign tasks that were necessary to achieve balance. Give a reason why you assigned a task to an individual contributor. When team members know your rationale, they will likely feel more valued and that their share of the workload is fair and reasonable.”

Organisational climate and the general atmosphere in any organisation will play a huge part in creating a positive environment and this will increase collaboration between the teams and productivity. (P07)

According to P03:

“The environment that has been created by the organisation will determine their will being on positivity. Employees will feel more productive in a positive climate where there are support and a culture of care from the employer.”

P04 went on to state that:

“The climate has a huge impact on employee's well-being and their participation so when the organisation has a positive atmosphere then everyone will be working feeling safe and appreciated within the rules this will increase proficiency and performance and start work also it will increase their trust and relationship between employees and other members of staff.”

Yes, the climate of the organisation, the relationships within the organisation and

communication between colleagues are much important for employees to maintain well-being. If the employers and organisations are cooperative and supportive, it creates a sense of belongingness in them and that will create commitment in them. (P02, P09)

4.8.1. Organisational climate and organisational commitment

Allen and Meyer (1997) recommended that support by the organisation to the employees in terms of organisational climate causes a sense of shared perceptions, norms, or activities, which increases organisational commitment. This perceived environment of support from the organisation in its climate strengthens employees' attachment with the organisation. The workplace freedom of expression also plays a vital role in improving the outcomes. It also acts as a driving force for the individual's commitment to the organisation because of the feeling of employees that he might not be rejected or embarrassed while expressing himself (Chen and Komorita, 1994; Jha and Singh, 2019). Hence, while asking that the organisational climate is motivating the employees to be committed to the organisation, various interviewees gave the following comments:

“Yes. I think the success of an institution also depends on its climate. Overall, the beliefs and perceptions of teachers impact the student experience.” (BSK)

“I know some organisations in which a satisfying climate energises the behaviours. We should not ignore climate because it is the overall working atmosphere for a positively motivated workforce.” (MZ)

On asking about that to what extent organisational climate satisfies the employees to enhance organisational commitment (Reichers and Schneider 1990; Shinde *et al.*, 2020), the interviewees were agreed that the organisational climate satisfies the employees to enhance organisational commitment:

“This needs continuous efforts by the higher hierarchy. Because you cannot satisfy a bulk of the people without having a shared climate.” (DF)

“Organisational climate is developed and enhanced further through training, workshops and increment bonuses and good insurance facilities for employees satisfies the employees. In this way, the employees can enhance commitment for the organisation.” (RK)

The arguments given by various interviews above clarify that organisational climate has a direct positive relationship with organisational commitment as narrated by various researchers (Chen and Komorita, 1994; Allen and Meyer, 1997; Jha and Singh, 2019; Goswami *et al.*, 2020).

4.9. Improved employee behaviour

Employee behaviour is defined as a person's response to a certain employment setting. Employees must behave properly at work in order to sustain a positive workplace culture as well as earn the respect and admiration of their co-workers. following the data analysis, kind and polite. Office life is far more fun when employees try to be courteous and friendly to their co-workers, managers, and customers than when they try to cause disruptions or drama. Participants who were asked what factors may enhance employee behaviour provided the following responses:

P07 asserted:

“Employee engagement and shapes their attitudes and behaviour toward the organisation. I feel satisfied and motivated when the policies are fair and inclusive regardless of any biases. In this way, I feel personal bonding with the organisation.”

P09 commented:

“Organizational climate is highly correlated with organisational commitment and perceived organisational performance. Simple linear regression outcomes indicated that organisational climate is significant in predicting organisational commitment and perceived organisational performance.”

P01 said:

“Trust at all levels of leadership. The relationship between the people and the organisation.”

Support and recognition for hard work. When the team are all agreeing to keep a positive climate and atmosphere amongst each other than this will be an agreed behaviour, and everyone will be committed to his role and responsibility this will improve the productivity and performance of the whole team.”

P03 alluded to the notion of:

“The culture or climate of the organisation motivates the employees similarly if the organisation does not recognise the effort of employees, then it can demotivate them. Thus, if there is a positive culture in the organisation then it can create commitment among employees.”

P07 commented:

“If the employees feel more controlled and less valued then it can have a negative impact on the employee’s performance. Thus, if there is an improvement on it then definitely employees get motivated and show commitment to their work.”

Within our organisation and in many others, having a positive, innovative and caring climate is essential for the staff. With such an environment, the organisation is bound not only to retain highly committed staff but also to attract very good loyal talent again with heavy organisational commitment. It is human nature to stick to where they feel valued and can develop. (P02, P03, P05)

P10 elaborated:

“Within our organisation and in many others, having a positive, innovative and caring climate is essential for the staff. With such an environment, the organisation is bound not only to retain highly committed staff but also to attract very good loyal talent again with heavy organisational commitment. It is human nature to stick to where they feel valued and can develop.”

P10 stated:

“Every individual prefers to stay with an organisation where they have personal growth and where they are valued. Thus, if an organisation succeeds to create an atmosphere which is concerned for their employees, then they will create loyally and committed employees.”

P05 put it:

“To create commitment among employees, organisations much create a culture to support their employees. The employees will feel committed where they are valued and bring out their talent when they are given opportunities to grow.”

4.9.1. Employee behaviour and organisational commitment

Previous studies have indicated the direct link between employee commitment and employee behaviour (Zajac and Mathieu, 1990; Schmidt, 2009; Ali *et al.*, 2020). The personal properties of work experience, education, and age also act as mediators to strengthen the relationship between organisational commitment and employee behaviour (Steers, 1977; Hart *et al.*, 2000; García and Vila, 2005; Madhukar and Sharma, 2017; Al-Kurdi *et al.*, 2020). Guest *et al.* (1987) recommended that strong work ethics, lower education, job tenure and age correlate the positive relation of organisational commitment and employee behaviour. Hence on the question of ‘what extent practices of HRM act as an indicator of organisational commitment’, numerous interviewees give consistent positive remarks:

“The HRM team executes the policies and procedures. They need to ensure the fair treatment is provided to all the employees who would impact the employee behaviours.” (RR)

“The behaviours need to be organisational oriented to raise commitment. Behaviours signal the commitment as an organisation as both in terms of visionary and non-visionary benefits and incentives.” (ZK)

Following up with the question of to what extent strong work ethics exist to strengthen the relationship of employee behaviour and organisational commitment, the interviewees gave consistent responses such as:

“The organisation has a firm work ethic policy, and they also communicate those values from time to time to their employees. then I guess the employee behaviour and the organisational commitment always go side by side and if those organisations do not address this, they always face challenges.” (DS)

“I think our policies are devised to keep the employees’ behaviours in mind. Our best practices involve keeping employees happy, motivated, and involving them in the decision-making process. Whatever policies we devise, it’s keeping employees in mind, how they can work on their growth, how we can improve their engagement, and how we make them feel involved. So yes, everything revolves around them. They are the important stakeholders in our business, so we must make them feel involved in the process for commitment.” (MZ)

As mentioned above, the remarks given by different employees illuminate that employee behaviour directly correlates with organisational commitment as narrated by various researchers (such as Steers, 1977; Zajac and Mathieu, 1990; García and Vila, 2005; Schmidt, 2009; Mostafa *et al.*, 2019; Kim and Luengalongkot, 2020).

4.10. Organisational citizenship behaviour

Organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) is about all the positive and constructive employee actions and behaviours that aren't part of their formal job description. It's anything that employees do, out of their own free will, that supports their colleagues and benefits the organisation as a whole.

4.10.1. Employees committed to the organisation

The data suggest that asking for feedback on your performance is another way to show your dedication at work. Even though most companies have a formal evaluation process, asking for feedback, even in an informal way, can show that you are committed to the industry and are trying to advance the hard skills necessary for your job. Organizational commitment improves a company's performance and helps it achieve its objectives because motivated personnel are more productive and committed to their work. Participants who were asked how they show their commitment to the organisation said:

P01 holds the view that:

“Organisational citizenship behaviour shows employee engagement, and it is an indicator of commitment towards the organisation as well. OCB is about doing extra work other than the usual job responsibilities. So, only committed employees would go the extra mile as it shows their bonding to their work.”

P08 asserted that:

“I am loyal to the organisation. I feel emotionally attached to the organisation and my students. I am not in a position to quit the job as I am not going to get the same level of satisfaction, trust, and respect. I have invested time to earn this status which has ultimately made me committed to the organisation.”

P07 noted:

“Job satisfaction is the key to job commitments. When employees are happy with their role then they will do it to their best ability and have self-motivation to be creative and innovative within their role they don't feel enforced who do the rules and there will be no need who have strict rules on them.”

P01 said:

“Yes, I believe that I am committed to my organisation because I do feel an appetite for competence, and I am comfortable working for the betterment of my organisation beyond my normal duties.”

P04 argued that:

“I am highly committed to my organisation as I am being well looked after with opportunities for career progression, financial rewards and to develop my skills and competencies. I am also well valued as I have an employee voice, which is listened to.”

P09 explained her viewpoint:

“I am a committed employee of my organisation because the entity supports me in my personal and professional growth. Not only that I am rewarded on a monetary basis. I work for an entity that takes care of me.”

P11 implied that:

“Yes, I am highly committed to my organisation because am appropriately receive financial rewards, I am included in the team I work for, and I feel belongingness to the team and

company.”

4.10.2. Perform the tasks in the organisation beyond formal responsibilities

Any organisation has a duty to protect the health, safety, and welfare of its personnel, outside contractors, and the communities where it conducts business. As far as is reasonably practicable, employers are required by law to protect all employees' health and safety while they are at work. By coordinating others' efforts and going above and beyond, they convey that they value it when a team member takes the initiative and goes above and beyond to achieve a goal. There are other milestones that you could go beyond, including time and money. Participants' answers to the question of what it means to go above and beyond their duties at work were as follows:

P10 said:

“I think I do not limit myself to the usual responsibilities. I go the extra mile and take initiative to contribute to helping my colleagues. I train the newcomers, I support the students additionally for their employability skills, career counselling, and personal development.”

P01, P02, and P08 acknowledged that when employees are willing to go beyond their formal roles by helping out co-workers, volunteering to take on special assignments, introducing new ideas and work practices, attending non-mandatory meetings, putting in extra hours to complete important projects, and so forth, their companies are more efficient and effective.

According to P07:

“Get the cooperation and approval of management or those at the executive level. This is especially important if the organisation assigned the task of defining roles and responsibilities to people who are not at the executive level. They should be agreeable to the methods you used in assessing the current organisational structure, and your proposed changes, if any.”

P06 pointed out that:

“When the organisation creates a positive culture and appreciates the work ethic within the team then will result in to increase in the performance and commitments of the employees.

The employees will see whether the organisation is following its high standard when dealing with its employees and observe the rewarding system then this will increase the trust and the commitment toward their work. Appreciation of the team's performance will increase their commitments and citizenship within the organisation.”

P01 commented:

“In the education sector, it is expected to complete tasks and activities not often defined in the roles and responsibilities. This is a common practice in our organisation as staff are highly committed to the organisation. I always do a load of tasks outside my boundaries to show my organisational commitment and belongingness.”

P15 holds the view that:

“In the education sector, it is expected to complete tasks and activities not often defined in the roles and responsibilities. This is a common practice in our organisation as staff are highly committed to the organisation. I always do a load of tasks outside my boundaries to show my organisational commitment and belongingness.”

4.10.3. Organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour

The organisational commitment is discussed as it has an affecting impact on organisational citizenship behaviour, the individual and the organisational performances and, as a result, the interests in the organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour has been increased rapidly (Salas *et al.*, 2017; Jena and Pradhan, 2018).

Several studies related to organisational performance has examined that through organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational commitment, the performance of the organisations is improved (Anwar *et al.*, 2020). However, it has also been evident that the individual performance dimensions like the target achieving characteristics are impacted by the organisational citizenship behaviour and the organisational commitment. Hence, in the educational sector, such type of research study for the context of Pakistan has not been done which is examining the impact of the organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour from the employee perspective (Salas *et al.*, 2017; Jena and Pradhan, 2018; Anwar *et al.*, 2020).

This study attempts of answering the questions that have been set out in this research based on the literature (Anwar *et al.*, 2020): ‘What are the factors that are impacting the organisational commitment among employees in university settings in Pakistan? How organisational commitment impacts organisational citizenship behaviour in the organisations? How organisational citizenship behaviour impacts organisational performance?’.

Qualitative research has intended to measure the gaps between organisational commitment and the employee’s evaluation of organisational citizenship behaviour. It is also shown that various types of characteristics related to organisational commitment are observed to be having different kinds of meaning for several groups of the peoples and perception of the performance of the organisation may also be influenced (Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Romi and Ahman, 2020).

The qualitative research approach was adopted by employing the interview participants’ content analyses as per their experiences. The qualitative methodology approach has been adopted in a combination of quantitative approach for exploring (Saxena and Dhar, 2021) the role of the organisational commitment for building the organisational citizenship behaviour, individual and organisational performance that received significantly less attention up until today.

Operationalisation of organisational commitment concept appears to be depending on the organisational settings, policies and overall environment based on the employee perceptions (Belwalkar *et al.*, 2018; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020; Mokhtar *et al.*, 2021). The interviewees confirmed that organisational commitment improves organisational citizenship behaviour. For instance, a university professor asserted that:

“The organisational commitment improves the organisational citizenship behaviour. I think everyone from the organisational commitment. Organisational commitment is relevant to organisational citizenship behaviour as the committed employees work more than their set targets, and it ultimately brings a volunteering attitude of employees in the organisation. The employees feel more comfortable in the organisation if they are positively engaged through productive activities such as organising social activities towards society. Employees’ commitment is increased by various policies, support and feeling of justice. The commitment employees also

feel more associated with the organisation, and they tend to perform additional tasks without any formal rewards.” (DZ)

This citation confirms that the role of the organisational commitment is crucial for a favourable organisational citizenship behaviour of the employee (Cooper-Hakim, 2005; Chughtai and Zafar, 2006; Tella *et al.*, 2007; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). The researchers have also asserted that the management of employee commitment in the organisation has created favourable organisational citizenship behaviour (Jones, 1980; Ahmed *et al.*, 2019; Ko *et al.*, 2021).

The courses of action and organisation both are bonded together using the constructed definition of organisational citizenship behaviour which also targets the organisational commitment (Herscovitch and Meyer, 2001; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). The correlations between employee turnover and organisational commitment are enhanced as per consistent analysis by the scholar (Randall 1990, Hawkins, 2019; Ahmad and Kaleem, 2020). Further relationship between the organisational commitment and employee behaviour and discretion in employee was concluded by scholars (Herscovitch and Meyer, 2001; Djaelani *et al.*, 2020) as well as a direct relationship was observed between organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational commitment (Ryan and Organ, 1995; Jameel *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, on asking about ‘how would you describe the organisational commitment improves the organisational citizenship behaviour’, many interviewees give consistent positive responses as described below:

“Yes. A good professional person is always a good citizen. That is very simple. A person who is good in his own office, in his commitment, who has a progressive nature, who always work for the betterment, who look to overcome all those challenges which are faced, and he always tries to solve those problems. Ultimately, he will be a good corporate citizen and he will be performing very good in the society as well.” (AK)

“Of course, if you are more active because all the organisations are basically addressing the social issues, or they are putting the solution especially in the context in the universities set up so they are doing the welfare of the society. So, if our faculty members are committed towards the organisation so I guess it would also improve the citizenship behaviour.” (DS)

Similarly, on asking about ‘do you think the employees perform extra work voluntarily in the organisation’, some of the interviewees provided the identical response in a positive manner like:

“Some of them, yes. Of course, like for any organisation, there’s a certain percentage of people who work and who work more than they are obligated to. So, yes there’s definitely a percentage of people who go beyond their obligatory roles, but there’s a very big percentage of employees who barely meet the task, who barely finish the task that they have been hired to. So, I think it is a sort of exactly the organizational citizenship behaviour. It needs to be embedded in the culture and the culture should promote good citizenship behaviour. So, I think this is something the organisations can look at and work on.” (MZ)

“Yes! A lot of volunteer work. Most of the administrations do their work but some departments always do it for their financial benefit. An academician does a lot of work like research or certain other volunteer activities or giving time to a particular student or getting busy in some additional activities without any additional payments.” (DF)

Hence, shortly, it may be said that there exists a positive relationship between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour based on the above comments in line with the previous research studies of various scholars (Randall 1990; Ryan and Organ, 1995; Herscovitch and Meyer, 2001; Morales and Pasamar, 2019; Khaola and Rambe, 2020).

Figure 4. 3: The association between participants and developed themes concerning research question two.

Source: Researcher

4.11. The impact of organisational citizenship behaviour on organisational performance

The findings suggest that OCBs may increase an organization's ability to adapt to environmental changes. Helping behaviours may boost morale, team cohesiveness, and a sense of belonging, all of which can boost performance and help a firm attract and retain better employees. OCB can also improve employee morale. It increases people's job relevance. It increases worker productivity and performance; in fact, research show that OCB positively predicts performance. It results in improved social ties among employees. We then asked the participants to elaborate based on it, and they responded as follows:

P09 said:

“My performance depends on the key job roles which I am expected to do as per my job description. The extra activities are not part of my job, but my colleagues and students get benefited from them.”

P04 noted that:

“The additional activities I perform at work help me to learn more and to expand my working experience. I think this dedication and commitment are considered when it comes to promoting an employee to higher positions such as the head of an academic department.”

P01 highlighted:

“Keeping an eye on enhancing your skill set and exploring ways to learn something new is the initial step towards becoming a better version of yourself. It not only helps to increase your work performance but also creates potential opportunities for your professional development.”

P04 stated:

“I tried to find an additional activity that sharpened my skill and develop my knowledge in my career even in my hobbies and activities outside my work I try to research by reading About my profession in teaching I always try to innovate and change the activities for learner to better activities.”

P09 said:

“Additional activity will increase the relationship between the team and create a more positive climate and enthusiasm amongst the team. When the team achieves something in addition to their basic role then they will be very proud of their achievements, and this will increase their vision of all future standard performance at work.”

P02 argued that:

“The additional work improves my current practice and very often, I learn new skills and knowledge. Therefore, I am personally satisfied as I am always improving myself. This again encourages me to commit more to my organisation.”

P07 said:

“The additional work always helps my present practice, and I frequently develop new abilities and knowledge as a result of it. Hence, I am personally satisfied because I am constantly growing. This motivates me to devote more time to my organisation.”

P06 went on to explain:

“Yes, I believe my additional activities will improve my skills and my experience on such tasks improve which in turn contribute to my further achievements. I will be self-motivated to learn and improve my skills.”

P03 stressed that:

“The additional work always helps my present practice, and I frequently develop new abilities and knowledge as a result of it. Hence, I am personally satisfied because I am constantly growing. This motivates me to devote more time to my organisation.”

P11 stated:

“I believe my additional activities will improve my skills and my experience on such tasks improve which in turn contribute to my further achievements. I will be self-motivated to learn and improve my skills.”

4.11.1. The employees performing volunteer activities

The results demonstrate that all employment contracts contain implicit covenants of good faith

and confidence. The employer can be in breach of the employment contract if they add considerable new job requirements without compensating the employee more. Under no circumstances may your yearly income be less than the National Minimum Wage. When probed for further details, the individuals responded as follows:

Yes, the volunteer activities also contribute towards the achievement of the goals. The employees who perform additional activities feel highly motivated and involved in the organisation emotionally as well, so it adds value to the organisation.

P07 stated:

“Yes, that will develop the interpersonal relationship among the staff in the organisation and helps to achieve our organisational goals. The benefits of well-designed corporate volunteer programs have been established: They boost productivity, increase employee engagement, and improve hiring and retention, to name just a few.”

P07 said:

“The benefits of well-designed corporate volunteer programs have been established: They boost productivity, increase employee engagement, and improve hiring and retention, to name just a few. But too often, firms' programs fall short.”

P08 indicated:

“Involving volunteers can help organisations: Engage a more diverse range of skills, experience and knowledge. Reach more beneficiaries. Raise awareness about the organisation's cause, its profile and what it does.”

P02 stated that:

“Any contribution which is purely intended to add value to the organisation whether it is the additional activity by going the extra mile or the formal job responsibility will add to the performance of the organisation.”

In further elaboration, P08 said:

“Every little help, we have often heard it and in practice, it works. The volunteer activities are opportunities for everyone to develop their skills and knowledge further. It is also an opportunity to show a higher level of commitment to the organisation. Hence, all the

volunteer activities improve overall organisational performance.”

Finally, according to P15:

“Volunteering activities provide opportunities for everyone to further develop their skills and knowledge. It also provides opportunities to demonstrate a higher level of devotion to the organisation. As a result, all volunteer activities increase the overall effectiveness of the organisation.”

The data revealed that if the workers complete their tasks on time, they will have more time to work on other projects. This increases production and allows you to save money. achieving goals If workers are dedicated and productive, both the quality and quantity of their labour will improve.

P01 elaborated:

“Employees' attitudes and performance have an impact on how the organisation performs, if every employee's work is done correctly and if employees enjoy their working conditions.”

P01 added:

“High levels of organisational commitments are related to superior business performance, increased profitability, improved productivity, employee retention, customer satisfaction metrics, reduced customer churn, and above all improving the workplace culture.”

P07 stated:

“Organisational citizenship is the outcome of an employee's commitment where the employee feels belongingness, valued, and encouraged. This will create a feeling in employees to show gratitude towards the company in the form of organisational citizenship where they believe they work for their company.”

P08 reflected:

“Very satisfied with my job as a teacher because I feel I'm making difference in learners' lives, and I like to see learners improving their skills and knowledge so they can increase their employability skills. I always enjoy teaching and always find ways and approaches and read about teaching styles to innovate and provide the best for the learners.”

P04 also recognised that:

“The employees do beyond their duties because of their commitment. They will be aimed at achieving organisational goals. If the employees are treated fairly by providing them equal opportunities for growth and development, they tend to be committed and have OCB.”

P12 noted that:

“When there is organisational citizenship in an employee, they feel more connected with the organisation and work beyond their boundaries because they value their contribution. This happens only when the employee is highly motivated and committed.”

P05 said:

“Organisational citizenship is the outcome of an employee’s commitment where the employee feels belongingness, valued, and encouraged. This will create a feeling in employees to show gratitude towards the company in the form of organisational citizenship where they believe they work for their company.”

P13 put it:

“In some cases, yes organisational commitment has yielded to Employee citizenship they felt belonging.”

P07 reported:

“I think there should be justice in the organisation to gain organisational citizenship behaviour. The resource distribution, opportunities, chances to progress, training, and financial compensation all should be fair and equitable. Without procedural and distributional justice employees cannot be committed which is a pre-requisite of OCB.”

Finally, P04 concluded that:

“Employees could engage in this type of Organisational Citizenship Behaviour by speaking favourably about the organization to those outsiders of it, participating in charity projects the company participates in, and planning or attending company-sanctioned social events.”

4.11.2. Impact of organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour

The literature is suggesting as per Chapter II that organisational commitment led to different outcomes related to the organisational citizenship behaviour whereas organisational citizenship behaviour results in the individual as well as the organisational performance. The literature is evident that favourable organisational commitment is leading in a positive manner such as it yields favourable organisational citizenship behaviour, individual performance and organisational performance. Similarly, the literature is also suggesting as per Chapter II that organisational citizenship behaviour led to different outcomes related to organisational performance as well as individual performance. The literature is evident that favourable organisational citizenship behaviour is leading in a positive manner such as it yields favourable individual performance and organisational performance.

4.11.2.1. Improved individual performance

Birnbaum and Somers (1998) and Munene (1995) analysed the direct relationship between individual performance and OCB and observed a high correlation between organisational citizenship behaviour and individual performance. The research work is also done on the positive relationship between individual performance and OCB by scholars (Moberg and Rotenberry, 2007; Diefendorff *et al.*, 2002; Somech and Bolger, 2004; Chu *et al.*, 2005; Pasamar, 2019; Rao and Zaidi, 2020). The perception of individuals about duties assigned to them is influenced by the OCBs (Ryan and Organ, 1995). Therefore, while asking do you think you are concerned with your present job, the interviews provided the following arguments:

“I am not concerned with my job as I am performing my role on daily basis and in return getting compensation which I am satisfied with.” (ZA)

“At the moment, the present job is going good, but I get so much tired after a long day working in the labs.” (BSK)

While asking ‘how would you describe the optional activities you perform to improve your job performance’, most of the interviewees gave identical answers such as:

“I enjoy them actually. So, they are not only for the benefit of the organisation but in a large part they are for me. So, any courses or training that I opted for, are for me first and then the organisation. The training or activity would help me professionally and personally and it would benefit the organisation. So, it is for both the organisation and me. Everything other than work I am opting for which in some capacity is still work-related.” (MZ)

“I have already described that. Sometimes the activities do not seem related, but activities are quite related to the work role. A student-teacher relation, attachment to the student is to teach them. Sometimes you have to take them to the other grounds instead of just their classroom, you have to take them to the playground, you have let them, play a match. So, all these activities which actually I perform although they do not seem related, they are actually highly related with my job.” (DF)

In a summarised form, the above statements are consistent with the previous research that organisational citizenship behaviour is having a direct positive relationship with individual performance (Munene, 1995; Birnbaum and Somers, 1998; Diefendorff *et al.*, 2002; Somech and Bolger, 2004; Moberg and Rotenberry, 2007; Bakotic, 2016; Ribeiro *et al.*, 2020).

4.11.2.2. Lower absenteeism

Two meta-analyses found a correlation between absenteeism and organisational commitment (Harrison et al 2006; Meyer et al 2002). These findings of the interviews tell us that employees who are often absent from work are less emotionally attached to the organisation, or the other way around. However, longitudinal studies have found that while absenteeism is not a predictor for affective commitment (Cohen and Golan 2007), affective commitment does predict absenteeism (Hausknecht et al 2008; Clausen et al 2015). It should be noted, however, that the effect sizes found were rather small, suggesting that affective commitment has only a small

impact on absenteeism, and that other factors such as physical and psychological wellbeing, workload, and social support may be more important.

4.12. Organisational performance

Van Dyne *et al.* (1994) described that OCB is the main driving factor of behaviours of employees which causes consolidation between the behaviour of employees and goals of the institute. Thus, this realisation of the main goals of the institute causes an enhanced performance of the organisation (Hag and Jahangir, 2004; Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019; Haque, 2020). Hence, the OCB is a series of admirable and positive organisational behaviour which transmits the multi-dimensional correlations with the performance and consequences of organisation in a positive manner (Jahangir and Hag, 2004; Pinho *et al.*, 2014; Kopp *et al.*, 2020), and the core functional behaviour of organisations are protected by OCB (Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Alsayyed *et al.*, 2020; Liu and Kianto, 2021). So, while asking, ‘do you think, the employees perform volunteer activities for the organisation to improve organisational performance’, the interviewees provided the following consistent arguments:

“It always depends on the preference of the employees or the top management. I already said that it is a kind of personal philosophy. If the culture of the department is developed in such a way that it promotes working for social causes voluntarily, it increases the employees’ contribution to the organisation. The organisational culture is promoting the volunteer activities by an example from top management that are conducting many volunteer activities.” (DS)

“Yes, the employees do but also depends on how happy the employees are, the happier the employees, the more they are interested towards all such activities.” (BSK)

While asking to what extent employee’s behaviour is motivated ‘to perform activities beyond job responsibilities’, most of the interviewees gave identical answers such as:

“Employee’s behaviour is motivated by the organisation, definitely to perform activities beyond the job responsibilities. Because the employees....,

as I have already given an example, if a child is asked, he will get a bicycle on getting the first position in the class. He will work hard, so employees are motivated because performing extra activities will boost their personality and social status. They will get fame and reputation.” (DZ)

“I would say again; it is all about motivation. If managers take care of the employees’ well-being in our culture, that person is considered the best. A person would not focus on the work if a family issue at home keeps that person bothered, and of course, that individual would not perform more than an expectation or sometimes even less. A good manager with leadership qualities can sense the employee behaviour to support. In this way, commitment and citizenship behaviour both occur naturally”. (DF)

In short, the above comments are observed to be consistent with the previous research that prove that there exists a direct relationship between organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational performance (Van Dyne *et al.*, 1994; Ehrhart, 2004; Hag and Jahangir, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Haque, 2020; Bhuiyan *et al.*, 2020).

4.12.1. Improved turnover

Although for most organisations’ performance remains the most important outcome, today managers and business leaders emphasise the importance of attracting, motivating and retaining key talent (Morrow 2011). Scholars who first examined the construct of organisational commitment assumed that highly committed employees were less likely to quit their job (Meyer and Allen 1991). Employees with high continuance commitment intend to remain with their employer to avoid costs associated with leaving, whereas employees with high normative commitment feel that it would be morally inappropriate to leave the company. Likewise, employees that are emotionally attached to the organisation enjoy being an organisational member and are thus less likely to quit. Indeed, a large number of studies have demonstrated that affective commitment is a strong predictor for employees’ turnover intentions: the subjective probability that an individual will leave their organisation within a certain period of time (Fisher and Mansell 2009; Ng 2015; Ozkan et al 2020). It should be noted, however, that the relationship with actual turnover is weaker (Harrison et al 2006; Meyer

The main aims of this qualitative research work include the employees' perceptions in a current research study that may probe to a deeper and comprehensive understanding rather than only examining the surfaced features. The section aims to report the findings and the current data supporting the developments of the phenomenon of the present research study on different dimensions. Employees' perceptions of organisational commitment and the consequences of organisational commitment such as organisational citizenship behaviour and performance have been captured.

The analyses of this content of the study have been identifying the core elements relevant to organisational commitment and different dimensions that impact the relationship with organisational citizenship behaviour. The main elements uncovered in the present thesis, such as organisational commitment, has been described by various scholars as having a positive relationship with organisational citizenship behaviour (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019). Along with the literature (Bakker and Leiter, 2010; Supriyanto *et al.*, 2020) many of the participants of this qualitative interview have emphasised that organisational commitment is necessary for better performance of an organisation, which also supports the main concept (focal construct) described in Chapter II of this research study. The interviewees have been emphasising the core concepts and elements of organisational commitment based on employees' perceptions in terms of the performance of the organisation. It also observes that it affects various staff members of the universities and highlights the core role of adapting employees' behaviours and perceptions of the organisation for core competence.

It has been observed that the organisational commitment is influenced by various factors of the organisation such as the organisational structure (Katsikea *et al.*, 2011), organisational culture (Asree *et al.*, 2010), organisational justice (Wall and Cook, 1980; Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Lambert, 2003; Polatacan and Cansoy, 2019), organisational climate (Payne and Huffman, 2005), employee behaviour (Steers, 1977; García and Vila, 2005; Fitrio *et al.*, 2019), management style (Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1998; Hofstede, 1981, 1991; Phatak, 1986; Sani *et al.*, 2019), organisational corporate social responsibility (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Peterson, 2004; Polatacan and Cansoy, 2019), organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) (Stanley *et al.*, 2002), job satisfaction (Muchinsky, 2006), individual performance (Ryan and Organ, 1995) and organisational performance (Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010). However, organisational commitment has various kinds; most of these studies emphasise affective organisational commitment as it is closely related to work performances (Grawe *et al.*, 2012).

The organisational commitment also results in improving the productivity of employees (Meyer *et al.*, 2002), job satisfaction, motivation and OCBs (Cooper-Hakim and Viswesvaran, 2005; Chughtai and Zafar, 2006; Tella *et al.*, 2007), it also reduces absenteeism and turnover as well (Cooper-Hakim and Viswesvaran, 2005). The employee committed to the organisation may easily adhere to the organisation's goals and objectives and be keen to accept them (Valentine *et al.*, 2002; Nurdewati and Ellyawati, 2020). The researchers focus on the main aspects of the organisational commitment to enhancing the OCB, resulting in enhanced performance of the individual and the organisation (Ryan and Organ, 1995; Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Jameel *et al.*, 2020). Various theories also focus on these aspects of organisational commitment based on the organisational factors present in the diverse environments of the organisation. The most crucial theory related to the conceptual framework of the research work under consideration is the social exchange theory, which covers several factors that play a vital role in enhancing the organisation's performance (Organ, 1988; Moorman, 1991; Polatcan and Cansoy, 2019; Supriyanto *et al.*, 2020).

4.13. SUMMARY

The findings chapter examined the data analysis findings from interviews with 15 individuals who work in the higher education sector. The data demonstrates how participants in the Pakistani universities created the notion of employee commitment. The commitment of an organisation's staff would help achieve its goals and increase organisational effectiveness and efficiency, which is one of a number of critical elements that determine an organisation's capacity to succeed. According to research, one of the most crucial elements of modern human resource management is employee commitment, which is closely tied to the values, motivation, and engagement of the workplace.

It has been observed that various main themes which have been generated through qualitative data analysis confirms the findings of literature review. The organisational structure ensures flow of information in the organisation which has been emphasised by 10 participants. Employee wellbeing, chances of development, learning opportunities and learning opportunities are ensured through organisational justice which have also been confirmed by

various participants multiple times. The overall organisational culture promotes an innovative atmosphere and creative thinking which increases the productivity of the organisation.

As a consequence, the key topics influencing organisational commitment and citizenship behaviour were discussed in this chapter. Through qualitative data analysis, the researcher was able to analyse the current situation, define the extent to which respondents are concerned with engaging with one another, and study their influence on the application of organisational citizenship to enhance organisational performance. The next chapter discusses the investigation and analysis of the data collected, as well as the current approach for reviewing the literature.

The qualitative research study has been completed based on perceptions and comments. The most crucial type of inspiration in the current research study is the requirement of profound clarity into the conceptualisations and measurements of organisational commitment. Regardless of the significance of organisational commitment, this has not been defined well in the social sciences literature (Grawe *et al.*, 2012; Fischer *et al.*, 2020; Djaelani *et al.*, 2021). The primary definition related to 'organisational commitment' has already been developed in Chapter II, and this conceptualisation analysis has been given in this chapter. It is observed that insufficient attention has been paid so far relevant to organisational commitment and the influence on the organisational citizenship behaviour and the individual and organisational performance from the employee's perspective in the university sector of Pakistan. Therefore, the current research study attempts to achieve a substantial level of understandings of the central construct 'organisational commitment' provided by various interviewees of the qualitative research work. This chapter has deliberated the qualitative findings which addressed the purpose of the current research study (to develop a complete understanding of the organisational commitment and effect of organisational commitment on the organisational citizenship behaviour and on the individual and organisational performances) as well as on the research questions.

The succeeding chapter shall present the research study conclusion, its practical managerial and theoretical implications. The research study suggestions and limitations for upcoming research shall also be summarised in that chapter.

CHAPTER V: CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

5.1. INTRODUCTION

The present research has investigated the relationship between organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour, individual and organisational performance in the university context from the employee's perspective. The study is expected to fill a gap in the existing literature predominantly by establishing alternative and unconventional insights and perspectives into those factors that influence the organisational commitment (antecedents) and its key consequences (organisational citizenship behaviour, organisational performance, and individual performance). This study has employed a qualitative research method (interviews) to establish measurement scales and assess the research hypotheses.

The discussion in the prior chapter signifies that the research findings of the current research grasp a range of implications. It is also significant for the management that yearns to develop a favourable organisational citizenship behaviour that shall enhance individual and organisational performance. The study findings also identify six core factors impacting the favourability of organisational commitment, i.e., organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate and management style. Moreover, organisational commitment is observed to be positively associated with organisational citizenship behaviour. Additionally, organisational citizenship behaviour has been positively related to individual and organisational performance.

The main contributions of present research have been its demonstration of robust findings describing phenomena related to organisational commitment. It represented the perceptions that impact organisational citizenship behaviour, individual and organisational behaviour. Moreover, the present study adds unique viewpoints to the emerging literature on employee behaviours and commitment (mainly related to organisational citizenship behaviour). The qualitative study discussions specify potential future research guidance, and the present research's limitations are observed. The research is supplying implications for the management striving to identify and implement a favourable employee commitment. It has hoped that the future study shall be done based on current results to explore further.

Accordingly, the chapter explores the theoretical, methodological, and managerial detailed research contributions. The research findings implications are highlighted below. The current study limitations, recommendations and future implications for the upcoming research studies are showcased as well. Lastly, the conclusions have been drawn in the end.

5.2. IMPLICATIONS OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

This research asserts to make significant contributions to the existing body of knowledge. The gaps found in previous literature is the key contribution such as, ‘what are the factors that have an impact on organisational commitment?’, also ‘what is the impact of organisational commitment on organisational citizenship behaviour’, ‘what are the main impacts of organisational citizenship behaviour on individual and organisational performance?’. The gaps in the literature have been summarised as follow: firstly, it is observed that less attention has been given to the employees perceptions regarding the organisational commitment. Secondly, it has been noted that there is a lack of acknowledgement of the associations between organisational commitment, its various aspects, antecedents, and consequences (Evans *et al.*, 2020; Wilkanandya *et al.*, 2020). Thirdly, the management literature has an inadequacy of a qualitative research study related to employees’ perceptions of organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour in the context of university settings (Abugre, 2020; Aguiar-Quintana *et al.*, 2020; Donglong *et al.*, 2020; Holland and Kim, 2020). This research has been developed for filling the mentioned research gaps.

In the outline to present research, the distinction has been made between various factors (organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate, employee behaviour and management style) (refer to section 2.2 of chapter 2). The organisational commitment has been observed to have a strategic significance that needs multi-disciplinary approaches considered in the current study. The organisational commitment has complex relationships with other organisational practices and factors. Moreover, it is seen as the significant carrier through which the organisation’s performance may be estimated and enhanced.

Figure 5. 1: Research findings demonstrated in the visual form

Source: Research findings demonstrated in the visual form, the factors derived from literature review and confirmed through qualitative findings

This study adds to the present viewpoints of researchers (Abugre, 2020; Aguiar-Quintana *et al.*, 2020; Donglong *et al.*, 2020; Holland and Kim, 2020) which is related that ‘employee commitment impacts organisational citizenship behaviour’. The research examined employees’ perception related attributes related to organisational commitment, its components, and its outcomes. The research discussion based on quality evidence demonstrated the relationship between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour, yielding positive organisational performance. Both the students and the employees choose the university based on the performance and services provided by that organisation. The organisational commitment has been the basis of the employees’ organisational citizenship behaviour, forming specific positive scenarios that promote the organisation’s performance. The well-managed organisational commitment should enhance the motivational level of the employees working in the organisation. The organisational commitment may change individuals’ views about the organisation that consolidate and strengthen the perception of employees (Vondey, 2010; Jameel *et al.*, 2020). Meanwhile, no research has investigated

organisational commitment in its relationship with organisational citizenship behaviour and individual/organisational performance; therefore, there is no direct comparison of this study with previous research.

- 1) The Meyer and Allen scale was used to measure employee commitment as it relates to affective, normative, and continuance dimensions of commitment (Singh & Gupta, 2015). Findings indicate that even though employees exhibited higher rates of commitment based on team or professional affiliation and loyalty, there are significant differences in various organisations in terms of how employees perceive affiliations based on the existing organizational factors (Singh & Gupta, 2015). The previous research on different contributing factors and consequences of organisational commitment was done from the perception of academic staff and in different industries not considering many factors in one study, but this research has been conducted with respondents having administrative and managerial positions in the universities as it has not been studied extensively before (Wilkanandya et al., 2020).

- 2) Employees belonging to a collectivist society are found to be more strongly engaged in OCB. Individual differences are a weak predictor of OCB (Moorman & Blakely, 1995). Van Dyne et al. (2000) found that there is a strong and significant link between collectivism, individual differences and perceived trust on organisational citizenship behaviour. The perception of organisational justice and OCB varies in accordance to the national culture; this evidence is found by Ang, Dyne and Begley (2003). They conducted research across nations to measure the OCB of employees belonging to different cultures. Cohen (2006) also found that cultural differences especially individualistic or collectivist orientation does have an impact on organisational citizenship behaviour. He argued that collectivist cultures encourage OCB. A little has been investigated on the relationship between organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour in Pakistani university context from employees' perceptions of the organization. So, this study has explored more about the relationship in the light of the employee's perception (Ayesha Noor, 2009; Evans et al., 2020).

- 3) According to Oplatka (2006) and Hannam and Jimmieson (2002), there is very little research carried on organisational commitment and OCB in the context of universities, it needs some serious attention. The university staff commitment particularly teachers' commitment and OCB can be seen in three forms. First is involvement in novel and initiative actions. Second is helping the colleagues in their job and third is improving and helping the students and teaching them with positivism and helping them in getting their targets (Somech & Drach-Zahavy, 2000). According to Yucel (2008) all the employees especially teachers play an important role in improving the organisations and students. Teachers with high commitment and OCB have more value as compared to other because academic institution is dependent on them. Teacher's relationship with students is strong in high achieving institutions as compared to lower achieving universities (Shann, 1998). Therefore, it means organisational commitment and OCB is practiced more in high achieving universities than the low achieving universities. This study has encompassed the commitment in the university settings (Hussain and Khan, 2020; Michele *et al.*, 2020).
- 4) Quality of relationship amongst the teachers and the other departments of educational institutions are determined by many factors such as employee behaviour, perceived organisational justice and support, perceived organisational structure, climate, culture, management style, rewards systems and job satisfaction. These are the factors that determine OCB in an educational institution. These factors have a strong impact on organisational commitment and yields OCB of employees in universities and teachers (Garg & Rastogi, 2006). Organisational commitment is influenced by management style, organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational climate, employee behaviour and organisational justice has a direct relationship with OCB, performance of employees and OCB therefore this performance includes OCB. These organisational factors should be very favourable in order to make this relationship effective (Gadot, 2006). Management literature has been explored to shed more light and encompass these factors in a study which can help to enhance the managerial comprehension to effectively support the university to increase employee organisational commitment and OCB on employee perception of commitment and OCB (Abugre, 2020; Donglong *et al.*, 2020; Holland and Kim, 2020)

The present research complements the viewpoints of the researchers (Ryan and Organ, 1995; Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Jameel *et al.*, 2020) that employees' attributes regarding (organisational commitment as the base of) organisational citizenship behaviour that could drive this type of judgment and attitudinal consequences as individual and organisational performance (Hussain and Khan, 2020; Michele *et al.*, 2020). This research contributes to the behavioural theory through its findings in a holistic way. Organisational commitment has drawn the attention of the authors related to employee behavioural and employee engagement studies (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Waddock and Parallel, 2004; Sen *et al.*, 2006; Singh *et al.*, 2008; Al Zeifiti and Mohamad, 2017; Hendri, 2019; Supriya and Dadhabhai, 2020). The contribution of the present research is to develop broader understandings of employee commitment through examining if organisational citizenship behaviour influences the individual and organisational performance in the perception of employees. So, the current study is among the first research studies to validate empirically the assumptions of scholars (Hussain and Khan, 2020; Michele *et al.*, 2020; Odhiambo, 2019; Kolsom *et al.*, 2020; Manalo *et al.*, 2020) that organisational commitment has the impacts on organisational citizenship behaviour and the individual/organisational performance in the context of university setting in Pakistan. It should develop insights that would substantially add to the scope of knowledge and support the validation and purify the findings in the literature related to the field. The study's contribution in the most substantial component of the doctoral thesis is related to the alliance of the research's implications to the extension of the domain of study.

The research contributions extending the limitations of the knowledge have been presented in the current section, starting from theoretical interpretations and expanding to methodologic contributions. The managerial contributions have been incorporated in the following sections.

5.2.1. Theoretical contribution of the study

There four main questions of the research which are posed: "What are the factors that have an impact on organisational commitment?", "How does organisational commitment impacts on organisational citizenship behaviour?", and "What are the main impacts of organisational citizenship behaviour on individual and organisational performance?", based on study objectives (Section 1.5 of Chapter I). The four main objectives of the research to address these research questions have been developed.

This dissertation provides a threefold theoretical contribution to the existing literature in terms of; a) extending to the theory, b) conceptualising the employee perspective c) generalising the findings.

5.2.1.1. Extending the theory

This research contributes to employee behaviour and commitment literature by examining the existing literature and offering unique theoretical findings. The foremost and the comprehensive contribution related to the present study is to broaden the knowledge through investigating within a university setting the multiple effects of the commitment on the employee perceptions about the performance of the organisation in Pakistan (Odhiambo, 2019; Kolsom *et al.*, 2020; Manalo *et al.*, 2020) asserted that the organisational commitment is relevant to organisational citizenship behaviour; however, these relationships have been rarely studied. In the context of current research, many scholars (Ridwan *et al.*, 2020; Michele *et al.*, 2020; Abugre, 2020; Aguiar-Quintana *et al.*, 2020; Donglong *et al.*, 2020; Manalo *et al.*, 2020) have examined commitment; however, it was not related to organisational citizenship behaviour as an outcome of organisational commitment. Therefore, the present study offers the examination of employee perceptions and the key factors that influence the favourability of organisational commitment (antecedents) and the consequences. Moreover, it strives to tackle the research gaps and respond to the previous demands for explorations from the employees' perspectives (Abugre, 2020; Aguiar-Quintana *et al.*, 2020; Donglong *et al.*, 2020; Holland and Kim, 2020).

It has been seen that Pakistan being a collectivist society having more affective commitment tends to show more commitment if all the organisational factors as discussed in the study are favourable such as organisational structure, culture, climate, justice, management style etc.

The establishment of multi-disciplinary concepts (refer to Section 2.2) for organisational commitment was observed to be the main contribution of the current study. Developing a multi-disciplinary understanding of relationships that might be interpreted in findings with the relevance related to operationalisation to the research is quite challenging (Palmer and Bejou, 2006; Latuszek, 2021). This study has been one of the pioneer inductive type of research

through combining organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour, individual performance, organisational performance in the Pakistani university context, and knowledge relevant to the organisational commitment for holistically describing the organisational citizenship behaviour. Simultaneously, this research contributes to the body of knowledge related to employees' commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour, and organisational and individual performance through collecting and examining the employee perceptions.

This research has pursued redefining and regenerating current research in the area of organisational commitment. This study contributes to organisational citizenship behaviour literature by establishing and assessing the scale specifying organisational commitment related to the scope of its influences. The academic perspective asserts that the present research findings take up a more methodical and inclusive approach compared to any other study so far.

In the offered research model, the key components that influence the organisational commitment (organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate and management style) have been determined, while the major consequences (organisational citizenship behaviour, organisational performance and individual performance) of proposed organisational commitment in the employees' perceptions. The organisational commitment has been the way forward to motivate the employees and improve the organisation's performance (Organ, 1988; Moorman, 1991; Ongori, 2009; Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019; Jameel *et al.*, 2020). On the basis of the findings of the research, the main factors that influence organisational commitment are 1) organisational structure, 2) organisational culture, 3) organisational justice, 4) organisational climate, and 5) management style. The current research encompasses previous research by investigating the relations between organisational commitment and its antecedent and the consequences from employees' perceptions. Hence, the current study's findings offer benefits in university settings. Moreover, the results require great cautions while applying the theories in other contexts and invoking the framework of the organisational commitment.

5.2.1.2. Conceptualising the employee perceptions

After establishing the significances of organisational commitment, a question arises of the organisational commitment's importance? What have been the main factors that are influencing organisational commitment? Does organisational commitment have any influence on the critical areas of the business? These are the questions that lead to the main questions of the research. The findings of the research shows that employees have a higher emphasis on the following key aspects.

Employees asserted that:

Organisational structure: A favourable structure consists of all the elements which encourage 'effective communication', 'participation' and 'opportunities to grow'. An organisational structure is either **centralised** or **decentralised**. Traditionally, organisations have been structured with centralised management and a defined chain of command. However, employees in the universities of Pakistan advocated a more '**flatter**' hierarchy and '**more participative environment**' and they indicated they tend to be more committed and feel associated with the organisation if there is **less use of centralised power**. In many organisations the '**decentralisation**' of decision-making yields more **OCB** where employees tend to go **extra mile** to achieve certain goals in the organisation.

Organisational justice: It has been observed from the literature review and qualitative research findings that employees perceive justice in the organisation as the '**opportunities of learning**', '**training and CPD**', '**fair rewards**', '**opportunities of promotion and growth**' within the organisation. Employees tend to show a discretionary behaviour known as 'citizenship behaviour'. Discretionary behaviour refers to **the employee behaviour 8k7y h, that is not directly or explicitly recognised by the formal reward system, and in the aggregate promotes the efficient and effective functioning of the organisation** (Van Dyne, Cummings, & McLean Parks, 1995; Organ, Podsakoff, & MacKenzie, 2006). **Discretionary effort/behaviour** of the employees is the key to improving performance in any organisation simply because **the employees are motivated, engaged and put in much more effort than what is expected which results in increased performance**. So, the given working environment and opportunities ensured through the justice system in the organisation.

Management style: The **authoritative management** style tends to bring a **gap** between employees and the managers. Employees do not trust the managers if there are no participation opportunities in the organisations. The **participative management** style in an educational

institutional setting can be the most beneficial one to make the teachers and other staff more **committed** as it involves everyone in the decision-making process. From the research findings employees feel more valued and motivated if they are involved in important activities in the organisation. So, managers in the universities can implement **participative** or **collaborative** management style. It yields citizenship behaviour among employees as a result of collaborative style of management.

Organisational culture: Organisational culture is the collection of values, expectations, and practices that guide and inform the actions of all team members. Organisational culture affects all aspects of the organisation, from punctuality and tone to contract terms and employee benefits. When workplace culture aligns with the employees, they are more likely to feel more comfortable, supported, and valued. The positive and innovative culture boosts the organisational citizenship behaviour and the commitment which has been reinforced by the research findings and the literature review.

Organisational climate: On the basis of the objectives of the research (refer to Section-8.2.1), the current research has focused first on organisational commitment. Afterwards, the concept of organisational commitment, the antecedents and consequences are introduced and operationalised in employees' perceptions. The organisational commitment therefore, assess the activities of an organisation regarding the management of organisational commitment (Grawe *et al*, 2012; Fischer *et al.*, 2020).

Employee behaviour: Employee behaviour is as an employee's reaction to a particular situation in the organisation. Employees should behave sensibly at workplace not only to gain appreciation and respect from others but also to maintain a healthy work culture. The employees need to adhere to the rules and regulations of the organisation. Hence, the positive employee behaviour tends to result organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour (Grawe *et al*, 2012; Fischer *et al.*, 2020).

Job satisfaction: This research findings revealed that organisational commitment is the emotional responses which an employee has towards the organisation while job satisfaction is the responses that an employee has towards its job. Additionally, job satisfaction creates loyalty, confidence and commitment to the organisation as reported by the study findings and literature review (Kasim & Ghaffar, 2012). It leads to the improvement of productivity and

avoid negative behavior such as absenteeism and turnover (Linda & Michael, 2014) which encompasses organisational citizenship behaviour.

Organisational citizenship behaviour: OCB includes cooperating with others, volunteering for additional tasks, orienting new employees, offering to help others accomplish their work, and voluntarily doing more than the job requires (Borman & Motowidlo, 1993). **OCB is strongly related to organisational commitment, structure, justice, employee behaviour, climate, culture, management style and job satisfaction. job attitudes.** Job satisfaction, perception of fairness and organisational commitment in particular make employees want to engage in organisational citizenship behaviour.

- **Individual performance:** The research findings showed that employee performance is how employees fulfil the duties of their role, completes required tasks and behaves in the organisation.
- **Task performance:** The research study revealed that employees carry out the core activities included in their job. This could include the service quality or their impact on the people in their team in the university.
- **Contextual performance or ‘organisational citizenship behaviour’:** It has been found out in this study that the voluntary activities that benefit the organisation but sits outside the employees’ core roles. For example, helping other colleagues or students reaching their targets, or contributing to additional initiatives.
- **Adaptive performance:** In this qualitative research employees emphasised on training and development. Employees respond to changing job demands or support innovation in the universities which indicates their performance.

Organisational performance: The research findings shown that organisational commitment results into benefits such as **(i) increased job satisfaction (ii) increased job performance (iii) increased emotional attachment of employees with the organisation (iv) improved quality of service in the universities (v) decreased employee turnover (vi) decreased intention to leave (vii) decreased intention to search for alternative jobs (viii) decreased absenteeism.** Employee commitment is to be viewed as a vital factor in the organisation. Universities which ignore employee commitment has difficulty in retaining and replacing the competent employees and thus finds it hard to optimise performance. The recruitment process incurs costs and time to the organisation.

The reviews of relevant research studies (Odhiambo, 2019; Abugre, 2020; Aguiar-Quintana *et al.*, 2020; Donglong *et al.*, 2020) asserts that there has not been any study which discusses, evaluates and adopts a favourable organisational commitment. It is attributing to facts that organisational commitment is a challenging research domain with various aspects that demand in-depth examination.

The research findings also propose that organisational commitment has been recognised to be the essential factor of organisational citizenship behaviour. The support has been extended in theory related to the antecedent and consequence of organisational commitment. The research has well examined the constructs of the research, and it indicated that concept might be used effectively in contexts of other research studies. Additionally, the research may support the service scholars for investigating the field. This dissertation provided shreds of evidence in current debates over and the theoretical definition of organisational commitment. Although prior scholars (Grawe *et al.*, 2012; Fischer *et al.*, 2020; Djaelani *et al.*, 2021 etc.) showed the significance of organisational commitment and its relation to organisational citizenship behaviour, a concrete definition of the construct leads the field. This study contributed comprehensive and integrated perspectives conceptualised to extend the knowledge of multiple aspects of favourable organisational commitment in contexts of university setting in Pakistan. It confirmed the relevance to employ major antecedents and the consequences for of the proposed constructs. In spite of the limitations of the study, this research is provided with a few substantial results concerning dimensions of the construct of organisational commitment and OCB. The findings propose that organisational commitment has undoubtedly been a construct having multidimensional constructs.

The theoretic contributions of the study are regarding the establishment of conceptualisations of the concepts of organisational commitment, the antecedents and its consequence. This dissertation adds value by contributing to the present knowledge at the level of conceptualisation through investigation of organisational commitment from the perspective of employees to gain deep understandings of roles played through organisational commitment in building organisational citizenship behaviour that leads to enhanced organisational/individual performance. Thus, the study enlightens organisational commitment concepts and relationships between relevant research variables. The study demonstrates the conceptualisations of 'commitment' from university teaching faculty and administration angle as an entity of five

major components: organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate and management style. The present study's finding shall help the university top management in ensuring that they may generate an environment to support organisational commitment to enhancing organisational citizenship behaviour of the employees and it shall strengthen individual and organisational performance.

5.2.1.3. Theory testing and generalisation

As described above, current research pursues to holistically explain the relationship between organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour, and organisational and individual performance in employees' perceptions within university settings. By examining the proposed research idea having a relationship between organisational commitment and its antecedent (organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate and management style) and main consequences of the research (organisational citizenship behaviour, individual and organisational performance) in context of universities operating in the Pakistan, present study is hoped to providing further understanding of prior literature and contributing to theory generalisation and testing. However, the employees in Pakistan and other university stakeholders might have some distinguishing characteristics affecting the results of the current study, and results may also be generalised on the educational sector (Ridwan *et al.*, 2020).

The present research also assured that the assessment of current constructs' measurements is adopted, identified, and refined. Present research complements the view of authors (Odhiambo, 2019; Kolsom *et al.*, 2020; Manalo *et al.*, 2020), claiming that (1) lack of research on the constructs of organisational commitment (2) there exists an association between organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour and the individual or organisational performance. Additionally, for better understanding the concepts of organisational commitment and its constructs (Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019; Hussain and Khan, 2020; Michele *et al.*, 2020; Moneva *et al.*, 2020), the employee perceptions have been examined through qualitative research.

In summarised form, this research has been unique for operationalising and conceptualising the concept of favourable organisational commitment and its influences on organisational

citizenship behaviour and organisational/individual performance in the university setting. This study attempts to construct a new preface foundation that could have important implications for the top management. The study's theoretical contributions imply that the generalisability of results would be sufficient.

5.2.2. Practical recommendations for managers

This research has proposed the managerial contributions for top management and other decision-makers in the organisations who seek for deeper understanding of the relationship between favourable organisational commitment and factor in the antecedent (i.e. organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate and management style) from employees' perspective and the effects on favourable organisational citizenship behaviour and favourable organisational performance. The present research findings have significant managerial implications through the presentation of an inclusive scenario of where favourable organisational commitment can be achieved within the organisation for achieving favourable organisational citizenship behaviour in the perceptions of employees of the university. Alternatively, an insightful comprehension of relevant concepts could support managers and university administration in devising favourable organisational commitment to creating favourable organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational/individual performance.

Another conclusive remark has been drawn through the research regarding the difference between the employees and management dimensions. For instance, the manager inclined more towards performance, whereas the employees emphasised the organisational culture and climate. The employees are inclined more towards achieving satisfaction as an essential element which leads to the performance. In contrast, top management tends to consider the financial performance and employee behaviour to a level of commitment within the organisation. The incorporations of the employees and the management attitudes and skills hold great potentials for organisations. This research provides the managers with insight into the implication of organisational commitment. Therefore, it is necessary to enhance organisational commitment to strengthen the OCB and the organisational performance.

5.2.3. Recommendations

After data presentation and analysis and after answering the study's questions, the researcher provided the following recommendations:

- 1) The managers in the universities should focus on having a more 'flatter hierarchical structure' in the organisation to maximise the employees' attachment, communication, learning, collaboration and involvement in their tasks and to the overall organisation which brings citizenship behaviour.
- 2) In the universities employees both academic and non-academic staff should be provided fair chances of training, learning, growth in the organisation. The fair reward system, continuous motivation and encouragement can lead to organisational commitment and OCB. Managers need to ensure there is procedural, distributive and interactional justice in the organisations. Distributive justice occurs when employees believe that outcomes are equitable (Colquitt et al., 2013). These outcomes are either tangible, such as pay, or intangible, such as positive feedback. Employees perceive procedural justice when they feel they can voice their opinion regarding the process. Employees also believe procedures are fair when they are consistent, accurate, ethical, and lack bias (Colquitt et al., 2013). Interactional justice focuses on the way in which an individual is treated when decisions are made; individuals feel they are being treated fairly when employers provide explanations for decisions and treat employees with dignity, respect, and sensitivity (Colquitt *et al.*, 2013).
- 3) The climate of the organisation is determined by the perceptions of the employees about the working environment. So, it is the managers who can encourage team work, collaboration and dedication at work. The satisfied employees which can be achieved through bringing up organisational justice as mentioned above, can build long lasting positive perceptions about the organisation which ultimately results in commitment and OCB.
- 4) The values, norms, policies and procedures shape the culture of an organisation. The culture of creativity and innovation can take place if there is organisational commitment. So, managers need to reinforce the mission, vision and values of the

organisation in different meetings and training sessions and should link the individual tasks of the employees to the bigger goals of the universities to make them feel part of the bigger mission. It results in affective commitment and OCB.

- 5) Managers need to ensure mentoring and coaching to the staff and provide continuous feedback for continuous improvement as employees during their interviews put a huge emphasis on training and learning and CPD activities which help them to develop personally and professionally.
- 6) It has been seen in the research findings that employees feel more encouraged, engaged, and participative if managers use participative or democratic management style in the universities. Particularly the teaching faculty wants to be involved in the decision making regarding the curriculum and teaching activities, Hence, managers need to ensure that the participative management style is employed in the organisations.
- 7) Finally, to encourage OCB top management such as university vice chancellors, head of departments and managers can exemplify certain behaviours such as punctuality, regularity, team working and bringing innovative ideas etc.

Moreover, the management needs to support employees and encourage favourable organisational citizenship behaviour enhanced by job satisfaction. Top management is required to understand the processes of improving the level of commitment of the employees to increase the organisational citizenship behaviour through promoting organisational justice, encouraging, and inspiring management style (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Waddock and Parallel, 2004; Sen *et al.*, 2006; Singh *et al.*, 2008; Al Zeifiti and Mohamad, 2017; Hendri, 2019; Supriya and Dadhabhai, 2020). As hoped, the study's findings will help the university top management in collaborating with the employees for mutual understanding of concepts related to enriching the level of commitment of the employees.

The employees and other university stakeholders, who understand the university's strengths and weaknesses, shall take correct decisions. It helps in implementing activities of organisational commitment favourable in responding to the developmental performance needs of employees. Practically, managers can create an environment of trustworthiness and ensure organisational justice providing fair opportunities to employees that contribute to their individual performance. Moreover, top management should be more responsive to

organisational citizenship behaviour by considering that responsiveness is the most significant influence on the organisation's performance. Notably, the current study offers to support managers in comprehending the employee perceptions of organisational commitment.

It has been discussed above that organisational commitment as the main construct of organisational citizenship behaviour (Stanley *et al.*, 2002; Haque *et al.*, 2019; Ingsih *et al.*, 2020) improves employee behaviour as they emotionally attach and identify themselves with the organisation (Muchinsky, 2006; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020). It helps to build positive perceptions in the mind of employees (Ryan and Organ, 1995; El-Nahas *et al.*, 2013; Prasetio *et al.*, 2017; Massoudi *et al.*, 2020). Hence, it would be beneficial for the management to consider the emotional aspect of organisational commitment to yield favourable organisational performance.

Incorporating favourable organisational commitment has been challenging as it is subjective to each behaviour (Grawe *et al.*, 2012; Fischer *et al.*, 2020; Djaelani *et al.*, 2021), and the top management strives to in gain and model favourable employee behaviour. (Meyer *et al.*, 2002; Bakotic, 2016; Ibrahim and Daniel, 2019; Moneva *et al.*, 2020). Hence, the current study's findings are of utmost significance for the university's decision-makers and the top management of the university play a significant role in developing the organisational processes and operations. Ultimately, it ensures a favourable organisational climate that impacts individual performance.

By showing the critical elements of favourable organisational commitment (organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate, and management style) this study shall assist various university administrators, particularly faculty management, understand the significant aspects of organisational commitment. This study offers valuable guidelines for university leaders (deans, board of directors) and faculty members who are cautious of identifying which elements constitute an organisational commitment. Moreover, it requires establishing a clear overview of their management practices and consistent organisational commitment, favourable to organisational citizenship behaviour. It also contributes to bridging the gap between academia and management through establishing organisational commitment as the main component leading to organisational citizenship behaviour and individual performance (Ehrhart, 2004; Vondey, 2010; Romi and Ahman,

2020). This primary research aim is of helping the university administration and teachers create a positive organisational commitment to enhancing OCB and organisational performance.

This research represents a deeper understanding of ‘organisational commitment’ concepts, the main factors influencing organisational citizenship behaviour and resulting in organisational and individual performance. The scale of organisational commitment emphasises that commitment is a stimulus for employees’ behavioural and motivation for improving employees’ perceptions for creating favourable organisational citizenship behaviour and positive performance of the organisation. The organisations can adapt the organisational commitment scale and relevant constructs inculcated into the research study as essential guidelines and checklists for examining the scope of organisational activities. Moreover, university management may be encouraged to compete internationally with enhanced organisational performance.

This research suggests that for achieving the competitive advantages, the corporation could have a clear understanding of the favourable commitment level, which is influenced through main aspects of organisational structure, organisational culture, organisational justice, organisational climate, and management style. The faculty members revealed that organisational commitment plays a vital role in enhancing the organisation’s performance. The outcomes of the current study suggest that university management should be cautious in orchestrating favourable organisational commitment in evoking attention and desired performance.

The organisational structure has been another element that influences favourable organisational commitment. This would result in insight that would make major contributions to university management in understanding those factors impacted by organisational structure (Katsikea *et al.*, 2011; Yigit, 2016; Hardiningsih *et al.*, 2020). The organisation’s structure has been becoming significant as a means of differentiation as requirements of the current employees have been changed due to the Covid-19 impacts. The organisational structure should include the MIS and other IT experts to fulfil ‘online working’ needs and a flexible working environment at the university. The job responsibilities and the roles for employees could be redefined as the core activities under the organisational structure. Organisational commitment develops a feeling of obligations, and employees also analyse the cost of leaving the organisation. Hence, during the pandemic, this aspect of commitment became more functional

and to hand have been ways to communicate the commitment level of the organisation with stakeholders. The current study's finding proposes that the top management should also understand the significant influences of organisational structure. The organisational structure should be refined and updated to enhance the organisation's performance.

The resulting significant relationships between favourable organisational commitment and organisational culture suggest that the management may emphasise cultural values to promote commitment in the employees. University's culture inculcates the values, beliefs promoted by the management and practices that guide the employees' actions and trigger commitment (Asree *et al.*, 2010; Jadhav *et al.*, 2017; Soelton *et al.*, 2020). The top management should consider the organisational culture as it supports employee perceptions and strategically enhances organisational citizenship behaviour. Therefore, the current study's findings offer practical guidelines and scales in modifying and selecting organisational culture that may enhance the employees' organisational commitment and citizenship behaviour to improve the organisation's performance.

Organisational justice is observed to be another factor that influences favourable organisational commitment. This would result in insight that could make major contributions to university management to understand the positive effects of organisational justice (Mowday *et al.*, 1979; Wall and Cook, 1980; Lambert, 2003; Polatacan and Cansoy, 2019; Tayyaba and Shenlei, 2020). The justice system in the organisation has become significant as it refers to employees' perceptions of fairness that include the provision of equal opportunities, information, rewards (distributive justice), training and relationships of employees. It increases the employee's satisfaction if the perceptions of justice are favourable, enhancing organisational commitment and citizenship behaviour and results in the organisation's enhanced performance. The fair rules and policies for all the staff are recommended to be designed to improve perceptions of organisational justice. The findings of the current study offer that the top management should also understand the significant influence of organisational justice on organisational commitment, which should be refined and updated to enhance the organisational performance. Organisational climate is observed to be another factor that influences favourable organisational commitment. This would result in insight that could make major contributions to university management to understand the positive effects of the organisational climate (Payne and Huffman, 2005; Genty, 2017; Haldorai *et al.*, 2020). The climate in the organisation has been becoming significant to provide a favourable commitment for employees to motivate

the employee and increase the employee's level of satisfaction, which will enhance organisational citizenship behaviour and results in improved performance of the organisation. The current study's findings suggest that the top management should also understand the significant influences of organisational climate. The organisational climate should be refined and updated to enhance individual and organisational performance.

Management style is observed to be another factor that influences favourable organisational commitment. This would result in insight that could make major contributions to university management to understand the positive effects of the management style (Phatak, 1986; Hofstede, 1991; Hampden-Turner and Trompenaars, 1998; Sani *et al.*, 2019). The top management style in the organisation has been becoming significant because showing a positive style of management to the employees motivate not only the employee but also increase the level of satisfaction of the employee who would enhance the organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour and results into the enhanced performance of the organisation. The positive management style for all the staff is recommended to be considered as effective to improve the organisational commitment.

This study observed that favourable organisational commitment influences employees' organisational citizenship behaviour. This research finding suggests that the university top management may emphasise organisational commitment to influence the behaviours of the employees to become more favourable due to an enhanced level of organisational commitment (Chhabra, 2014; Nwibere, 2014; Indarti *et al.*, 2017; Hassi, 2019; Fischer *et al.*, 2020; Kaur *et al.*, 2020; Chang *et al.*, 2021; Utami *et al.*, 2021). In addition, the provision of resources to the employees improves their perceptions about the organisation. It increases the intangible asset of commitment, improving organisational citizenship behaviour and performance. For example, the attitude of employees to perform additional duties beyond their formal job responsibilities is considered a positive element to achieve the higher goals of the organisation. Therefore, committed employees tend to show organisational citizenship behaviour. This study also reflects that favourable organisational citizenship behaviour influences individual and organisational performances. These research findings propose that the university management may emphasise organisational citizenship behaviour as behaviours of the employees become more favourable due to an enhanced level of commitment in employees.

5.3. RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The conceptualisations of organisational commitment are represented in the current study as a preliminary foray addressing the roles of organisational commitment on organisational citizenship behaviour and performance. Nevertheless, the interpretation of these research findings could be made in the light of some significant limitations relevant to future research relating to methods of the sampling and analyses, as explained below.

The understanding of organisational commitment's constructs and some of the antecedents and consequences has been attempted in this study. However, the research findings have not been described without certain limitations. The limitation of the study has been grouped in two sub-sections: sampling/analyses method and the levels of measurement.

The present research study has been carried out in only one setting confined to the context of universities in Pakistan. The findings might not be the same in a different contextual setting. Nonetheless, the researcher established the measurement research items as per the previous qualitative research studies and literature of various settings. Still, distinct aspects of Pakistani universities would affect to lesser or greater degrees on a few aspects of the concepts researched in this study. Hence, it is recommended for future research studies to consider some other contextual settings in other countries to repeat this research for testing generalisability of outcomes (the external validities) (refer to Section 8.2.1.3, theory generalisability and testing).

This study has been conducted in both public and private organisations in terms of the context of this research. Therefore, a single type of organisational structure might be considered in future studies. More empirical research may be performed in replicating the current research in different research settings.

Another research limitation related to current research is the number and sample categories that have been used. There was a mix of university faculty members (senior lectures, professors, visiting faculty, government employees and private contractors) and the administrative staff. Future research may replicate the current study with a different set of employees' domains and numbers of respondents. It is also recommended to choose one particular group of employees that might be administrative staff only or teaching faculty with a specific range of experience. Therefore, it could also cause reservations regarding the generalisability capacity of the

research findings (Churchill, 1999; Odhiambo, 2019).

The research design may also be another limitation of the present study. The current study uses semi-structured interviews with university faculty members and administration from Pakistani universities to explore their feelings, experiences, beliefs and understandings. Hence, the qualitative questions employed in the study could be aligned to a measurement scale in the form of a survey. Hence, it is also recommended to conduct further research using both qualitative and quantitative methods.

During the phase of the quantitative study, a lack in accessing complete research sampling led the study to employ a non-probabilistic technique of sampling (i.e., convenience type of the sample). In contrast, the subjects have been selected based on proximity and accessibility to a research scholar. The probabilistic sampling approach is employed, generally enabling researchers in estimating amounts of errors in sampling (Churchill, 1996). The probabilistic sampling method is adopted to eliminate potential biases related to the generalisability and validity of scale (Churchill, 1999; Kostyk *et al.*, 2021).

This research has presented a one-sided view from university faculty members and administrative staff. This study measured the judgments of the respondent related to the university teaching system. The incorporations of students, and other university beneficiaries would increase the scope of the study. In terms of results, this might produce different outcomes. However, based on the resources available, it put this beyond the research scope.

5.3.1. Future research avenues

The current research focuses on favourable organisational commitment, its antecedents and its relationship with organisational citizenship behaviour and performance of the organisation and individual, opening several routes possible for future study. This research section proposes a few suggestions in extending the current knowledge in the literature related to, organisational commitment, organisational citizenship behaviour and individual/organisational performance.

Moreover, this research used multiple constructs and applied these in a higher education setting in Pakistan. Scholars willing to research the university educational setting in the UK may

investigate reliable and validated measurements. This study shows a first effort in conceptualising a favourable organisational commitment and the antecedents and consequences in the educational setting in Pakistan. Therefore, future research could be further well developed in terms of organisational commitment concepts in the educational setting, but various other stakeholders can be considered. It could be helpful also of considering multiple different services modes. In such respect, further research should also investigate whether the phenomenon of favourable organisational commitment construct modifies the relationships that could differ from the dimensions of organisational commitment under study. Moreover, future research can investigate whether the associations found in the present study are sustained in different countries.

The current research employed university employees' perceptions about organisational commitment, and future research studies may investigate supplementary forms of organisational commitment in helping the generalisability of concepts described. Furthermore, this research may be a base for a prospective study to develop favourable organisational commitment from students and other stakeholder's perspectives. Sustaining organisational commitment would also be studied from the perspective of management. Moreover, to investigate the generalisability, a comparison between perceptions of faculty and administration could also give insights into the phenomenon of organisational commitment.

This research has been a pioneering effort examining the associations between favourable organisational commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour in the university context of Pakistan. It can be attempted to empirically assess the organisational commitment by employing mixed-methods research techniques to explore and validate the conceptual research model by utilising the SEM.

This study based on its scope and context has the opportunity to be published in the following journals:

- Journal of Management
- Journal of business research
- Academy of management perspective
- Academy of management
- Asia pacific business review

The author will explore more avenues where the study findings can be showcased, and more research platforms shall be explored to enhance the study.

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APPENDIXES

Appendix 1:

Interview protocol: Universities administration and faculty interview questions sheet (Definition of constructs, study questions and key references)

Introduction: My name is Iqra Abbas, and I am currently pursuing my PhD at University of the West of Scotland London Campus. I have completed my MBA in Human Resource Management at University of Bedfordshire with a Distinction. I have also achieved my MSC in International Business Management. I am currently working as Senior Lecturer and Curriculum lead at London Professional College.

Aim of the research: This study is being conducted to examine the **the influence of Organisational Commitment on Organisational Citizenship behavior: A study of employees' perception in the context of a university setting in Pakistan.**

The traits of influencing the organisational commitment on organisational citizenship behaviour had been very helpful for us to complete the cited research work in context of a university setting in Pakistan. This qualitative interview protocol may need yours twenty to thirty minutes. The qualitative interview protocol basically consists of three sections, first section is regarding the respondent's profile, second section is regarding the details of university and third section is regarding the responses to the variables of interview protocol.

NOTE:

It is testified that the dialogue conducted shall remain confidential. The audio conversation of the interview protocol may also be kept as a guarantee of keeping the confidentiality of this interview. Comment to any question of the interview may be avoided if you feel uncomfortable and that question may be bypassed. The audio recording may also be stopped or deleted at any point of interview protocol.

Respondent Profile

Please respond to the following by either writing in the blank space provided or choosing the appropriate option.

(Name of University.....

1.1. Name

1.2. Designation

1.3. Gender (1. Male, 2. Female)

1.4. What is yours age group?

1. Under 22 Years
2. 22 to 30 years
3. 30 to 40 years
4. Above 40 years

1.5. What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?

1. Below Bachelors
2. Bachelors/Sixteen Years of Education
3. Masters/Eighteen Years of Education
4. Doctorate/Ph.D. or above

1.6. How long have you been with the university?

1. Less than 5 years
2. 5 years to 10 years
3. 10 years to 15 years
4. 16 years and above

2.1. What type of organisation do you belong to? *

1. Government organisation
2. Private organisation

Section Three - Responses

Constructs	Qualitative questions	Major references
ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT (OCM):	<p>How employees are controlled systematically to gain the organisational commitment?</p> <p>To what extent, the university organisational structure controls the organisational commitment?</p> <p>To what extent organisational structure improves the attitude and behaviour of employees for organisational commitment?</p>	Herscovitch and Meyer, 2001, Organ, 1988, Ryan and Organ, 1995
ANTECEDENTS OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT		
ORGANISATIONAL CSR (OCSR):	<p>To what extent social activities for employees make them committed to the university?</p> <p>Do you think, the employees are self-esteemed by the policies of CSR and become more committed?</p> <p>To what extent employees associate themselves to activities of CSR to boost organisational commitment?</p>	Davis, 1960; Meyer and Allen, 1990; Mael and Ashforth, 1989; Peterson, 2004; Mowday <i>et al.</i> , 1979
ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE (OS):	<p>To what extent university organisational structure impacts the activities of CSR?</p> <p>Do you think the organisational structure contains the positions of social experts to perform the activities of CSR?</p> <p>[To what extent the organisational structure of the university implements the solution to social issues?</p> <p>How the organisational structure of the university fulfils the requirements of corporate policy?</p>	Jones, 1995; Freeman, 1984; Donaldson, and Preston, 1995; Moskowitz, 1972; Werther and Chandler, 2006; Abouzeid and Weaver 1978; Arlow and Gannon, 1982
ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE (OC):	<p>Do you think the organisational culture is task oriented to achieve the CSR goals of organisation?</p>	Schein, E. (1999); Fischer, A.H. and Van Vianen, A.E.M. (2002); Alas, R. and

ORGANISATIONAL JUSTICE (OJ):	To what extent the rewarding system exists in organisational culture to give the social benefits to employees?	Vadi, M. (2006); Jaeger, A.J. and Thornton, C.H. (2008)
	Do you think the organisational culture is socially responsible?	
	To what extent university public support system exists to perform activities of CSR?	
	Are employees respectfully treated by the internal activities of CSR?	Colquitt and Jackson 2002; Bies and Tyler, 1990; Adams, 1963; Lee, 2001
ORGANISATIONAL CLIMATE (OCL):	To what extent required information are provided to every employee regarding CSR in the organisation?	
	To what extent correct decisions are made as per fairness policy regarding CSR in the organisation?	
	How fair reward system is adapted in the organisation to improve social life of the employees?	
	To what extent decision making by top management fulfils the requirements of organisational CSR?	Vidaver-Cohen, 1998; Sen and Bhattacharya, 2004; Kramer and Porter, 2006; Maignan and Ferrell, 2005; Dolnicar and Pomeroy, 2009; Balmer and Greyser, 2011; Arvidsson, 2010; Parguel and Larceneux, 2011; Carroll, 1991
EMPLOYEE BEHAVIOUR (EB):	In your opinion, do you think ethical corporate policies are implemented to incorporate activities of CSR?	
	How organisational climate supports the corporate behaviour of employees by communicating activities of CSR?	
	To what extent employees are encouraged to actively participate in the activities of CSR?	
MANAGEMENT STYLE (MS)	Do you think, employees' objectives are in line with the organisational CSR?	Collier and Esteban, 2007; Davis, 1973; Heslin and Ochoa, 2008
	To what extent employee behaviour is improved by fulfilling the social requirements of gratuity or bonuses etc.?	
	To what extent employees are retained by maintaining social responsibilities and corporate behaviour?	
CONSEQUENCES OF ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT	To what extent, top management involve themselves in activities of CSR?	Waldman and Javidan, 2008a; Waldman and House, 2008b; Den Hartog and De Hoogh, 2008
	Do you think, the organisational CSR is derived by personal morality of the management?	
	To what extent management works as per ethical style by considering social issues?	

ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR (OCB):	<p>How would you describe the organisational commitment improves the organisational citizenship behaviour?</p> <p>Do you think the employees perform extra work voluntarily in the organisation?</p> <p>Do you think employees are committed to distinguish themselves to achieve the organisational citizenship behaviour?</p>	<p>Herscovitch and Meyer 2001; Organ, 1988; Ryan and Organ, 1995</p>
INDIVIDUAL PERFORMANCE (IP):	<p>Do you think, you are concerned with your present job?</p> <p>How would you describe the optional activities you perform to improve your job performance?</p>	<p>Paullay and Stone 1994; Organ, 1988; Kanungo,1982b</p>
ORGANISATIONAL PERFORMANCE (OP):	<p>Do you think, the employees perform volunteer activities for organisation to improve organisational performance?</p> <p>To what extent employee's behaviour are motivated to perform activities beyond job responsibilities?</p> <p>In your opinion what optional volunteer activities you may perform to boost organisational performance?</p>	<p>Organ <i>et al.</i>, 2006; Hall <i>et al.</i>, 2009; Van Dyne, 1994; Hag and Jahangir, 2004</p>
MODERATORS OF OC AND OCB		
JOB SATISFACTION (JS):	<p>To what extent you are satisfied from your job?</p> <p>To what extent you are committed to the organisation?</p> <p>To what extent you perform the tasks in the organisation beyond the formal job responsibilities?</p> <p>To what extent job satisfaction improves the relationship between job commitment and organisational citizenship behaviour?</p>	<p>Penner <i>et al.</i>, 1997; Tang <i>et al.</i>, 1998; Ryan, and Organ 1995; Chu <i>et al.</i>, 2005; Podsakoff <i>et al.</i>, 2003</p>

Appendix 2

Questionnaire – Pakistani Higher education Institution (Institutes of Reference)

Research Aim:

This study is being conducted to examine **the influence of Organisational Commitment on Organisational Citizenship behavior: A study of employees' perception in the context of a university setting in Pakistan**. The traits of influencing the organisational commitment on organisational citizenship behaviour had been very helpful for us to complete the cited research work in context of a university setting in Pakistan.

The co-operation of the survey respondent has the core values in the completion of this study project. Yours help in this study will play a vital role in the accomplishment of the data collection and investigation of the work. You can answer the questions by ticking only **one box** from the "Likert Scales" of "strongly disagree, somewhat-disagree-t disagree-neutral-somewhat agree-agree-strongly agree".

This questionnaire is being filled by respondents help as a volunteer. The data collected during this study from you will be kept private and responses of the survey will be offered in the form of aggregated amount without showing the name of single respondent. The survey work may take up to 15 minutes in completion.

Much gratitude for your contribution in this survey work.

Iqra Abbas
 University of the West of Scotland
 London Campus, United Kingdom

Research Variables

- Below are the statements of the university sector. Please indicate your general impressions about your **university's organisational structure**.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Our university is having well defined organisational structure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The organisational structure impacts on the activities of CSR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
University is having the positions of the social experts to manage the activities of CSR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
University organisational structure addresses the social issues	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
University organisational structure fulfil the requirements of the corporate policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Almost all the required positions are filled as per organisational structure	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

2. Please indicate your general impressions about your **university's organisational culture**.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Organisational culture of the university is encouraging for employees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organisational culture of the university is task oriented	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
My university performs socially responsible activities towards stakeholders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rewarding system is present in my university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The university has a socially responsible culture	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
University public support system exists to perform activities of CSR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

3. Please indicate your general impressions about your **university's organisational justice**. (Organisational justice refers to the organisation members' perceptions of whether the organisation that they are part of is treating them fairly (Greenberg 1990).

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
My university follows all the rules to ensure a fair treatment of all the employees.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees are treated respectfully	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Required information is provided to all the employee	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Job decisions made by the leaders are unbiased	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Fair reward system is adapted in the organisation to improve social life of the employees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Our university is having equal opportunity policy	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organisational justice motivates the employees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

4. Please indicate your general impressions about your **university's organisational climate**.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The organisational climate of my university is encouraging to progress	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Decision making by top management considers their social responsibility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ethical policies and activities are implemented to incorporate activities of CSR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organisational climate supports the corporate behaviour of employees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees are encouraged to actively participate in the activities of CSR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organisational climate is motivating for all employees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The organisational climate is constructive for employees to perform their tasks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

5. Please indicate your general impressions about your **university's employee behaviour**

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
The employee's behaviour in my university is encouraging	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The employee objectives are in line with the set objectives of the university and the organisational CSR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The social benefits of gratuity and bonuses are provided to improve the behaviour of employees in my university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The employees in the university are retained by maintaining the social responsibilities and corporate behaviour	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The employee's behaviour in the university is improved through different training programs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Policies regarding management of employee's behaviour exist in my university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

6. Please indicate your general impressions about the **management style of the university**.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

Strongly disagree Disagree Somewhat disagree Neutral Somewhat agree Agree Strongly agree

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Management style of my university is helpful towards employee performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Management team of my university involve themselves in activities of CSR	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organisational CSR is derived by personal mortality of the management of university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Management of university works as per ethical style which considers social issues	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Management style is monitored and controlled through policies by leaders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The management style of my university motivates the employees	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

7. Please indicate your general impressions about the **activities of CSR** in your university.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Different CSR activities take place in my university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Social activities for employees in the university make them committed by increasing the engagement	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees become self-esteemed through the policies of CSR and become more committed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
CSR activities help to attract students and build relationships with various stakeholders	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees associate themselves to the activities of CSR and it helps to boost organisational commitment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Policies regarding CSR exist in my university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
CSR activities and initiatives motivate the employees at large	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

8. Please indicate your general impressions about your **organisational commitment**.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Organisational structure improved the attitude and behaviour of employees for organisational commitment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Management style impacts the organisational commitment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees are controlled systematically by HR practices to gain the organisational commitment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
HRM practices (for example, holiday policy and training etc) also impact commitment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Psychological needs of employees are fulfilled	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Committed employees yield higher performance outcomes in my university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

9. Please indicate your general impressions about your **organisational citizenship behaviour**

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
Employees tends to do extra work beyond university timing without any benefit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The organisational commitment improves the organisational citizenship behaviour	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees do volunteer activities for the organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees are committed to organisation to distinguish themselves in the OCB	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees do extra activities for the university online at home in Covid-19 pandemic	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees are having higher motivational level to perform extra work beyond the job responsibilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

10. Please indicate your general impressions about the **job satisfaction**.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
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I am happy with the job role they have been assigned for	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employees are satisfied due to rewarding and promotional programs in the university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The employees both material and psychological needs are fulfilled in the organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am satisfied with the current position	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am committed to my organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I tend to perform the tasks of the organisation beyond the formal job responsibilities.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

11. Please indicate your general impressions about **Individual performance**.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

Strongly disagree Disagree Somewhat disagree Neutral Somewhat agree Agree Strongly agree

Better performance at work increases self-esteem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Individual's job commitment and job involvement impacts the performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Individual engage and pre-occupy to responsibilities given to them	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I am having no issues about my job in the university	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I happily work on my call of duty	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I perform optional extra activities for the university which impacts my job performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

12. Please indicate your general impressions about your **organisational performance**.

Tick the box that best describes your opinion.

Strongly disagree Disagree Somewhat disagree Neutral Somewhat agree Agree Strongly agree

University can attain its main objectives	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
University economic situation is efficient	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The quality of work procedures is consistent across all departments	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Employee's behaviour is motivated to perform activities beyond job responsibilities which ultimately impacts organisational performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I prefer to perform optional volunteer activities to boost organisational performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

It is rare to make big mistakes when performing tasks at my organisation

In order to get fully understanding about your opinion, please answer the following questions.

1. What is your gender?

- Female Male
 Prefer not to say

2. What is your age group?

- Under 25 Years 25 - 30 years
 30 - 40 years Above 40 years

3. What is the highest degree or level of education you have completed?

- Below bachelor Bachelor
 Masters Ph.D./ Doctorate

4. How long you have been with the university?

- Less than 5 years 5 - 10 years
 10 - 15 years 16 years and above

5. What is your employment status?

- Chancellor or vice chancellor Registrar/ Assistant registrar Rector
 Senior professor Lecturer Staff member
Other

I would like to thank you again for your kind cooperation and valuable time.